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a Novel Integration of
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Parts I and II

WP6: Assessing European labour market inequalities from different perspectives

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D6.4 - Part I

Patterns of divergence and convergence,
distribution and institutional capacity

Patterns of EU convergence and divergence
focussing on income and income distribution

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Uneven Paths to Prosperity: Club Convergence and Regional Disparities in Income, Inequality, and Poverty Across the EU

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Abstract

This paper employs Phillips and Sul's (2007) nonlinear dynamic factor model to discern patterns of EU-27 regional convergence in the standard of living as measured by GDP per capita, poverty and income inequality. It finds that the hypothesis of overall income convergence is rejected at the regional level, whereas that of club convergence is supported. The number and the composition of clubs are significantly influenced by the period considered and the length of the time series. The club convergence analysis of the GDP per capita from 2000 to 2023, reveals three clubs with the largest club including regions with medium levels of GDP per capita. After 2007, the clubs' transition paths show a moderate diverging trend: The club systematically above the cross-country mean diverges upward from the mean, whereas the lower one level diverges downwards. Capital regions and metropolitan areas are generally concentrated in the highest club, suggesting a tendency towards polarisation following the urban-rural divide. The likelihood of being part of the high-income club is positively correlated with the share of manufacturing and high-end/high-skill services. By contrast, a large share of the low-skill service sector negatively affects such a likelihood. Additionally, digital transformation, globalisation and migration are all associated with a higher probability of being in the high-income club. To provide a more comprehensive picture of standards of living, gaps in readily available indicators of poverty and income inequality are closed through statistical techniques applied to EU-SILC data. Similar to GDP per capita, the hypothesis of overall convergence in income poverty and inequality is rejected, whereas club convergence is confirmed. For both indicators, a higher number of clubs than for income is identified. The transition paths of the two largest clubs—which cover the majority of EU regions—remain relatively stable and close to the mean, however, smaller clubs show strong separating dynamics, either towards higher or lower levels of poverty and inequality. Better labour market and educational outcomes are associated with a greater probability of being in low-poverty and low-inequality clubs and appear better predictors of membership in low-poverty and low-inequality clubs than globalisation and migration. Overall, the paper suggests that the process of EU convergence has not stopped, however regional dynamics are heterogeneous.

Keywords: Club convergence, Dynamic factor model, EU integration, Income, NUTS 2 regions, Inequality, Poverty

JEL: R11, O47, C21, I32

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Abbreviations

AROP	At-risk-of-poverty
AROPE	At-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion
CEE	Central and Eastern European
EA	Euro Area
EMU	Economic and Monetary Union
ESPON	European Territorial Observatory Network
EU	European Union
EU15	Member States accessed before 2004
EU13	Member States accessed after 2004
GDP	Gross domestic product
GVA	Gross Value Added
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
ML	Maximum Likelihood
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
NWE	Northern and Western Europe
OLR	Ordinal logistic regression
PS	Phillips and Sul
PPS	Purchasing Power Standard
SE	Southern European
VLT	von Lyncker and Thoennesen

Introduction

The GI-NI project identifies three transformations as being crucial in terms of their societal and economic impact: i) the rapid emergence and diffusion of digital technologies; ii) the new forms of international trade and foreign investment, including global production networks and fragmentation of production; iii) the rapid increases in migration.¹ These changes come with real opportunities but also challenges to prosperity and social fairness, which are at the heart of the European integration and the EU Social Model. In this context, the concept of upward economic convergence and social cohesion are key.

The body of economic literature on convergence has largely been shaped by the neoclassical concept of β -convergence, which suggests that low-income countries grow at a faster rate than high-income countries, eventually catching up with them over time.² This idea is at the heart of EU economic convergence driven by EU integration. The single market by allowing free movement of people, capital, goods and services can trigger catching up. As highlighted in Alcidi (2018a) convergence has always been considered the fundamental economic mechanism and precondition for achieving EU socio-economic cohesion. The latter is an explicit objective of the EU, as formulated in Article 130a of the Single European Act (1986): “[I]n order to promote its overall harmonious development, the Community shall develop and pursue its actions leading to the strengthening of its economic and social cohesion”. Against this potential, the Act recognises that the creation of the internal market would lead to cross-border relocation of resources and productive activities and some countries and regions would be negatively affected. This consideration constituted the ground for the creation of the European Structural Funds as well as the backbone of the EU Cohesion Policy intended to act against regional disparities, on the one hand by devising redistributive measures, on the other hand by equipping poorer regions with the tools to improve their potential growth (and hence their productivity).

As suggested in Eurofound (2023), despite the importance of convergence within the EU policy debate, neither a common definition of convergence nor a unique approach to measuring it exists. Indeed, different statistical methods are adopted.³ In practice, the concepts of β -convergence and σ -convergence⁴ are assumed to offer useful information about outcomes associated with EU integration, economic shocks, and EU policies.

However, over the years, β -convergence has faced significant criticism in the literature. Critics highlight several conceptual issues, ranging from the assumption of a common steady-state (Bernard and Durlauf, 1995, 1996), the underlying notion of equilibrium (Fingleton and McCombie, 1999), the neglect of distributional dynamics (Quah, 1993), and the lack of consideration for local characteristics (Martin and Sunley, 1998). Overall, most empirical studies have focused on documenting convergence, rather than delving into the underlying factors that drive this economic process. In addition, the main focus has been on income, neglecting other indicators that are relevant to capture the development in the standards of living, using countries as the main unit of analysis.

More recently, the literature on EU convergence has evolved and expanded dramatically driven, on one hand, by the interest in understanding the impact of EU enlargements and the deepening of the EU integration process, and, on the other hand, by new empirical techniques able to capture more

¹ For conciseness, these three transformations will be named digital transformation, globalisation and migration.

² The concept formalised in Barro and Sala-i-Martin (1990) builds on the growth equation that derives from the transition path of the neoclassical growth model for closed economies as in Solow (1956).

³ For an overview of the different methodologies please see Section 1.1.

⁴ While β -convergence looks at whether poorer economies are growing faster than richer ones, σ -convergence refers to a reduction in the dispersion (or variance) of economic indicators.

nuanced developments in the convergence processes using more granular data. Furthermore, an increasing interest in understanding the role of specific, local factors in affecting convergence and the outcomes of EU cohesion policies has spurred a growing interest in the spatial dimension, hence focussing the analysis on regions or even smaller spatial units.

Against this background, the paper addresses three main questions: i) How has the process of EU convergence in standards of living evolved over the last two decades? ii) Have recent trends such as digital transformation, globalisation and migration affected it? iii) Do geographical factors (e.g., a region including the capital and/or a high number of metropolitan areas or being predominantly urban or rural) play a significant role?

The focus on major trends like digital transformation, globalisation, and migration stems from their traditional association with innovation, economic openness, and higher economic growth in the literature. As income rises, it is generally expected that poverty declines and inequality may also reduce. However, these trends have recently faced extensive criticism for their perceived negative social impacts, such as increasing poverty and inequality, becoming central issues in a polarised political debate. The reality is more nuanced, with limited evidence supporting such claims. The existing literature is relatively sparse and does not yield clear-cut or robust results. For instance, Sánchez-López et al. (2019) who investigated the influence on inequality exerted by trade and financial globalisation and technological development over the period 2005-2015 in 29 European Member States find that both trade globalisation and the degree of technological development are associated with a reduction in inequality, while financial globalisation is associated with an increase in inequality. Similar results were reported by Jaumotte et al. (2008). More recently Richiardi et al. (2024) investigated the impact of digital transformation in the EU on individual employment outcomes, wage growth, and income inequality, during the decade 2010-2019. While they identified vulnerabilities among workers "left behind" by digital transformation, the overall effects on inequality were limited.

The focus on spatial factors is driven by recent documented patterns in the EU. Eurofound (2023b) argues that despite the high priority given in policy to achieving geographically balanced economic development, gaps in living conditions still exist between rural and urban areas and in some cases, these gaps are growing. Such differences in social, political, cultural and economic outcomes may pose a serious threat to social cohesion in Europe. More recently, the Ninth EU Cohesion Report (European Commission, 2024) documents stark differences in economic and social development, opportunities, and living standards between urban and non-urban regions. The report also highlights that sub-national economic development is often characterised by strong polarisation between capital regions and large metropolitan centres on the one hand, and regions with lower population density on the other. Furthermore, the national convergence process is found sometimes overshadowed by increasing sub-national disparities, notably between large metropolitan areas and other regions, as well as by regions lagging behind, often caught in a 'development trap'.

The paper contributes to the recent literature in threefold ways. First, it examines regional convergence dynamics over an extended period (2000-2023) using the concept of club convergence. This was first introduced by Baumol (1986) to capture time dynamics, assuming different patterns across clusters of regions gradually converging toward a common steady state. This hypothesis is tested not only on income but also on poverty and inequality, which are less explored in the literature

yet crucial indicators for understanding distributional aspects⁵ and hence capture living standards comprehensively.⁶

Second, the paper delves into the factors influencing these convergence dynamics, with a specific focus on digital transformation, globalisation, and migration. This approach moves beyond the traditional emphasis on the state of convergence to explore the potential drivers of both upward and downward convergence. Additionally, by investigating these three trends, the study contributes valuable insights to the ongoing policy debate.

Third, the paper extends the coverage of the relevant time series, both in the cross-section and cross-time dimension, enabling a more comprehensive regional analysis. Overcoming limitations in regional data, which is a significant challenge in convergence studies,⁷ this approach provides a more detailed and robust assessment of regional convergence across the EU.

Once regional data on poverty and inequality series are enriched beyond the readily available ones, the paper uses a two-step empirical approach, as described by Bartowska and Riedl (2012). In the first step, a dynamic clustering methodology is applied to analyse club convergence or divergence in GDP in three key areas: GDP per capita in PPS, poverty (measured by the at-risk-of-poverty rate, AROP) and income inequality (measured by the income quintile share ratio, S80/S20). The existence of clusters is evaluated using the time-varying factor model introduced by Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009), which accounts for both individual (in this case, regional) and transitional variations. The second step utilises an ordered logit model to examine the factors that have a statistically significant impact on the formation of convergence clubs. The main dataset spans from 2000 to 2023 thus, covering significant events such as the EU enlargements of 2004, 2007 and 2013⁸, the financial crisis, the sovereign debt crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic. Shorter time series are available for the inequality and poverty indicators, spanning from 2008 (2005) to 2023 (with income reference period, respectively, of 2004-2022 and 2007-2022).

The paper has a rich set of empirical findings, the main ones are the following. The number and the composition of clubs are significantly influenced by the period considered and the length of the time series. The club convergence analysis of income per capita suggests moderate diverging tendencies, with the higher income slightly diverging from the mean upwards, and the lowest one marginally diverging from the mean downwards. Capital regions and metropolitan areas are generally concentrated in the highest-income club, suggesting a tendency towards urban-rural polarisation. The likelihood of being part of the high-income club is positively affected by a larger share of the population with higher education and the share of manufacturing and high-end/high-skill services. Indicators of technological change, globalisation and migration are all associated with a higher probability of being in the high-income club. Similar to GDP per capita, the hypothesis of overall convergence in income inequality and poverty is rejected at regional levels, while club convergence is confirmed. For both indicators, more clubs than for income are identified. In both cases, the two largest clubs—encompassing the large majority of EU regions—remain relatively stable and close to the mean. However, smaller clubs appear to drift far away from the mean (toward high and lower club

⁵ As suggested by Milanovic and Van der Weide (2014): “the literature on the relationship between growth and income inequality focuses exclusively on the effects on average incomes, suggesting that there has been little interest in the specific parts of the income distribution (the higher moments of the distribution).”

⁶ The European integration process and the EU Cohesion Policy has undoubtedly contributed to promoting convergence in income per capita. However, it remains uncertain whether this holds also for regions and whether the rise in average incomes has led to an increase or decrease in income concentration.

⁷ Tselios (2009): “More specifically, little is known about the way in which income distribution affects the functioning and performance of regional economies, in general, and those European regions, in particular, possibly because of lack of adequate European regional data on individual and household income levels.”

⁸ Eight Central and Eastern European countries plus Cyprus, and Malta accessed in 2004 marks, Bulgaria and Romania joined in 2007, and Croatia in 2013.

averages) pointing to stronger separating dynamics. This is especially the case for inequality. Better labour market and educational outcomes are associated with a higher probability of being in low-poverty and low-inequality clubs. Digital transformation seems to increase the likelihood of belonging to the higher clubs of poverty or inequality, especially working via the labour market demand. Available indicators of regional openness and migration are associated with a higher likelihood of belonging to the lower clubs of inequality and poverty, respectively, only in certain model specifications. Suggesting limited robustness.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. **Section 1** focuses on the literature review, which covers several themes. On the one hand, a short overview of the theoretical and empirical convergence models and methods is provided. Next, the literature that has examined the convergence of the same variable of interest in this study - GDP per capita, poverty, and inequality in the EU - is examined, with a particular emphasis on the results obtained through the application of the club convergence approach. **Section 2** explains the above-mentioned two-step empirical methodology focusing on the Phillips and Sul model and giving some details of the ordered logistic model. The data description includes the dependent variables, which are used to examine club convergence, as well as the independent variables included in the ordered logit model. Control variables include the sectoral composition of the economy, human capital, technological and digital development, foreign investments, the intensity of regional migration, and other region-specific characteristics linked to agglomeration and/or concentration. **Section 3**, provides a detailed account of the findings from the convergence analysis, while **Section 4** focuses on reporting the outcomes of the econometric estimation and indicates further development in this line of research. **Section 5** concludes. The study includes a statistical appendix that provides, inter alia: i) details of the methods used to expand the time series of the selected indices of inequality and poverty; ii) the description of the independent variables used for the ORL; iii) robustness checks of OLR estimates.

1. Literature review

Convergence, both from a theoretical and an empirical perspective, has a well-established record in the economic literature. The concept of convergence is derived from Solow's 'neoclassical growth model' (Solow, 1956; Swan, 1956), which posits that the diminishing return to capital leads to a reduction in income disparities between economies over time. This occurs because capital tends to flow from high-income economies, where it is abundant, to low-income economies, where it is scarce, in pursuit of higher relative returns.⁹ In the model, the so-called Inada (1963) conditions imply that as each economy reaches its long-term equilibrium, differences in per capita real income will reduce, resulting in 'overall convergence' among countries.

However, more recent theoretical frameworks like the 'new growth theories', pioneered by Romer (1986) and Lucas (1988), argue that convergence between poor and rich countries is not guaranteed. These conflicting perspectives have led to the development of various convergence definitions and empirical testing methodologies, fuelling the debate about convergence for decades.

In response to criticisms of the original neoclassical growth model, several modifications have been introduced. Scholars like Parente and Prescott (1994), Barro and Sala-i-Martin (1997), Basu and Weil (1998), Perez-Sebastian (2000), and Howitt and Mayer-Foulkes (2005) replaced homogeneous technological progress across countries in the neoclassical production function with the assumption of country-specific technological growth rates. Azariadis (1996) and Galor (1996) further advanced the

⁹ Benabou's seminal study (1996) demonstrates that the neoclassical growth model not only predicts a convergence of income but also a convergence in income distribution. Therefore, it is likely that economies with similar characteristics would move towards the same pre-taxes income or wealth distribution, so that, over time economies with low-income inequality will see their inequality rise, while economies with high-income inequality will see their inequality fall.

model by showing that the neoclassical growth model can generate multiple equilibria; countries with identical economic structures may not always converge to the same equilibrium growth path, instead, some countries may converge to a high steady-state income level while others may fall into a poverty trap, giving rise to the ‘club convergence’ hypothesis.¹⁰

Baumol (1986) was the first to introduce the concept of β -convergence, which denotes a negative correlation between the growth rate of GDP and its starting level.¹¹ This concept captures the hypothesis that lagging regions should grow faster than more advanced ones, eventually catching up (Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 1992; Mankiw et al., 1992; Islam, 1995; Sala-i-Martin, 1996).

Barro and Sala-i-Martin (1991) introduced the notion of σ -convergence, defined as “a decline over time in the cross-sectional dispersion of per capita income or product”. In this approach, convergence focuses on the reduction of disparities among countries measured by statistical indicators such as the standard deviation or coefficient of variation. While β -convergence is necessary, but not a sufficient condition for σ -convergence.

Empirical evidence has generally supported cross-country convergence processes, though outcomes vary depending on the period, countries, and regions examined and some studies have highlighted the presence of non-linear convergence patterns. Given these complexities, empirical estimation of economic convergence remains a central topic of debate in economic literature. This is particularly the case within the EU context, where the process of integration was supposed to lead to upward convergence.

1.1 Income Convergence in the EU

The concept of economic convergence has attracted special attention in the EU context, particularly around three significant events: the introduction of the euro, the Eastern enlargements of 2004-2007 and the aftermath of the financial crisis.

Twenty years after the creation of the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU), the impact of the euro on convergence remains contentious. While reduced exchange rate volatility under the EMU promoted greater integration and institutional efficiency, Southern Member States have diverged socio-economically since the euro’s introduction, reversing earlier trends. Establishing causality is difficult, as the euro’s introduction coincided with rapid globalisation, which tended to benefit emerging economies (like new EU Member States) over advanced ones (like older EMU members). Such considerations were reinforced by the financial and sovereign debt crisis, which hit harder EA Member States. Furthermore, the post-crisis recovery failed to reduce growth disparities across EU Member States (see Monfort, 2020). This issue was particularly acute among older EU Member States in the euro area, where some countries faced prolonged economic crises. By 2018, the income gap between the richest and poorest Member States had widened compared to the period when the euro was first introduced, despite pre-crisis growth. Conversely, Central and Eastern European countries (CEE) showed better performance, closing in on the EU average even after deep, though brief, recessions. The latter evidence supported a growing consensus that the Eastern enlargements spurred rapid convergence of new Member States toward the EU average income.

¹⁰ With the idea of relaxing the neoclassical hypothesis, the concept of stochastic convergence was first introduced by Carlino and Mills (1993; 1996), refined by Bernard and Durlauf (1995), and later econometrically formalised by Pesaran (2007). Stochastic convergence occurs when pairs of regions experience co-moving income trajectories, or in other words, the output gap between the pair of regions is a stationary process with a constant mean. This type of convergence relaxes the neoclassical notion of convergence by allowing for the absence of steady-state dynamics, non-convergence or, equivalently divergence, in cases of diminishing returns, and the existence of endogenously driven club convergence.

¹¹ The speed of convergence can be measured either by disregarding countries’ initial characteristics or by controlling for them. The former is called unconditional or absolute β -convergence, and it assumes that all countries are converging towards the same steady state. The latter is called conditional β -convergence and the speed of convergence and the steady state towards which countries are converging can differ due to country differences.

One interesting aspect of the EU convergence process is the difference between outcomes at the country and regional level. Monfort (2008) highlights that the reduction of disparities among EU regions, between 1995 and 2005, was driven by a significant reduction in disparities among Member States. However, disparities among regions within the Member States were increasing. In a similar vein, Goecke and Hüther (2016) analysed conditional convergence in real GDP per capita using NUTS 3 data and found significant regional disparities. While many regions in Eastern Europe, Spain, and Portugal converged, regions in Greece, Italy, and the UK diverged. They highlighted the importance of manufacturing size and the EU subsidy direction in the convergence process. Monfort (2020) updates his analysis and finds that the financial crisis stopped convergence within the EU-28, the level of disparity has been more or less stable since 2008, but disparities are growing within many Member States. In a similar vein, Alcidi et al. (2018a) find that during the years 2000-07, cross-regional differences in GDP per capita in PPS fell and σ -convergence was taking place. From 2008, however, the variation at the regional level began to increase, showing that in the aftermath of the financial crisis, regional disparities in the EU expanded. Furthermore, Alcidi et al. (2018b) show that the EU's rapid convergence at the country level contrasts with within-country divergences. This is especially the case for CEE countries, where internal dynamics are characterised by strong diverging patterns, usually driven by the outstanding performance of the capital region. Conversely, many old EU Member States, which seem to have slowed down, or even lost track, in the EU convergence process, have been internally converging, thereby reducing income disparities across regions. Some studies indicate that CEE economies were able to achieve rapid internationalization driven by their integration into the European Single Market, proximity to major EU industrial centres (Germany) and lower wages. However, such a process led to a disproportionate concentration of economic activity in metropolitan regions, and not necessarily the whole country.

Alcidi (2019) finds that the β -convergence hypothesis at the regional level is supported, but notes that the convergence rate among regions is about 30% slower than among Member States, with greater regional income dispersion. From 2000 to 2007, cross-country and cross-regional differences in GDP per capita in PPS were narrowing, indicating σ -convergence. However, since 2008, regional disparities have widened, driven by some Southern countries and regions' poor performance. While many Eastern European regions, along with Spain and Portugal, experienced regional convergence, the opposite occurred in Greece and Italy, where regional income gaps increased.

Bisciari et al. (2020a, 2020b) emphasise the failure of Southern European countries to converge with Northern Europe from the mid-1990s to 2008, with the gap widening during the financial crisis. In contrast, CEE countries have been strong drivers of convergence since the mid-1990s, albeit with some cyclicity. The authors attribute this divergence to structural polarisation, particularly in technological capabilities. Northern countries, leveraging advanced technologies, successfully adopted export-led growth models, while many Southern countries struggled with competitiveness.

The studies reviewed above primarily focus on σ - and β -convergence, implicitly or explicitly assuming a common steady state across economies. However, since the introduction of the Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009) methodology for detecting convergence clusters, this approach has gained traction in studies examining EU Member States (Apergis et al., 2010; Fritsche and Kuzin, 2011; Bartkowska and Riedl, 2012; Monfort et al., 2013; Borsi and Metiu, 2015, Cavallaro and Villani, 2020) and Western European regions. This body of literature reveals varying speeds of development, marked by the emergence of clear geographical divisions between North and South, as well as West and East. However, over time, geographical patterns have become more complex. Notably, studies by Borsi and Metiu (2015) and von Lyncker and Thoennesen (2017) show that the number of clubs doubles when the first phase of the Great Recession is included in the analysis, highlighting the nuanced and evolving nature of economic convergence in the EU. The literature specifically regarding income at the NUTS 2 level and conducted with the Phillips and Sul methodology includes Bartowska and Riedl (2012), von

Lyncker and Thoennesen (2017), Cutrini (2019), Mazzola and Pizzuto (2020), Pintera (2021). A more detailed description of these last results is described in Section 3.1.2.

1.2 Convergence in income inequality and poverty

Literature on income inequality and poverty convergence is limited and even more so when the regional level is concerned¹² possibly because of the paucity of available data. It should also be recognised that there is no strong theoretical foundation predicting that inequality and poverty levels should converge across countries or regions. Following the neoclassical theory, income distribution should reflect income growth, with less inequality as income grows, however, growing empirical evidence in the last decades points to very different patterns.

Among the earliest studies, Alvarez-Garcia et al. (2004) classify the EU Member States in terms of the degree of inequality and then test for inequality convergence within and between countries over the period 1993-1997. Their results indicate a decrease in income inequality within and between countries, implying inequality convergence in the EU. Tselios (2009) employing data for the period 1995-2000¹³ finds the existence of unconditional convergence in income inequality. In regions with initially high inequality, there was a greater tendency for within-region inequality to decrease. Furthermore, he finds that the process of regional convergence in income inequality occurred regardless of the presence of conditioning variables. Otoi and Titan (2015) explore whether socioeconomic convergence occurs at national and regional levels and whether the EU cohesion policy is effective. They use the coefficients of variation to analyse convergence for disposable income, unemployment rates, the proportion of people living in households with low work intensity, and migration. They find that convergence and divergence are faster at the country level, and trends at the national level are mostly different from those at the regional level in terms of direction and magnitude. For unemployment rates and work intensity, regional data shows more volatility, indicating higher within-country volatility, whereas between-country volatility is higher for incomes and net migration. Except for unemployment, the Great Recession did not induce an erosion of the convergence observed in the pre-crisis period; in particular, low work intensity remained steady. Ari et al. (2022) test the inequality convergence in the EU-15 Member States through system GMM estimator. They find evidence of the existence of absolute convergence in income inequality between the EU-15 countries over the period 1988-2017. When control variables are included, the estimates indicate a more rapid convergence process across countries. One important result of their study is that convergence in income inequality occurs at higher values of the Gini coefficient, hence toward higher inequality. Savoia (2020, 2024), using 7 waves of the Luxembourg Income Study (LIS) database from 1990 to 2013,¹⁴ observed that regions were getting “equally more unequal” as they converged towards a higher level of income inequality. He also found that the regions eligible for the Cohesion Policy funding were characterised by a higher speed of convergence and may have played a substantial role in driving the overall convergence process.

As far as poverty is concerned, Cartone et al. (2024) examine conditional β -convergence of the at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion (AROPE), using a spatial quantile regression approach covering the

¹² At the EU Member States level (NUTS 0) income inequality convergence has been studied, among others, by: Alvarez-Garcia, et al. (2004), De Siano and D’Uva (2006) with Classification and Regression Tree Analysis, Clark (2019), Ari et al. (2022), Vale (2023). At the NUTS 1 level, Ezcurra and Pascual (2005) utilised ECHP data to provide descriptive evidence in graphical form (based on density functions) for a group of 65 regions over the period 1993–1998, thereby confirming the validity of inequality convergence in European Union. At the EU Member States level (NUTS 0) poverty convergence has been studied by Lafuente (2020) with respect to the at-risk-of-poverty rate after social transfers, People living in households with very low work intensity Severe material deprivation rate (2005–2018).

¹³ Using a combination of 102 NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 regions, belonging to 13 Member States (NUTS 1: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Spain, and Germany; NUTS 2: Sweden, Portugal, and the UK).

¹⁴ Only the sample 2004-2013 includes 103 observations.

period 2005-2015 at the NUTS 2 level. In the analysis, regional poverty convergence is found to be significant across 223 European regions. However, the convergence rate is faster in regions with higher poverty levels and slower when spatial factors are considered in the model. Across all quantiles, education—specifically, the reduction of early school leavers—plays a crucial role in alleviating poverty. This underscores the importance of educational attainment not only at lower levels but also at higher levels. A significant presence of skilled human capital also contributes to reducing poverty and social exclusion. By contrast, increasing economic growth does not seem to be a universal solution, even though the growth effect could be increased in areas where poverty reduction is low.

2. Empirical methodology and data

This study aims to assess the impact of various drivers on convergence in the standard of living across EU-27 regions, using a two-stage empirical approach with regional data at the NUTS 2 level (2021 version) over the period 2000-2023. In the first stage, clustering techniques are used to analyse convergence or divergence in the standard of living, proxied by GDP per capita (PPS), the at-risk-of-poverty rate (AROP), and the income quintile share ratio (S80/S20). Regional clusters are identified through the time-varying factor model developed by Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009), which accounts for regional heterogeneity and transitional dynamics.

In the second stage, an ordered logit regression (OLR) is applied to investigate the factors influencing the formation of convergence clubs. This model includes various control factors such as economic and geographical aspects, with a focus on digital transformation, globalization, and (regional) migration as key explanatory variables. Section 2.1 introduces the Phillips and Sul model, Section 2.2 explains the ordinal logit model, Section 2.3 outlines the methodology for addressing gaps in the dependent variables, and Section 2.4 presents the independent variables used in the logit model. Additional methodological details are provided in the Annex.

2.1 Club convergence

Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009) developed relative transition paths and a log-t test for convergence which, combined with a clustering algorithm, can endogenously determine convergence clubs without a priori classification of countries. Their method builds upon a neoclassical growth model and provides the necessary flexibility to accommodate heterogeneous technology in growth models. This empirical approach encompasses different options that can be reconciled with a variety of theoretical models, ranging from the traditional neoclassical model that predicts a single steady state for all regions, to club convergence that can also be related to multiple equilibria models. More specifically, it provides an empirical framework to distinguish between i) convergence to a single steady state shared by all economies as predicted by the neoclassical growth model; ii) overall divergence; and iii) club convergence, which may be interpreted as convergence to multiple steady-state equilibria.¹⁵

Phillips and Sul (2007a) started from a single-factor model (EQ1) extending it to a time-varying factor representation (EQ2).

$$X_{it} = \delta_i \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (\text{EQ1}) \qquad X_{it} = \delta_{it} \mu_t \quad (\text{EQ2})$$

In EQ1: δ_i measures the idiosyncratic distance between some common factor μ_t and the systematic part of X_{it} . The factor μ_t may represent the aggregated common behaviour of X_{it} , but could also be any common variable that influences the individual behaviour. The model aims to capture the evolution of the individual X_{it} in relation to μ_t via its two idiosyncratic elements: the systematic element δ_i and the error ε_{it} . In EQ2 δ_i is allowed to vary over time becoming δ_{it} , a 'time-varying factor loading coefficient' that accommodates diverse agent behaviour and its development. Moreover, δ_{it} includes a random

¹⁵ Since Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, and 2009), the club convergence methodology has evolved from a solely macroeconomic perspective, which primarily concentrated on GDP per capita and income, to a broader range of economic factors, such as house/rent prices, consumer price index, and total factor productivity. The interest also extended to other scientific disciplines, such as finance, ecology and energy fields. Tomal (2023) identified 354 published papers that demonstrate an exponential increase in interest in the Phillips and Sul club convergence methodology over the past decade.

component, which absorbs the error ε_{it} thus admitting a potential convergence behaviour in δ_{it} over time in relation to the common factor μ_t .

The Phillips and Sul approach does not assume any parametric form for μ_t , whereas, for modelling the behaviour of δ_{it} the authors referred to the following semiparametric form:

$$\delta_{it} = \delta_i + \sigma_i \xi_{it} L(t)^{-1} t^{-\alpha}, \quad t \geq 1, \quad \sigma_i > 0 \quad \forall i \quad (\text{EQ3})$$

where δ_i is fixed, ξ_{it} is *iid*(0,1) across i but weakly dependent over t , and $L(t)$ is a slowly varying function¹⁶ (like log t) for which $L(t) \rightarrow \infty$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. The parameter α sets the rate at which $\delta_{it} \rightarrow \delta_i$ with $t \rightarrow \infty$ and can be viewed as the speed of convergence. In particular, the convergence of δ_{it} to δ_i is guaranteed for all $\alpha \geq 0$. This last inequality, therefore, becomes the subject of the null hypothesis of the test along with the condition of a common value of δ_i across cross-sections. Thus, the overall relative convergence among the cross-sections is tested against the alternative allowing both overall divergence or club convergence.

The null hypothesis of overall convergence is given by EQ4a:

$$H_0 : \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \delta_{it} = \delta \quad \text{or equivalently} \quad H_0 : \delta_i = \delta \quad \& \quad \alpha \geq 0 \quad (\text{EQ4a})$$

The alternative hypothesis is given by EQ4b:

$$H_A : \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \delta_{it} \neq \delta \quad \text{or equivalently} \quad \{ \delta_i = \delta \quad \forall i \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha < 0 \} \quad \text{or} \quad \{ \delta_i \neq \delta \quad \text{for some} \quad i \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha \geq 0, \quad \text{or} \quad \alpha < 0 \} \quad (\text{EQ4b})$$

which corresponds to one of two cases, either overall divergence: $\delta_i = \delta$ for all i with $\alpha < 0$; or club convergence: $\delta_i = \delta$ for some i with $\alpha \geq 0$, or $\alpha < 0$.

To test the abovementioned hypothesis Phillips and Sul's model employs a regression log t test, whereby the loading coefficient δ_i is crucial in assessing the convergence of economies. Nevertheless, when the number of observations in the panel is less than the number of unknowns in the model it is impossible to directly estimate the loading coefficient without imposing a structure on δ_{it} , and μ_t . Thus, Phillips and Sul (2007b) suggested an alternative approach to model δ_{it} , by removing the common factor μ_t , and constructing the relative (loading or) transition parameter h_{it} :

$$h_{it} = \frac{X_{it}}{N^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N X_{it}} = \frac{\delta_{it}}{N^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{it}} \quad (\text{EQ5})$$

Where h_{it} denotes the transition path of unit i in comparison to the panel (clubs) average at time t . Convergence is present if $h_{it} \rightarrow 1$ for all i , as $t \rightarrow \infty$. The relative transition path, as referred to by Phillips and Sul (2009), tracks the trajectory of each cross-section i in relation to the club's average trajectory. As it can be observed in (EQ5) the common component μ_t has been eliminated. Thus, the relative transition coefficient h_{it} is considered to be a measure that defines the relation of the factor loading δ_{it} for a given country i to the panel average δ_t .¹⁷

Then, the cross-sectional variance ratio $H1/Ht$ is constructed. It compares the cross-sectional variance at an initial time point with that at time t . It is expressed as in (EQ6). This latter is a key component of the Phillips and Sul convergence testing methodology. It is employed to evaluate the extent of convergence or divergence among entities over time as it quantifies the evolution of the cross-sectional dispersion of the transition parameters h_{it} .

¹⁶ Possible choices for $L(t)$ are $\log(t+1)$, $\log_2(t+1)$, or $\log \log(t+1)$.

¹⁷ In EQ5:

- If $h_{it}=1$, entity i is exactly at the cross-sectional average.
- If $h_{it}>1$, entity i is above the cross-sectional average.
- If $h_{it}<1$, entity i is below the cross-sectional average.

$$\frac{H_1}{H_t} = \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (h_{i1} - 1)^2}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (h_{it} - 1)^2} \quad (\text{EQ6})$$

If H_t decreases over time, then H_1/H_t increases, indicating that the dispersion of the parameter h_{it} is shrinking and suggesting convergence among the entities. The economies are becoming more similar to each other over time.

If H_t increases over time, then H_1/H_t decrease, indicating that the dispersion of the parameter h_{it} is growing and suggesting divergence among the entities. The economies are becoming more dissimilar to each other over time.

If H_t remains constant, there is no convergence or divergence, and the economies are neither becoming more similar nor more dissimilar.

The log t regression test for convergence, involves running the following OLS regression with a robust covariance matrix:

$$\log\left(\frac{H_1}{H_t}\right) - 2 \log L(t) = \hat{a} + \hat{b} \log t + \hat{u}_t, \text{ for } t = [rT], [rT]+1, \dots, T \text{ with } r > 0 \quad (\text{EQ7})$$

Where \hat{b} is the key coefficient: if it is < 0 then it suggests convergence, whereas if it is ≥ 0 it suggests no convergence (either divergence or stagnation), furthermore b , is related with α , which represents the speed of convergence. Particularly, $\hat{b} = 2\hat{\alpha}$ and thus the hypothesis \mathcal{H}_0 can be tested through the weak inequality null $\alpha \geq 0$ as already mentioned in EQ4a.

The term $-2 \log L(t)$ plays the role of a penalty function and improves test performance, particularly under the alternative. For example, the transition distance Ht converges to a positive value as t approaches infinity under the alternative of club convergence. The inclusion of the penalty term in the regression provides the test with discriminatory power between overall convergence and club convergence (Phillips and Sul, 2009, p. 1168). The letter r denotes the truncation parameter, indicating that the first r per cent of observations are excluded. According to Phillips and Sul (2009), data trimming facilitates the focus on the later portion of the sample data, hence validating the regression equation in terms of the asymptotic representation of the transition distance H_t and ensuring test consistency in growth convergence applications.

The test takes the form of a one-sided t test.

$$t_b = \frac{\hat{b} - b}{s_b} \Rightarrow N(0,1) \quad (\text{EQ8})$$

Phillips and Sul's Monte Carlo simulations (2007, 2009) indicate the use of $r = 0.3$ and $L(t) = \log t$ for samples up to $T = 50$. The conventional critical values may be used, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of convergence at the 5% significance level if $t_{\hat{b}} < -1.65$ (and at the 1% significance level if $t_{\hat{b}} < -2.326$).

The rejection of the null hypothesis of convergence points to the possible existence of convergence clubs, clustered around distinct steady-state equilibria. Phillips and Sul (2007, pages 1798-1801) suggested using a four-step clustering approach to identify clubs that converge in the panel. The four steps ("last observation ordering", "core group formation", "sieve individuals for club merging", and "stopping rule" in Phillips and Sul 2007a pp.1800-1801) can be briefly summarised as follows: Initially, the units (regions) are arranged in descending order according to the most recent period in the time series dimension of the panel. Subsequently, a convergence club is established through the log t test. To be more specific, this is achieved by incrementally incorporating units (regions) into a group of the two highest-income regions at the beginning and conducting the log t test until the $t_{\hat{b}}$ for this group

exceeds -1.65 . Then, the log t test is conducted for this group and all remaining units in the sample, one by one, to determine whether they converge. If not, the initial three stages are implemented on the remaining units. If no clubs are identified, it is possible to infer that those units diverge.

An alternative club merging algorithm was developed by von Lyncker and Thoennessen (2017). They introduced two innovations in the club merging algorithm by Phillips and Sul. First, they add a further condition to the club clustering algorithm to avoid mistakes in merging procedures in the case of transition across clubs. Second, they propose an algorithm for diverging units.¹⁸

2.2 The ordered logit model

An ordered logit regression (OLR),¹⁹ originally proposed by McKelvey and Zavoina (1975), is employed to analyse the factors that empirically influence the emergence of convergence clubs. OLR is a suitable method for modelling the relationship between a dependent variable, with several categories with a meaningful sequential order, and one or more independent variables. In the context of this study, the different clubs²⁰ can be ordered according to the computed 'steady state' of the GDP per capita in PPS²¹ so that the OLR takes the form given in EQ (2.2.1).

$$y_i^* = X_i\beta + \varepsilon_i \quad \text{EQ (2.2.1)}$$

In this context, y_i^* is a latent variable that has ordinal values ranging from 1 to N (depending on the number of clubs), X_i is the set of independent variables (proxying for the dimensions described in Section 2.3). NUTS 2 are denoted by i (with i having a maximum value of 242 observations) ε_i is a random error, and the regression coefficients are represented by the column vector β . The estimation is run with a maximum likelihood (ML) model that is an iterative process. The log-likelihood of the "null" or "empty" model, which is a model without any independent variable, is the object of the initial iteration (referred to as iteration 0). The independent variables are incorporated into the model during the subsequent iteration. The log-likelihood increases with each iteration, as the objective is to optimise it. The model is said to have "converged" when the difference between successive iterations becomes extremely small.

2.3 Missing data integration in NUTS 2 level (AROP and S80/S20)

Readily available data at the NUTS 2 level for the indicators AROP²² and S80/S20²³ are limited both in the cross-region and time-series dimensions. To enhance the representativeness of the sample the following steps have been adopted in the order specified below:

¹⁸ As far as the existing routines are concerned, Phillips and Sul (2007, 2009) utilised a Gauss code in their empirical research. Schnurbus et al. (2017) presented a set of R functions to reproduce the main findings of Phillips and Sul (2009). In addition, Du (2017) created a comprehensive Stata package specifically designed for implementing the club convergence process. Mendez (2023) contributed supplementary code to automate the generation of figures and tables. Sichera and Pizzuto (2019) have developed a specifically designed R package "ConvergenceClubs" for implementing this methodology, which also utilises the alternative club merging technique devised by von Lyncker and Thoennessen (2017).

¹⁹ Ordered logit regressions are run with the Stata command "ologit". The marginal effects are computed with the command "margins, dydx()" per each independent variable at the mean of all other variables.

²⁰ The club to which a region belongs is the dependent variable in these models, and it is characterised as an ordinal variable. 1 corresponds to the lowest club, whilst higher values imply membership in higher clubs (in reverse order of the club categorisation for the GDP per capita in PPS and the same order for the inequality and poverty indicators).

²¹ The same of course applies for the inequality and poverty indicators.

²² Eurostat code: ilc_li41 and tgs00103.

²³ Eurostat code: ilc_di11_r.

- a. EU-SILC microdata based on the variable “region of residence”²⁴ only when it is available at the NUTS 2 level. This allows computing:
 - The at-risk-of-poverty rate based on the variable “poverty indicator” – hx080.
 - The inequality index S80/S20 based on the variable “equivalised disposable income” – hx090
- b. EU-SILC microdata based on the combination of the variable “region of residence” when it is available at NUTS 1 level only and the variable “degree of urbanisation”²⁵. In some cases, combining the two variables allows us to uniquely identify a region at the NUTS 2 level.

Under points a. and b. the following variables are used:

- The at-risk-of-poverty rate based on the variable “poverty indicator” – hx080.
 - The inequality index S80/S20 based on the variable “equivalised disposable income” – hx090
- c. Various methodologies for backcasting and interpolation when point a. and point b. are not feasible, given a certain availability of the regional data in the time-series dimension.

The computations have been recorded in the NUTS 2 2021 classification. Nevertheless, the conversion between various classifications of NUTS 2 is not always possible, without having access to the more detailed level NUTS 3, for example, due to changes in boundaries.²⁶

2.4 Independent variables

This section describes the set of independent variables, including control variables for economic, and geographical factors. The inclusion of control variables has the purpose is to ensuring an appropriate model specification and to disentangle the relationships between the three key transformations - the emergence and diffusion of digital technologies, globalisation and (regional) migration – and their influence on income, inequality and poverty convergent clubs. The selection of variables is grounded in the extensive review of the literature presented above.

Control variables: Economic factors

The economic control variables used are:

- The **sectoral composition of the economy** is represented by the employment share in the following four sectors: i) in Manufacturing (NACE C); ii) in Information and communication (NACE J);²⁷ iii) in the Financial sector (NACE K). Both the Information and communication and Financial sectors are known for strongly relying on highly skilled workers; iii) in routine services including Wholesale and retail commerce (NACE G), Transport and storage (NACE H), and Accommodation and food service activities (NACE I), a group of sectors that is known for strongly relying on low-skilled workers.

²⁴ EU SILC code: db040 refers to the region of the residence of the household at the date of the interview and depending on the MS can be recorded at NUTS 0, 1 or 2 level.

²⁵ EU SILC code: DB100. The Degree of urbanisation (DEGURBA) is a classification that indicates the character of an area. Based on the share of the local population living in urban clusters and in urban centres, it classifies local administrative units level 2 (LAU2) into three types of area: thinly populated area (rural area); intermediate density area (towns and suburbs/small urban area), and densely populated area (cities/large urban area). Eurostat (2023), “Degree of urbanisation classification - 2011 revision”, Statistic Explained, retrieved at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/SEPDF/cache/31486.pdf>

²⁶ For the changes that occurred through the different classifications of NUTS 2 see:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/history>

²⁷ That can be considered as well as a proxy for digital technology diffusion.

- The **employment rate** of the workers aged 25-34.
- The **human capital** is proxied by the percentage of the population aged 25–64 with secondary and tertiary education (ISCED 3-8).

Control variables Geographical/locational factor

The geographical/locational control variables employed are:

- A dummy to identify the regions including the **capital**.
- **Metro** for indicating the number of metropolitan areas in the region. These regions are defined as urban agglomerations (NUTS level 3 regions or groups of NUTS level 3 regions) where at least 50 % of the population lives inside a functional urban area (FUA) that is composed of at least 250,000 inhabitants.
- **Rural** index that corresponds to the ‘urban-rural’ typology.
- **Remote** index that corresponds to the ‘urban-rural-remoteness’ typology

Potential drivers: Digital transformation

To measure technological change multiple variables are used²⁸ with the attempt to capture different dimensions of such widespread transformation. However, given our interest in income, poverty and inequality, the selection of the indicators has been driven by two criteria: technology adoption in production and linkages with the labour market. Five indicators have been selected:

- The **3.0 and 4.0 technology creation** index, ranging between 1 (lowest value) and 4 (highest value), corresponds to the ESPON ‘taxonomy of the 4.0 inventing regions’. The term refers to regions that are innovation-driven, highly productive, and focused on technological advancement, particularly in automation, data exchange, digitalization, and smart manufacturing systems. These regions prioritize development in sectors like robotics, artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and big data analytics, which are key components of Industry 4.0. the latter is usually measured through patents.
- The **‘Green patent & tech’** index, ranging between 0.5 and 1.5, which corresponds to the ESPON ‘composite index of access to technology’ and has the purpose of capturing technological advancements related to the green transition.
- An indicator of **high risk of job automation**, which is an indexed share of regional jobs at high risk of automation, defined as the “process of substitution of human activities with machines”. An indicator of the **average risk of job automation**, which is an indexed average risk of job automation across occupations in regional labour markets, is used for robustness checks.
- Sectoral indicators of **robot adoption** representing the yearly average of the number of robots per employee in specific manufacturing sectors: a) robot adoption in technology manufacturing sectors; b) robot adoption in carrier manufacturing sectors; c) robot adoption in induced manufacturing sectors.
- Two indicators of regional **‘creation and displacement’**, one **for high-skill jobs** and one **for low-skill jobs** that classify regions depending on the degree of technological adoption and the adoption’s impact on high-skill (low-skill) employment share, within each type of technology.

²⁸ Different measures are used in the regressions, depending on the dependent variables considered.

Potential drivers: Globalisation

The notion of globalisation is vast and multifaceted. A recent IMF (2020) definition is: "Globalization refers to the growing interdependence of the world's economies, cultures, and populations, brought about by cross-border trade in goods and services, technology, and flows of investment, people, and information."²⁹. In the context of the GI-NI project globalisation has been referred to as "the new forms of international trade and foreign investment, including global production networks and fragmentation of production", thus when selecting the explanatory variables, particular attention was given to foreign investments. Inward foreign direct investment (FDI) plays a crucial role in the context of globalisation and in this context especially for the GDP per capita club formation.

For accounting for globalisation, the following predictors have been employed:

- An indicator of the **FDI class**: is an ordinal index ranging from 1 to 6 (with 1 being the lowest and 6 being the highest value) built based on the "Incoming FDI regional typologies" (Adamakou et al. 2024). **FDI Potential Index** is an index of FDI attractiveness (Maza and Villaverde, 2015) computed with a regional approach. As explained in Maza al Villaverde (2015) the index employs a sound way of selecting the variables involved in its construction, for which a factor analysis is performed. Accordingly, six factors ("economic potential", "market size", "labour situation", "technological progress", "labour regulation" and "competitiveness").
- '**Extra-EU FDI n(umber)**' and '**Extra-EU FDI v(olume)**' are the total deal value and the total number of incoming FDI projects originating from extra EU. These are added as the previous variable, 'FDI regtype', which only includes FDI originating from intra-EU.

Potential drivers: migration

Measures of migration and EU mobility flows at the regional level are very limited due to the complexity of collecting and monitoring such data. We rely on the ESPON indicators that combine fat migration flows at the NUTS 2 level and account for both external (international) and internal (domestic) migrations. Specifically, we use two predictors:

- The '**crude rate of net migration plus statistical adjustment**'.
- The '**migration regional weighted intensity (MRWI)**' measures the impact of migration on different regions across Europe by considering both the volume of migration flows and the size of the regional population.

In addition to migration, **commuter flows** are considered as well as an additional control variable.

Additional details on the independent variables are offered in **Annex**. Regression results are presented in **Section 4.1** for GDP per capita and **Section 4.2** for AROP and S80/S20 in terms of logit coefficients whereas the marginal effects are reported in **Annex**.

²⁹ IMF (2020), "Globalization: A Brief Overview."

3. Convergence analysis

As anticipated above, the convergence analysis is conducted on three variables, GDP per capita in PPS, AROP rate and S80/S20 poverty ratio. Before showing the result for club convergence, we analyse developments in σ -convergence, as measured by the coefficient of variation, defined as the ratio of the standard deviation and the mean. The reason for this is to emphasise that not all regions are necessarily on the same convergence path. For instance, while σ -convergence may point to an overall decline in dispersion across the entire distribution of regions (hence convergence), club convergence, by recognising the possibility of distinct groups converging within the broader, may still point to diverging patterns across some of the clusters.

The analysis of σ -convergence is further disaggregated by the EU's geographical macro-areas: Central and Eastern Europe (CEE)³⁰, Northwestern Europe (NWE)³¹, and Southern Europe (SE)³². The reason for it that the debate around EU integration has often emphasised the impact of the different waves of the eastern enlargement, for which economic convergence in these new Member States (CEE) has been a key indicator of success. By contrast, the financial crisis has often been viewed as a driver of decline in SE “old” Member States, and hence a trigger of EU divergence patterns. From this view, the economic literature has often included a geographical dimension in the convergence analysis.

3.1 Convergence analysis in GDP per capita in PPS

The convergence analysis for GDP in PPS³³ for the EU-27 NUTS 2 regional level covers 242 NUTS 2 regions and the period 2000-2023³⁴.

Figure 3.1.1a σ -convergence in GDP per capita in PPS, EU-27 NUTS 2, 2000-2025

Source: Authors' calculation on ARDECO database variable SUVGDP (update 9 June 2024)

³⁰ Central and Eastern European countries include Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia.

³¹ Northern and Western Europe include Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Sweden.

³² Southern European countries include Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal and Spain.

³³ Source: ARDECO (Annual Regional Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Regional and Urban Policy), maintained and updated by the Joint Research Centre (JRC). For more details see Auteri et al. (2024). Data are available at: <https://urban.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ardeco/explorer?lng=en>

³⁴ The sample includes as well 2024 and 2025. "ARDECO includes short-term forecasts at the regional level based on forecasts provided by AMECO at the national level. Regional forecasts are produced under the responsibility of the Directorate General for Regional and Urban Policy and of the Joint Research Centre" ARDECO website: https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/territorial/ardeco-database_en#Forecasts

Note: 2024 and 2025 are forecasts

The σ -convergence analysis suggests a clear declining trend in the degree of variation across regions. Cross-region disparities have declined by 16% when considering the overall period 2000-2023 (**Figure 3.1.1a**). The strong process of convergence, which began around 2000, stopped during the years of the financial and debt crisis and resumed, but with less impetus, in more recent years. More specifically from 2000 to 2008, the coefficient of variation declined quite substantially, from 0.44 to 0.39. It then remained relatively stable until 2018. Following a small rise during the COVID-19, it then started to decline again to reach 0.36 in 2024 (and 2025, forecast data). While the high value of dispersion recorded in 2000 was never met again, the strongest decline occurred in the pre-crisis period and around the bug enlargement.

Figure 3.1.1b σ -convergence in GDP per capita in PPS, EU-27 NUTS 2 by geographical areas, 2000-2025

Source: Authors' calculation on ARDECO database variable SUVGDP (update 9 June 2024)

This is confirmed by the examination of convergence by geographical macro-areas (see **Figure 3.1.1b**). σ -convergence is essentially driven by the CEE regions, especially in the pre-crisis period³⁵. By contrast, developments in the NW and SE regions point to extensive periods of increasing divergence and stability.

Against the evidence of such different patterns, the next section explores the emergence of multiple clusters of regions without assuming that they belong to predefined geographical areas.

3.1.1 Club convergence in GDP per capita in PPS

When applying the Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009) model to AROP, the results indicate that overall convergence towards a common equilibrium does not hold. The t-statistic is less than -1.65, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of convergence (see **Table 3.1.2a**). To verify, then, the presence of club convergence, the Phillips and Sul clustering procedure is performed (**Table 3.1.2a**). Four clubs are initially identified. All of them present positive coefficients, whose value is less than 2 indicating that GDP per capita growth rates (not the levels³⁶) converge over time. To prevent club over-identification³⁷, the merging procedure is adopted to determine whether the initial clubs jointly satisfy the convergence hypothesis. This allows to group them into larger clubs. Following the t-statistic criteria, the hypothesis of merging Club 1 and Club 2 and of merging Club 3 and Club 4 is rejected (the t-statistic is around -24, thus is less than -1.65) whereas it cannot be rejected for the merging of Club 2

³⁵ Among others see Eurofound (2023a).

³⁶ Phillips and Sul, 2009, p. 1169.

³⁷ Phillips and Sul, 2009, p. 1171.

and Club 3. Accordingly, the final clustering sees three clubs. For robustness check, the von Lyncker and Thoennessen (2017) merging procedure is applied. All clusters present positive beta coefficients, whose value is less than 2 indicating a convergence in growth rates. In terms of magnitude, the coefficients of Club 1 and Club 2 are very similar, while the coefficient of Club 3 is marginally higher. Club 2 and Club 3, before merging, show higher values of the coefficients, indicating a stronger growth convergence.

Table 3.1.2a Convergence hypothesis log t test, club clustering and final club merging, GDP per capita in PPS, NUTS 2 level, (2000-2023)

log t test		coefficient		t-stat	
		-0.336		-24.568	
Clubs	Number of regions	β	t-stat	α	GDP club average
Baseline					
Club 1	82	0.16	4.89	0.08	32,570
Club 2	134	0.28	5.83	0.14	21,853
Club 3	17	0.30	7.02	0.15	18,492
Club 4	9	0.22	7.88	0.11	15,713
Merging PS and VLT					
Club 1 (1)	82	0.16	4.89	0.08	32,570
Club 2 (2+3)	151	0.16	3.61	0.08	21,475
Club 3 (4)	9	0.22	7.88	0.11	15,713

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: for applying the log t test the variable is transformed in logarithm and the series is also subject to the application of the Prescott (1997) filter to wipe out the cyclical component and to keep the trend component. The smoothing parameter is set to 400. 'Baseline' is the convergence club classification before merging. Applied truncation parameter: $r = 0.333$ (discarded years: 8, starting point for regression 2008), applied critical value: $c = 0$, t-statistic at the 5% significance level: -1.645 ; t-statistic at the 1% significance level: -2.326 . To perform the log t test the routine 'logtreg', developed for Stata (Du, 2017), is used. The "Merging PS and vLT" part of the table shows the results of the cluster analysis, after merging adjacent clusters. For the merging procedure as described in Phillips and Sul the routine developed for Stata (Du, 2017) is used. For the merging procedure as described in von Lyncker and Thoennessen, the routine developed for R (Sichera and Pizzuto, 2019) is used.

To further complement the analysis, we examine the **transition curves of the convergence clubs**. They illustrate the trajectories that the regions follow over time as they converge towards a particular GDP steady-state. They point to three main messages:

First, in line with the rejection of the null hypothesis of overall convergence, the full set of regional transition paths³⁸ (**Figure 3.1.2a**) clearly show trajectories going in opposite directions, suggesting different clubs with different convergence trajectories.

Second, the set of regional transition paths grouped by clubs (**Figure 3.1.2b**), which shows the within-club convergence, suggests a reduction of the GDP per capita disparity within each club. Additionally, the intensity of convergence is different across clubs. For instance, at the end of the sample period, GDP per capita cross-region differences within Club 1 and Club 2 are very similar in size and much larger than those within Club 3. It is also worthwhile to notice that Club 3 is the less populated club, while Club 2 has by far the largest number of regions.

Third, the transition paths of all clubs³⁹ (**Figure 3.1.2c**) illustrate the long-run tendencies between clubs. The clubs show moderate separating tendencies in GDP per capita. At the end of the period, the

³⁸ Computed as (log) GDP per capita in PPS divided by the cross-sectional mean of each year.

³⁹ Computed by taking the cross-country average within each club.

distance between the clubs is greater than in 2000. Club 1 is systematically above the cross-country mean, whilst Club 2 and Club 3 are systematically below it. Club 1, after 2007, is slightly diverging from the mean upwards. Club 2 presents a more constant path by marginally diverging from the mean downwards. Club 3 is significantly diverging from the mean downwards.

Fig 3.1.2a Overall set of regional transition paths⁴⁰, GDP per capita in PPS, NUTS 2 level, 2000-2023

Fig 3.1.2b Final clubs and within-club convergence, GDP per capita in PPS, NUTS 2 level, 2000-2023

⁴⁰ As the variable under study is normalized by the cross-sectional mean of each year, the convergence approach of Phillips and Sul (2007) is also referred to as relative convergence (Sul 2019).

Fig 3.1.2c Transition Paths of the Convergence Clubs, GDP per capita in PPS, NUTS 2 level, 2000-2023

Source: Authors' calculation.

Descriptive statistics based on the GDP convergent clubs (**Table 3.1.2b**) show that over the entire period, Club 1 has a GDP club average of 32,570 euro and is composed of 82 regions. Club 2, which is the largest, with 151 regions, has a substantially lower average income, 21,475 euro. Club 3 has an income club average which is less than half of club 1. This difference is even greater at the end of the period. It should be noted that Club 3 includes only 9 regions, however, they appear to have been drifting away from the EU average and even more dramatically from the best performers.

Table 3.1.2.b Descriptive statistics of geographical variables by GDP convergent clubs

GDP per capita in PPS, 2020-2023, NUTS 2 (242 observations)							
GDP							
Club	club average	Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Club 1	32,570	N and % of capital	22 (81%)				

		metro	82	2.83	3.20	0	15
		urban/rural	82	1.86	0.62	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	82	2.19	0.98	1	4.1
		N and % of capital	5 (19%)				
Club 2	21,475	metro	151	1.43	1.8	0	11
		urban/rural	151	2.22	0.5	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	151	2.81	0.98	1	5
		N and % of capital	0				
Club 3	15,713	metro	9	0.11	0.33	0.0	1
		urban/rural	9	2.52	0.28	2.0	3
		urban/rural/remote	9	3.84	0.65	3	5

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: 'metro' is the number of metropolitan areas, 'urban/rural' is an index varying between 1 and 3 so that for values ≤ 1.67 the region is considered 'predominantly urban', for values > 1.67 and ≤ 2.34 the region is considered 'intermediate' and for values > 2.34 the region is considered 'predominantly rural'. 'Urban/rural/remote' is an index varying between 1 and 5, so that for values ≤ 1.8 the region is considered 'predominantly urban', for values > 1.8 and ≤ 2.6 the region is considered 'intermediate, close to a city', for values > 2.6 and ≤ 3.4 the region is considered 'intermediate, remote', for values > 3.4 and ≤ 4.2 the region is considered 'predominantly rural, close to a city', and for values > 4.2 the region is considered 'predominantly rural, remote'.

A more detailed analysis leads to additional interesting findings. We find evidence of a **country effect**⁴¹. In other words, with few notable exceptions, most of the regions of one country tend to be in the same club. More specifically, the majority of regions in Club 1 are from 10 countries only: Austria (7 out of 9), Belgium (6 out of 11), Germany (21 out of 38), Denmark (3 out of 5), Estonia, Ireland (2 out of 3), Lithuania (2 out of 2), Luxembourg, Malta, and Romania (8 out of 9)⁴². The majority of regions in Club 2 are from 14 countries: Bulgaria (5 out of 6), Cyprus (1 out of 1), Czechia (7 out of 8), Spain (18 out of 19), Finland (4 out of 5), France (25 out of 27), Croatia (3 out of 4), Hungary (7 out of 8), Italy (16 out of 21), Latvia (1 out of 1), Poland (9 out of 17), Portugal (7 out of 7), Sweden (5 out of 8), Slovenia (1 out of 2), and Slovakia (3 out of 4). Only the Netherlands (6 each) and Slovenia (1 each) are equally split into Club 1 and Club 2. Finally, Club 3 is made up of Greek regions (8 out of 13) and one French region (*Régions Ultrapériphériques Françaises*).

Additionally, **Member States' capitals most of the time belong to the highest-income club**. More than 80% of the capitals are concentrated in Club 1. This is the case of Member States presenting the majority of regions in Club 1 (AT, BE, DE, DK, EE, IE, LT, LU, MT, and RO), but also of most of the Member States presenting the majority of regions in Club 2 (BG, CZ, ES, FI, FR, HR, HU, PL, SE, SI)⁴³. Also, in the Netherlands and Slovenia, the capital belongs to Club 1, whereas in Italy this principle does not apply.

Furthermore, **metropolitan areas**⁴⁴ are generally concentrated in regions belonging to the highest-income club. Indeed, almost 50% of the regions including more than two metropolitan areas belong to Club 1 (versus the 26% of the regions belonging to Club 2). Club 3 never presents more than one metropolitan area.

Finally, **rural and remote areas are concentrated mostly in the lowest-income club**. The value of the urban/rural index and that of the urban/rural/remote index are inversely correlated to the GDP club average value. Further detail on the impact of the geographical variables on the club formation is provided in Section 4.1 dedicated to the regression results.

⁴¹ Regions belonging to the same Member State cluster together.

⁴² In Estonia, Malta and Luxembourg NUTS 2 corresponds to NUTS 0.

⁴³ Where NUTS 2 corresponds to NUTS 0.

⁴⁴ According to the 2021 indicator of the number of metropolitan areas at the NUTS 2 level the maximum number of metropolitan areas in a region is 15 (Germany).

It is important to highlight that **the number and composition of clubs may differ depending on the length of the time series**. It is worth noting that results found in comparable empirical studies, but covering shorter periods, point to a more diversified configuration of clubs. This may be attributed either to economic events (e.g. recessions) of the period under examination or to the fact that the period itself, when too limited in duration, somewhat undermines the validity of the t-test⁴⁵. For instance, Cutrini (2019), Mazzola and Pizzuto (2020), and Pintera (2021), which focus on shorter periods (2003-2017 and 2000-2015) to investigate the impact of the financial and the sovereign debt crisis on convergence identify a higher number of clubs. This higher number is explained by the fact that the time series used does not include enough years following the debt crisis up to the most recent years.⁴⁶ By extending the time series under consideration, the number of groups tends to decrease. In fact, in our sample when including the two forecast years 2024 and 2025, the number of groups would decrease from three to two. The first group would consist of 64 regions, while the second group would consist of 178 regions. Greek regions shift up to club 2. Additional figures with transition paths relating to the longer period are available in the **Annex (Figure A3.1.2a, A3.1.2b and A3.1.2c)**.

3.2 Club convergence analysis in at-risk-of-poverty rate

The second variable under observation, at the EU-27 NUTS 2 regional level, is poverty as measured by the AROP⁴⁷ rate. This measures the share of people with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers⁴⁸. The sample covers 217⁴⁹ NUTS 2 regions and the period 2005-2023⁵⁰.

The analysis of the σ -convergence (Figure 3.2.1) suggests that considering the overall period 2005-2023, the cross-region variation in poverty decreased by 16.4%, a percentage that is very similar to the one observed for income per capita. However, developments are quite different. The coefficient of variation declined up to 2011, from 0.46 to 0.39%. It then gradually increased, with some variation, until 2020. Unlike for GDP, the effects of the financial crisis and the first years of the sovereign debt crisis are not particularly visible on poverty, possibly reflecting the activation of automatic stabilisers and other discretionary cushioning measures, which prevented differences from emerging. However, different speeds of recovery across countries and regions in the aftermath of the crisis, seem to have led to increasing variation in poverty rates. This does not appear to have been the case during COVID-19. Variation in poverty declined during the pandemic and remained relatively stable afterwards. Importantly σ -convergence does not say anything about whether the convergence is toward higher or lower levels of poverty.

⁴⁵ Caution is advisable while using the clustering approach in this situation, since the efficacy of the log t test diminishes as the time dimension decreases in length (Phillips and Sul, 2007, 2009). Our analysis of the GDP per capita in PPS confirms that there is a significant increase in the number of clubs when the period is less than ten years. This finding is consistent with previous empirical studies (see von Lyncker and Thoennessen, 2017).

⁴⁶ According to Phillips and Sul (2007) where is discussed the power of the t-test when the time series is shorter than 50 years, a trimming of 1/3 is suggested. This implies placing more emphasis on the latter years rather than the earlier ones. Hence, the years taken into account for club formation are influenced by both the starting and ending dates of the series. In addition, although shorter periods of 10 years are often used, possibly due to limited data availability, it takes to bear in mind that the reliability of the test depends on the length of the series.

⁴⁷ For a detailed description of the sources, please see Annex.

⁴⁸ "The at-risk-of-poverty rate indicator measures low income in comparison to other residents in that country, which does not necessarily imply a low standard of living." Source: Eurostat statistics explained.

⁴⁹ Extra Regions Nuts 2 are not included as data are not available. Furthermore, 10 observations for Belgium, 5 observations from France (*Régions Ultrapériphériques Françaises*), 4 regions for Croatia, and 7 regions for Portugal are excluded.

⁵⁰ Recall that the collection year is T and the income reference period is T-1.

Figure 3.2.1 σ -convergence in AROP, EU-27 NUTS 2, 2005-2023

Source: Authors' calculation.

When looking at the distinction between the three geographical macro-areas CEE, NWE and SE (Figure 3.2.2), the greatest decrease in the coefficient of variation can be attributed to the regions belonging to the NWE group with -21%⁵¹. Whereas for CEE and SE, the decrease is not particularly remarkable, below 3%, and the patterns are characterised by downward and upward developments.

Figure 3.1.2 σ -convergence in AROP, EU-27 NUTS 2 by geopolitical areas, 2005-2023

Source: Authors' calculation.

3.2.1 Club convergence in AROP

When testing the Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009) model to AROP, the overall convergence towards a common equilibrium does not apply. The t-statistics is less than -1.65 implying the rejection of the null hypothesis of convergence (Table 3.2.2a).

Table 3.2.2a Convergence hypothesis log t test, club clustering and final club merging, AROP, NUTS 2 level, (2005-2023)

Log t test		coefficient		t-stat	
		-0.85		-61.294	
Clubs	Number of	β	t-stat	α	AROP club

⁵¹ Rate of change between the first and the last available year.

	regions				average
Baseline					
Club 1	9	0.27	4.03	0.13	23.24
Club 2	10	0.05	0.75	0.02	24.05
Club 3	5	0.07	1.02	0.03	24.70
Club 4	14	0.08	0.97	0.04	21.57
Club 5	21	0.10	1.37	0.05	17.88
Club 6	70	0.12	1.77	0.06	17.07
Club 7	34	0.16	2.30	0.08	13.31
Club 8	38	0.28	2.92	0.14	13.05
Club 9	8	0.74	3.81	0.37	10.21
Club 10	4	0.05	3.21	0.03	10.94
Club 11	3	0.01	0.05	0.01	8.44
Merging PS					
Club 1 (1-5)	59	-0.02	-0.30	-0.01	21.20
Club 2 (6 and 7)	104	-0.07	-1.34	-0.03	15.84
Club 3 (8 and 9)	46	-0.09	-1.33	-0.05	12.56
Club 4 (10)	4	0.05	3.21	0.03	10.94
Club 5 (11)	3	0.01	0.05	0.01	8.44
Merging vLT					
Club 1 (1-4)	38	0.10	1.46	0.05	23.03
Club 2 (5 and 6)	91	0.05	0.78	0.02	17.26
Club 3 (7 and 8)	72	0.12	1.75	0.06	13.17
Club 4 (9 and 10)	12	0.49	3.93	0.24	10.45
Club 5 (11)	3	0.01	0.05	0.01	8.44
Non convergent group = RO32					

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: 217 observations available. Excluded 10 observations for Belgium, 5 observations from France (*Régions Ultrapériphériques Françaises*), 4 regions for Croatia, 7 regions for Portugal. For applying the log t test the variable is transformed into logarithms and the series is also subject to the application of the Prescott (1997) filter to wipe out the cyclical component and to keep the trend component. The smoothing parameter is set to 400. 'Baseline' is the convergence club classification before merging. Applied truncation parameter: $r = 0.333$ (discarded years: 6, starting point for regression 2011), applied critical value: $c = 0$, t-statistic at the 5% significance level: -1.645 ; t-statistic at the 1% significance level: -2.326 . To perform the log t test the routine 'logtreg', developed for Stata (Du, 2017), is used. The "Merging PS and vLT" part of the table shows the results of the cluster analysis, after merging adjacent clusters. For the merging procedure as described in Phillips and Sul the routine developed for Stata (Du, 2017) is used. For the merging procedure as described in von Lyncker and Thoennesen, the routine developed for R (Sichera and Pizzuto, 2019) is used.

As above, the club convergence analysis follows the Phillips and Sul clustering procedure (see **Table 3.2.2**). Eleven clubs are initially identified. All of them present positive coefficients, ranging between 0.05 and 0.74, thus with a value less than 2 indicating convergence in growth rates. Subsequently, the merging procedure, that prevents the club over-identification is applied, to determine whether the initial clubs jointly satisfy the convergence hypothesis and to group them into larger clubs. The final clustering sees five clubs (both with the Phillips and Sul and the Von Lyncker and Thoennesen algorithm). On this occasion, the Von Lyncker and Thoennesen algorithm works better than the Phillips and Sul one which detects less stable (weaker) convergence clubs. Indeed, with the Phillips and Sul algorithm, the coefficients are negative for Club 1, Club 2 and Club 3. Conversely, using the Von Lyncker and Thoennesen algorithm, the five convergence clubs always present a positive sign indicating greater stability. In terms of coefficient magnitude, Club 4 is the one with the highest coefficient (0.5), followed by Club 3, and Club 1 in the range of (0.10). It is worth noting that the composition of the final clubs with the two merging procedures slightly differs. In the remainder of this section, as well as for the regressions, the club classification identified with the VLT algorithm will be taken into account.

Based on the analysis of the **transition paths** for AROP, the overall set of regional transition trajectories⁵² (**Fig 3.2.2a**) shows that cross-region differences tend to increase over time, driven by a few regions with marked declining trajectories. Moreover, the overall picture indicates the existence of different clubs with distinct patterns of convergence. The set of regional transition paths grouped by clubs (**Figure 3.2.2b**) shows the within-club convergence points to a reduction of the poverty index disparity within each club, though with different intensities. Club 1 and Club 4 exhibit a weak convergence. The strongest convergence, instead, is recorded in Club 3, which is the second most numerous. Even if Club 5 exhibits convergence in levels, as it includes only two regions its weight is relatively low.

The transition paths of all clubs⁵³ (**Figure 3.2.2c**) illustrate the long-run tendencies between clubs. In the case of the AROP index, the clubs still show moderate separating tendencies and are more marked than in the case of the GDP per capita. Only Club 1 is systematically above the cross-country mean, whilst Club 3, Club 4 and Club 5 are systematically below it. It is worth highlighting, however, that Club 2, which is the most numerous, remains exactly on average and does not exhibit any fluctuations in its trajectory over time. The trajectory of Club 3 is also relatively consistent, whereas Club 1, Club 4 and Club 5 exhibit a tendency to diverge from the average over time (the former upwards and the two latter downwards).

Fig 3.2.2a Overall set of regional transition paths⁵⁴, AROP, NUTS 2 level, 2005-2023 (217 obs.)

Fig 3.2.2b Final clubs and within-club convergence, AROP, NUTS 2 level, 2005-2023 (217 obs.)^{55,56}

⁵² Computed as (log) inequality index divided by the cross-sectional mean of each year.

⁵³ Computed by taking the cross-country average within each club.

⁵⁴ As the variable under study is normalized by the cross-sectional mean of each year, the convergence approach of Phillips and Sul (2007) is also referred to as relative convergence (Sul 2019).

⁵⁵ Von Lyncker and Thoennesen algorithm for merging clubs applied.

⁵⁶ Club 1 includes 38 regions, Club 2 includes 91 regions, Club 3 includes 72 regions, and Club 4 and 5 includes 12 and 3 regions respectively.

Fig 3.2.3c Transition Paths of the Convergence Clubs, AROP, NUTS2 level, 2005-2023 (217 obs.)⁵⁷

Source: Authors' calculation.

Descriptive statistics based on the AROP convergent clubs (Table 3.2.2b) show that during the period 2005-2023 period, the poverty club average ranged between 23% of Club 1 (highest poverty rate) and 8.5% of Club 5. Club 2 and Club 3 are the most numerous ones (respectively 91 and 72 NUTS 2 regions) with an AROP of 17.3% and 13.2%.

Table 3.2.2.b Descriptive statistics of geographical variables by AROP convergent clubs

AROP, 2005-2023, NUTS 2 (217 observations, non convergent RO32)							
Club	AROP club average	Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max

⁵⁷ Von Lyncker and Thoennesen algorithm for merging clubs applied.

		N and % of capital	5 (21%)				
Club 1	22.03	metro	38	1.03	1.22	0	5
		urban/rural	38	2.02	0.52	1	2.83
		urban/rural/remote	38	2.50	0.94	1	4.33
		N and % of capital	9 (38%)				
Club2	17.26	metro	91	2.45	2.84	0	13
		urban/rural	91	2.10	0.60	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	91	2.64	1.08	1	5
		N and % of capital	6 (25%)				
Club 3	13.17	metro	72	1.96	2.72	0	15
		urban/rural	72	2.25	0.51	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	72	2.83	0.92	1	4.71
		N and % of capital	3 (13%)				
Club 4	10.45	metro	12	1.67	1.97	0	7
		urban/rural	12	1.93	0.66	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	12	2.18	1.01	1	4
		N and % of capital	1 (4%)				
Club 5	8.44	metro	3	0.33	0.58	0	1
		urban/rural	3	2.00	1.00	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	3	3	2	1	5

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: 'metro' is the number of metropolitan areas, 'urban/rural' is an index varying between 1 and 3 so that for values ≤ 1.67 the region is considered 'predominantly urban', for values > 1.67 and ≤ 2.34 the region is considered 'intermediate' and for values > 2.34 the region is considered 'predominantly rural'. 'Urban/rural/remote' is an index varying between 1 and 5, so that for values ≤ 1.8 the region is considered 'predominantly urban', for values > 1.8 and ≤ 2.6 the region is considered 'intermediate, close to a city', for values > 2.6 and ≤ 3.4 the region is considered 'intermediate, remote', for values > 3.4 and ≤ 4.2 the region is considered 'predominantly rural, close to a city', and for values > 4.2 the region is considered 'predominantly rural, remote'.

A closer look at the clubs and the features of the regions within each club suggest that a **country effect⁵⁸ prevails in the clubs with a medium-high and medium value of AROP**. This is partially because, for AROP, Club 2 and Club 3 are the most numerous. More specifically, Club 2 has six Member States with a majority of regions in the club (Germany, Greece, Spain, Italy, Lithuania, and Sweden) and two Member States where NUTS 0 and NUTS 2 levels correspond (Latvia and Malta). Club 3 has seven Member States with a majority of regions in the club (Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, France, Hungary, Poland, and Slovenia) and one Member State where NUTS 0 and NUTS 2 levels correspond (Cyprus).

Member States' capitals⁵⁹ mostly belong to clubs with medium-high and medium levels of AROP. Club 2 includes the 38% of capitals and Club 3 includes the 25% of capitals. More specifically, Club 2 includes seven capitals and two Member States: Sofia (BG41), Berlin (DE30), Copenhagen (DK01), Madrid (ES30), Vilnius (LT01), Amsterdam (NL32) and Stockholm (SE11). Furthermore, belongs to Club 2 also Riga (LV00), and La Valletta (MT00)⁶⁰. Club 3 includes five capitals and one Member State: Prague (CZ01), Athens (EL30), Paris (FR10), Budapest (HU11) and Ljubljana (SI04). Belongs to Club 3 also Cyprus (CY00).

Metropolitan areas⁶¹ are generally concentrated in regions belonging to the club with a medium-high level of AROP. Almost 60% of the regions including more than two metropolitan areas belong to Club 2

⁵⁸ Regions belonging to the same Member State cluster together.

⁵⁹ For AROP we have available 26 Member States, Portugal is not included due to lack of data, as thus also the capital is missing along with the capital of Croatia.

⁶⁰ Where NUTS 2 corresponds to NUTS 0.

⁶¹ According to the 2021 indicator of the number of metropolitan areas at NUTS 2 level the maximum number of metropolitan areas in a region is 15 (Germany).

(vs the 31% of the regions belonging to Club 3 and the 4% of the regions belonging to Club 1 and Club 4). Club 5 never presents more than one metropolitan area.

The urban/rural index indicates that all the clubs on average belong to the classification of 'intermediate', with the value of the index ranging from 1.67 to 2.34. Three out of five clubs belong to the classification of 'intermediate, remote', whereas the remaining two belong to the classification 'intermediate and close to a city'.

Further results related to geographical characteristics will be presented in Section 4.2 as results of the ordered logistic regression.

3.3 Club convergence analysis in income quintile share ratio

The convergence analysis of inequality uses the S80/S20 ratio, which is the ratio of total income received by the 20% of the population with the highest income (the top quintile) to that received by the 20% of the population with the lowest income (the bottom quintile)⁶². The sample is available for 166⁶³ NUTS 2 regions and the period 2008-2023⁶⁴.

The σ -convergence analysis (Figure 3.3.1) indicates that cross-region disparities in S80/S20 increased over the entire period 2008-2023 by 8.5%. However, after COVID-19, the coefficient of variation started to decrease, although it did not reach back to the levels observed in 2008⁶⁵. This result needs to be taken with caution considering that coverage of the series S80/S20 for NUTS 2 excludes some Member State's data (DE, NL, PT, IE). A decline in cross-region convergence was recorded in 2009 and 2010, likely as the result of the activation of automatic stabilisers or other cushioning measures. Subsequently, inequalities increased during the period 2011-2015 and, then in 2017-2021. The increase was particularly strong in 2011-2013 the impact of the sovereign debt crisis. The sharp and substantial decline recorded in 2022 and 2023 seems to indicate the efficacy of the cushioning strategies to mitigate the impact of COVID-19.

Figure 3.3.1 σ -convergence in S80/S20, EU-27 NUTS 2, 2008-2023

Source: Authors' calculation.

⁶² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Income_quintile_share_ratio

⁶³ Are excluded from the sample Germany (37 regions), Croatia (5 regions), Ireland (5 regions), the Netherlands (12 regions), and Portugal (7 regions).

⁶⁴ Recall that the collection year is T and the income reference period is T-1.

⁶⁵ The income reference year is always the previous one, in this case, 2007.

Looking in detail at the distinction between the three geographical macro-areas, the greatest decrease in the coefficient of variation occurred in the CEE group with -18%. Instead, the increase is mainly driven by the SE, with a 66% increase, and to a more limited extent by NEW, with 34% raise.

Figure 3.3.2 σ -convergence in S80/S20, EU-27 NUTS 2, by geopolitical areas, 2008-2023

Source: Authors' calculation.

3.3.1 Club convergence in S80/S20

Similar to GDP and poverty, when applying the Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009) model to the S80/S20 ratio, the results indicate that overall convergence towards a common equilibrium does not hold. The t-statistic is extremely far from -1.65 and the null hypothesis of convergence is rejected (Table 3.3.2). According to the clustering procedure (Table 3.3.2) seven clubs are identified. All clubs, except Club 2, present positive coefficients (ranging from 0.20 to 1.51), whose value is less than 2 indicating that convergence is in growth rate. As for Club 2, the coefficient is negative, and the t-statistic is greater than -1.65, thus, it could be described as a club of weak convergence. Following the merging procedure to prevent club overidentification, the original Club 3, Club 4 and Club 5 are merged into Club 3, which becomes the most numerous (with 78 regions) and still presents a positive beta coefficient of 0.11 (which is, nevertheless, much lower than the coefficients of the three clubs from which it originates). The other clubs remain unaltered from their original configuration. Club 4 is the second most numerous and presents a beta coefficient of 0.20. The highest coefficient belongs to Club 5 (1.5) which nevertheless includes only 5 regions.

Table 3.3.2 Convergence hypothesis log t test, club clustering and final club merging, S80/S20, NUTS 2 level, (2008-2023)

log t test		coefficient		t-stat	
		-1.130		-152.11	
Clubs	Number of regions	β	t-stat	α	S80/S20 club average
Baseline					
Club 1	4	0.31	0.71	0.16	7.96
Club 2	19	-0.01	-0.08	0.00	6.43
Club 3	31	0.53	3.95	0.27	4.96
Club 4	18	0.74	4.67	0.37	4.58
Club 5	29	0.49	3.22	0.24	4.58
Club 6	59	0.20	2.33	0.10	3.80
Club 7	5	1.51	5.68	0.76	3.20

Merging PS					
Club 1 (1)	4	0.31	0.71	0.16	7.96
Club 2 (2)	19	-0.01	-0.08	0.00	6.43
Club 3 (3-5)	78	0.11	1.33	0.06	4.74
Club 4 (6)	59	0.20	2.33	0.10	3.80
Club 5 (7)	5	1.51	5.68	0.76	3.20
non convergent group = ES74					

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: 166 observations available. Are excluded from the sample Germany (37 regions), Croatia (5 regions), Ireland (5 regions), the Netherlands (12 regions), and Portugal (7 regions). For applying the log t test the variable is transformed in a logarithm and the series is also subject to the application of the Prescott (1997) filter to wipe out the cyclical component and to keep the trend component. The smoothing parameter is set to 400. 'Baseline' is the convergence club classification before merging. Applied truncation parameter: $r = 0.333$ (discarded years: 5, starting point for regression 2013), applied critical value: $c = 0$, t-statistic at the 5% significance level: -1.645 ; t-statistic at the 1% significance level: -2.326 . To perform the log t test the routine 'logtreg', developed for Stata (Du, 2017), is used. The "Merging PS and vLT" part of the table shows the results of the cluster analysis, after merging adjacent clusters. For the merging procedure as described in Phillips and Sul the routine developed for Stata (Du, 2017) is used. For the merging procedure as described in von Lyncker and Thoennessen, the routine developed for R (Sichera and Pizzuto, 2019) is used.

Based on the analysis of the **transition paths** for AROP, the overall set of regional transition paths⁶⁶ (Fig 3.3.3a) shows that cross-region differences tend to increase over time but this is clearly due to the trajectories taken by the regions belonging to Club 1 and Club 5. Moreover, the collective overall picture indicates the existence of many clubs with distinct patterns of convergence.

Fig 3.3.3a Overall set of regional transition paths, S80/S20, NUTS 2 level, 2008-2023 (166 obs.)

Fig 3.3.3b Final clubs and within-club convergence, S80/S20, NUTS 2 level, 2005-2023 (166 obs.)⁶⁷

⁶⁶ Computed as (log) inequality index divided by the cross-sectional mean of each year.

⁶⁷ Club 1 includes 4 regions, Club 2 includes 19 regions, Club 3 and Club 4 are the most numerous with, respectively 78 and 59 regions, Club 5 includes 5 regions.

Fig 3.3.3c Transition Paths of the Convergence Clubs, S80/S20, NUTS2 level, 2008-2023 (166 obs.)

Source: Authors' calculation.

The set of regional transition paths grouped by clubs (Figure 3.3.3b) shows a reduction in the income inequality index disparity within each club, while the intensity of convergence varies. For instance, at the end of the sample period, inequality cross-region differences within Club 1 Club 3, and Club 4 are very similar.

Finally, the transition paths of all clubs⁶⁸ (Figure 3.3.3c), which illustrates the long-run tendencies between clubs, suggesting that inequality in Club 1 and Club 2 is systematically above the cross-country mean, whilst Club 4 and Club 5 are systematically below it. Club 3, which is the most numerous, remains around the average with a marginal upward tendency over time. On the one hand, the trajectories of Club 1 and Club 2 converge upwards, and the speed of convergence of the former is higher than the one of the latter. This points to weak convergence. On the other hand, Club 4 and Club 5 converge downward, and the speed of convergence of the former is lower than the one of the latter. Overall, clubs exhibit stronger separating tendencies than GDP and AROP.

A closer look at the convergent clubs (Table 3.3.2b) shows that over the entire period, Club 1 has an S80/S20 club average of close to 8% and is composed of only 4 regions. Also, Club 2 is quite small with

⁶⁸ Computed by taking the cross-country average within each club.

19 regions and a medium-high rate of S80/S20 (6.4%). Club 3 is the most numerous with 78 regions and a medium level of S80/S20 club average (4.7%). Club 4 is the second largest club including 59 regions and presents a medium-low level of S80/S20 (3.8%). Finally, Club 5 has only 5 regions and shows a low level of S80/S20 (3.2%).

Furthermore, the club composition reveals that, similarly to income per capita, a **country effect prevails in the clubs with a medium and medium-low level of inequality**: This is because Club 3 and Club 4 are the most numerous. More specifically, six Member States present a majority of regions in Club 3 (Greece, Spain, Hungary, Italy, Romania and Sweden) and the four member states where NUTS 0 and NUTS 2 levels correspond belong to Club 3 (Cyprus, Estonia, Luxembourg and Malta). Eight Member States present a majority of regions in Club 4 (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Finland, France, Poland, and Slovenia).

Member States' capitals⁶⁹ mostly belong to the club, which has a medium level of inequality. Indeed, Club 3 included 8 capitals and 4 Member States: Wien (AT13), Brussels (BE10), Prague (CZ01), Copenhagen (DK01), Athens (EL30) Helsinki (FI1B), Budapest (HU11), Stockholm (SE11), Cyprus (CY00), Tallinn (EE00), Luxembourg (LU00) and La Valletta (MT00)⁷⁰. Club 2 and Club 4 include respectively 5 and 4 capitals. Only Sofia (BG41) is included in Club 1 and Bratislava (SK01) in Club 5.

Similar reading holds for **metropolitan areas⁷¹, which are generally concentrated in regions belonging to the club with a medium level of inequality.** Almost 50% of the regions including more than two metropolitan areas belong to Club 2 (vs the 20% of the regions belonging to Club 2 and the 27% of the regions belonging to Club 4). Club 1 presents only 4% of the regions including more than 2 metropolitan areas whereas Club 5 never presents more than one metropolitan area.

The urban/rural index indicates that four out of five clubs on average belong to the classification of 'intermediate', with the value of the index ranging from 1.67 to 2.34. Only Club 5 has an average value of 2.37 which collocates it in the 'predominantly rural' group. The urban/rural/remote index indicates that three out of five clubs belong to the classification of 'intermediate, remote'. The remaining two belong to the classification 'intermediate and close to a city'.

Further results related to geographical characteristics will be presented in Section 4.2 as results of the ordered logistic regression.

Table 3.3.2.b Descriptive statistics of geographical variables by S80/S20 convergent clubs

S80/S20, 2008-2023, NUTS 2 (217 observations, non convergent RO32)							
Club	S80/S20 club average	Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Club 1	7.96	N and % of capital	1 (5%)				
		metro	4	1.25	1.26	0	3
		urban/rural	4	2.16	0.86	1	2.83
		urban/rural/remote	4	2.67	1.25	1	3.67
Club2	6.43	N and % of capital	5 (24%)				
		metro	19	1.68	1.92	0	8
		urban/rural	19	1.97	0.51	1	2.67
		urban/rural/remote	19	2.46	0.89	1	4
Club 3	4.74	N and % of capital	12 (57%)				
		metro	78	1.06	1.17	0	6
		urban/rural	78	2.09	0.59	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	78	2.68	1.08	1	5

⁶⁹ For S80/S20 we have available 22 Member States, but the capital of Poland, PL91 (Warsaw), is not included in the sample.

⁷⁰ Where NUTS 2 corresponds to NUTS 0.

⁷¹ According to the 2021 indicator of the number of metropolitan areas at the NUTS 2 level the maximum number of metropolitan areas in a region is 15, but for the case of S80/S20 the maximum number is 8 that is in France.

		N and % of capital	2 (10%)				
Club 4	3.8	metro	59	1.22	1.22	0	7
		urban/rural	59	2.29	0.51	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	59	2.89	0.99	1	5
		N and % of capital	1 (5%)				
Club 5	3.2	metro	5	0.60	0.55	0	1
		urban/rural	5	2.37	0.82	1	3
		urban/rural/remote	5	3.03	1.36	1	4.5

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: 'metro' is the number of metropolitan areas, 'urban/rural' is an index varying between 1 and 3 so that for values ≤ 1.67 the region is considered 'predominantly urban', for values > 1.67 and ≤ 2.34 the region is considered 'intermediate' and for values > 2.34 the region is considered 'predominantly rural'. 'Urban/rural/remote' is an index varying between 1 and 5, so that for values ≤ 1.8 the region is considered 'predominantly urban', for values > 1.8 and ≤ 2.6 the region is considered 'intermediate, close to a city', for values > 2.6 and ≤ 3.4 the region is considered 'intermediate, remote', for values > 3.4 and ≤ 4.2 the region is considered 'predominantly rural, close to a city', and for values > 4.2 the region is considered 'predominantly rural, remote'.

4. Ordered logit regression results

The second step of the analysis consists of identifying potential determinants or factors that can lead a region into a convergent club rather than another. The exercise is done for each of the variables measuring the standard of living.

4.1 Ordered logit regression for GDP per capita club convergence formation

In the econometric exercise for identifying some of the determinants in the formation of the convergent clubs in GDP per capita, we estimate four models (Table 4.1.1). Model 1 includes only variables describing the sectoral structure of the economy as this allows including the maximum number of observations. Models 2, 3 and 4 incorporate regressors related to the three transformations – (digital) technology, globalisation and migration – as well as a geographical index

In all model specifications (from Model 1 to Model 4)⁷² the logit coefficients of the economy's sectoral composition are always statistically significant and present the expected sign. A positive sign for the share of employment in the Information and communication sector (NACE J) and the Financial sector (NACE K), both characterised by a high level of technology and/or a highly qualified labour force, are positively associated with higher income clubs. On the contrary, the routine services (NACE G, K and I) generally characterised by a high share of low-skilled workers, are negatively associated with higher income clubs. As far as the sign related to the share of employment in Manufacturing (NACE C), our results suggest a positive association with the higher-income clubs⁷³.

Table 4.1.1 Logit regression results (logit coefficients), clubs in GDP per capita income in PPS

	Model 1 Logit coeff.	Model 2 Logit coeff.	Model 3 Logit coeff.	Model 4 Logit coeff.
Empl. share Manufacturing	9.282***	9.259***	7.476**	5.269^

⁷² Marginal results are shown in Annex A4.1.

⁷³ In this case the expected sign is debatable. Mazzola and Pizzuto (2020), referring to Brankman et al. (2015), claim that leading regions tend to be less specialized in low-tech manufacturing. By using the share of GVA in manufacturing they find a negative and statistically significant sign. Cutrini (2019), instead, using the employment share as in our case, finds a positive and statistically significant sign.

	(2.686)	(3.097)	(3.356)	(3.557)
Empl. share Routine	-12.03***	-10.08*	-13.03*	-12.47*
	(4.182)	(5.577)	(6.731)	(6.701)
Empl. share Finance	83.67***	51.20*	57.99*	55.97^
	(25.31)	(30.92)	(34.04)	(34.21)
Empl. share ICT	82.61***	54.65**	54.97**	53.25*
		(25.11)	(27.53)	(28.12)
3.0 4.0 Creation degree		0.529***	0.565***	0.516***
		(0.170)	(0.192)	(0.196)
High risk of job automation			0.585	0.944*
			(0.470)	(0.502)
Green patent & tech				3.023**
				(1.470)
FDI type class		0.523***	0.427**	0.405**
		(0.193)	(0.192)	(0.194)
FDI potential			0.343^	0.383^
			(0.227)	(0.236)
Migration (RWI)		20.31**	19.72*	10.03
		(10.01)	(10.19)	(11.39)
Remoteness		-1.998**	-1.415	-1.712^
		(0.986)	(1.083)	(1.114)
Observations	242	210	198	198
Pseudo R2	0.287	0.371	0.363	0.375

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. For the regressions in the case of AROP, Club 3 (with 8 regions) has been merged with Club 2 as it is recommended that the categories should be not less than 5% each. Thus, in this case, we have a logit regression with as a dependent variable a dummy for identifying Club 1.

As independent variables related to the three main transformations, (digital) technology, globalisation, and migration, we use three explanatory factors for each of the first two transformations, plus one variable to proxy regional migration⁷⁴.

(Digital) technology is proxied by three variables: the '3.0 and 4.0 tech creation', the share of regional jobs at high risk of automation and the 'degree of green patent and green technology'. For all of them, a positive and statistically significant logit coefficient is found. This means that regions with higher values in terms of the ability to create high-tech technology, a high share of jobs that are at risk of being substituted by machines and high availability of green patents and green technology are more likely to belong to a club with a higher GDP per capita converging level.

Globalisation is also proxied by two variables: a composite indicator of openness to incoming foreign direct investments (FDI), and a composite indicator of the degree of FDI attractiveness. Both present a coefficient with a positive and significant coefficient meaning that regions with higher values for

⁷⁴ Due to the lack of data in the NUTS 2 dimension, the independent variables have been included in batches, rather than all at once. This approach allows to maximise the number of available observations, which ranges from 210 in the Model 1b and 198 in the Model 2b and Model 3b.

openness of incoming FDI⁷⁵ and degree of FDI attractiveness is more likely to belong to a club with a higher GDP per capita converging level.⁷⁶

Migration is proxied by the ‘migration regional weighted intensity’ (RWI), which determines the impact of intra-EU migration considering both the volume of migration flows and the size of the regional population. The indicator provides a measure of the relative importance of migration for a region in relation to its population size. The indicator presents a positive and significant sign in **Model 2** and **Model 3**, indicating that regions where the relative importance of migrants to the population is higher are more likely to belong to clubs with higher GDP. Attempts to include, alternatively, the ‘crude rate of net migration plus statistical adjustment’ and the ‘labour regional interregional balance – inflows’⁷⁷ do not lead to significant coefficients, and the results are not shown in the table.

Finally, the geographical variables (e.g. the number of metropolitan areas and the urban/rural index) are generally highly correlated with other regressors. For example, the capital dummy and the number of metropolitan areas are highly correlated with the ICT and the financial, or the rural/urban index is highly correlated with the FDI type class. For this reason, we have included only the ‘remoteness index’ as it is more granular compared to other geographical variables used above. The sign is negative and statistically significant in Model 2 and marginally statistically significant in Model 4, indicating that regions with a higher degree of remote areas are more likely to belong to a club with a lower GDP per capita converging level.

4.2 Ordered logit regression for AROP and S80/S20 GDP club convergence formation

Following the literature, the identification of the drivers of convergent clubs for poverty and inequality primarily focuses on factors linked to human capital development (e.g., level of education, level of skill in the workforce, and adult learning including upskilling and reskilling) and labour market outcomes (e.g., employment and unemployment rates). Moreover, among the three main transformations this study deals with, the (digital) technological transformation seems to be the most relevant.

Digitalisation impacts labour market dynamics and, hence, poverty and income inequality through income and labour market channels. The impact of technological and digital transformation on poverty and inequality is transmitted via the labour market by impacting labour demand, labour supply and the interplay between these two. On the demand side, digital transformation has the potential to influence workers' employment and wage outcomes, and consequently poverty and inequality of individuals in two main ways. As explained in Richiardi et al. (2024 forthcoming) on the one hand, although digital technology advancements may result in the displacement of workers and a decrease in employment and wages, it is also plausible that the digital transformation is accompanied by job creation, employment, and wage increases through a positive productivity effect. On the supply side, digital transformation affects labour supply mainly via acquiring skills (including digital skills). Access to the

⁷⁵ As explained in Section 2.3 the ‘FDI type class’ includes five distinct categories, in turn, calculated based on six indicators. As a robustness exercise, the six indicators are taken individually and included in the model. The results obtained show that the indicators are all significant except the ‘regional external influence’. Furthermore, they all show positive and significant coefficients except for the ‘regional network selectivity’. Thus regions with higher values of ‘connectivity’ ‘intensity’, ‘regional weighted intensity’, ‘regional interregional balance’ and ‘regional send receive balance’ (measuring correspond to higher-income clubs).

⁷⁶ Data on extra EU FDI are more limited both in terms of NUTS coverage and reliability. Nevertheless, two indicators ‘Extra-EU FDI number’ and ‘Extra-EU FDI volume’ measuring, respectively, the total number and the total deal value of incoming FDI projects originating from extra EU, are included in the regression exercise. However, the results are not statistically significant and not shown.

⁷⁷ That is a proxy for the degree of commuting.

internet and digital tools favours knowledge enhancement via open online courses and/or whole academic paths. Finally, the effect on labour market outcomes depends upon the extent to which the skills acquired match (do not match) labour demand, originating flows in and out of employment. The impact on poverty and income distribution goes through the activity status of individual workers and to the extent that the probability of being in the pool of those belonging to the job destructed (created) or transformed hit the lower (medium and upper) part of the distribution. This section aims to focus on these dynamics.

Table 4.2.a Ordered logit regression results (logit coefficients), clubs in AROP and S80/S20

	Model 1 Logit coeff. AROP	Model 2 Logit coeff. S80/S20	Model 3 Logit coeff. AROP	Model 4 Logit coeff. S80/S20	Model 5 Logit coeff. AROP	Model 6 Logit coeff. S80/S20
Empl. rate 25-34	0.119*** (0.0308)	0.102*** (0.0321)	0.110*** (0.0296)	0.0968*** (0.0300)	0.105*** (0.0299)	0.0902*** (0.0305)
Education (3-8)	0.0445** (0.0174)	0.0867*** (0.0234)	0.0393** (0.0171)	0.0782*** (0.0212)	0.0374** (0.0170)	0.0612*** (0.0223)
H-R of job autom.	-1.595*** (0.420)	-3.246*** (0.591)	-0.618* (0.345)	-1.415*** (0.419)	-0.878** (0.394)	-2.435*** (0.547)
Robot adoption (a)	-0.611*** (0.146)	-0.981*** (0.199)				
Robot adoption (b)			-0.0410 (0.142)	-0.205 (0.357)		
Robot adoption (c)					-0.289 (0.207)	-0.992*** (0.319)
Displ./creation HS	0.378* (0.220)	0.290 (0.289)	0.326^ (0.225)	0.380 (0.264)	0.361^ (0.221)	0.363 (0.273)
Displ./creation LS	-0.606** (0.264)	-0.477^ (0.331)	-0.545** (0.266)	-0.425 (0.300)	-0.561** (0.262)	-0.380 (0.311)
FDI type class	-0.109 (0.123)	-0.698*** (0.185)	-0.114 (0.122)	-0.615*** (0.170)	-0.106 (0.122)	-0.629*** (0.175)
Migration (RWI)	-9.112 (8.827)	0.580 (11.47)	-26.59*** (8.363)	-13.86 (10.23)	-23.12*** (8.061)	-7.565 (10.39)
Remoteness	-0.808 (0.774)	-1.418^ (0.944)	-0.490 (0.808)	-1.510* (0.903)	-0.579 (0.785)	-1.711* (0.907)
Observations	183	144	183	144	183	144
Pseudo R2	0.173	0.355	0.132	0.256	0.136	0.290

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. For the regressions in the case of AROP, Club 5 (with 3 regions) has been merged with Club 4. In the case of S80/S20 Club 1 (with 4 regions) has been merged with Club 2 and Club 5 (with 7 regions) has been merged with Club 4. In the context of the ordinal logistic regression model, it is recommended that the categories should be not less than 5% each. H-R stays for high-risk, Robot adoption (a) is in technology manufacturing sectors, robot adoption (b) is in carrier manufacturing sectors and robot adoption (c) is in induced manufacturing sectors. HS and LS stay for high-skilled and low-skilled, respectively. Remoteness is the urban/rural/remote index.

Table 4.2a (Models 1-6)⁷⁸ includes the analysis of factors affecting AROP and S80/S20 convergent clubs. It shows that the logit coefficient⁷⁹ is positive and statistically significant for the employment rate aged 25-34⁸⁰ and the percentage of the population aged 25-64 with a level of education ISCED 3 – 8. The

⁷⁸ Marginal results are shown in Annex A4.2.

⁷⁹ As a general rule for the interpretation of the sign of the coefficients for poverty and inequality is that e the positive sign indicates a positive effect namely the probability of being in a lower club in terms of poverty/income inequality. A negative sign has a negative effect, namely the probability of being in a higher club in terms of poverty/inequality.

⁸⁰ This result is confirmed also when the population aged 20-64 is used (not shown in the regression tables).

results hold both for AROP and for S80/S20. Thus, regions with higher employment rates and higher value of human capital are associated with clubs where the percentage of individuals below the poverty line, as well as the inequality index, is lower.

As far as the (digital) technological transformation is concerned, five different indicators are used. The logit coefficient of the high risk of job automation⁸¹ is negative and statistically significant. A higher share of regional jobs at high risk of automation is associated with clubs where the percentage of at-risk-of-poverty individuals, as well as, the inequality index, is higher⁸². This is possibly due to substituting human activities with machines, which may affect low-skilled workers the most. These latter can be displaced towards jobs with a lower income and/or lose their status of employment. Replacing the high risk of job automation with the average risk of job automation across occupations does not change the results in terms of sign and significance⁸³. The explanation could be that the average risk of job automation is higher for the 'low-skill' occupations. To the model are also added three variables representing the robot adoption, that are included alternatively as they are highly correlated: a) the robot adoption in technology manufacturing sectors; b) the robot adoption in the carrier manufacturing sectors c) the robot adoption in induced manufacturing sectors. In **Model 1** and **Model 2**, a negative and significant relationship is found with robot adoption in the technology manufacturing sector. This indicates that regions with a higher stock of robots per employee are associated with clubs where the poverty and inequality indexes are higher. As for the case of the risk of job automation, the negative effect can be explained by the displacement effect possibly of the low-skilled.

The indicator of displacement and creation of high-skill jobs (low-skill jobs) shows a positive (negative) and statistically significant sign for AROP but is not significant for S80/S20. Thus, regions characterised by a lower level of displacement, a higher level of technology adoption coupled with a higher level of job creation for the high-skill (low-skill) are associated with clubs where poverty is lower (higher). This conclusion is further supported when using two separate dummy variables to indicate regions with high rates of job creation and technology adoption for high-skilled and low-skilled jobs, respectively as shown in **Table 4.2b** in the Annex. From this latter table is more evident that the positive effect of the high-skilled coefficient is lower than the negative effect of the low-skilled coefficient. Job creation is known to have a beneficial impact on poverty, nevertheless, the exact impact of an increase in the employment rate on the median income is contingent upon a variety of factors, such as the categories of jobs being added, the wages associated with those positions, and the overall distribution of income. Thus, the following explanations may hold. For the high-skilled, the positive logit coefficient in AROP may reflect that a part of the high-skilled is not necessarily in the high-income part of the distribution, possibly because a share of the high-skilled belongs to the youngest cohort at the first work experience. For the low-skilled, the negative logit coefficient on AROP may reflect the fact that the combination of low earnings and unstable working conditions outweighs the positive impact of the job creation. It can be the case of the creation of gig jobs⁸⁴. The impact on poverty, but not on inequality, may be determined by the fact that S80/S20 has limited scope as it exclusively evaluates the top 20% and poorest 20% of the income distribution disregarding what happens in the middle range of the distribution. The significant coefficients for AROP, but not for S80/S20, may indicate that job creation and wages impact individuals within a middle level of income, excluding those in the highest and lowest 20 per cent of the distribution. This effect applies to both high-skill and low-skill individuals.

⁸¹ Is the "automation process of substitution of human activities with machines".

Source: https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/Final_Report%20Scientific.pdf

⁸² Regions heavily reliant on routine, manual, or repetitive tasks may face greater risks. Adding the share of employment in the routine sector, indeed, almost double the coefficient of the high risk of job automation. (results not shown in tables) in the case of AROP and marginally in the case of S80/S20 (results not shown in tables).

⁸³ Results are not shown in the table.

⁸⁴ "Short-term (low value-added) work"

Furthermore, the lack of significance for the coefficient of the inequality index can be a symptom of the fact that the wage polarisation, a gap between well-paid skilled jobs and low-paid, least-skilled ones, brought about by the digital transformation is not particularly pronounced⁸⁵.

Only one indicator of globalisation is kept in **Models 1** to **Model 6**, the openness⁸⁶ to the incoming FDI which shows negative and statistically significant coefficients. In this case, a higher degree of openness to the incoming intra-EU FDI is associated with clubs where the percentage of individuals below the poverty line, as well as the inequality index, is higher. The migration coefficient is negative and statistically significant only in Model 3 and Model 5 (and not in Model 1 probably due to the high positive and statistically significant correlation with the robot adoption per employee in the manufacturing technology) indicating that regions where the relative importance of migrants to the population is higher are more likely to belong to clubs with a higher percentage of poor.

Regarding the geographical variables, the descriptive statistics presented in Sections 3.2.2 and 3.3.2 suggest that Member State's capitals, as well as metropolitan regions, tend to belong to the club with a medium level of both AROP and S80/S20, while the value of the urban/rural index (as well as that of the urban/rural/remote index) taken at its average club value is similar among clubs. In the ordered logit regressions, as in the case of the GDP, some geographical variables are highly correlated with other regressors. For example, the capital dummy or the rural/urban index is highly correlated with the FDI type class. For this reason, only the urban/rural/remote index is included as it is more granular (as explained in Section 2.4). Once controlled for other regressors, the coefficient has a negative and statistically significant sign in **Model 4** and **Model 6** and marginally statistically significant in **Model 2**, indicating that regions with a higher level of remote areas are more likely to belong to a club with a higher S80/S20 converging level.

4.3 Further research development and methodological considerations

The findings and research challenges highlighted in this paper offer a valuable reference for future research. In particular, areas such as enhancing poverty and inequality data series, addressing methodological concerns regarding the importance of time series length, and advancing interpretative analyses—especially concerning the impact of technological and digital transformation on inequality and poverty—present promising avenues for further investigation.

Regional analysis at the NUTS 2 level, covering all the EU Member States is made complex by the paucity of data in both cross-sectional and time-series dimensions. At the moment, the richest dataset available is the ARDECO one, covering mainly domestic product, employment, labour cost, labour productivity, capital formation and capital stock. Limitations related to the availability of data for poverty and inequality indicators are particularly pronounced as can be deduced by the small number of publications specifically devoted to this aspect. Moreover, the challenges would be amplified if the commonly used indicators, such as AROP, AROPE, and S20/S80, were to be combined with other distribution indicators aimed at investigating more specific aspects, such as the depth of poverty or the inequality among other income quintiles. Alternatively, considering the club formation based on wage differentials and gaps may lead to more detailed results.

Convergence studies have gained significant traction in recent years, particularly through the Phillips and Sul (2007, 2009) methodology, later refined by von Lyncker and Thoennessen (2017) and applied to a range of fields beyond economics (e.g., Tomal, 2023). While this method offers notable advantages, it is sensitive to time series length and cross-sectional entities, often identifying more clubs when the time frame is shorter.

⁸⁵ See for example the conclusions of Capello et al. (2024).

⁸⁶ Openness is a concise expression for a more complex concept as explained in Section 2.3.

Looking ahead, expanding the analysis of poverty and inequality in response to rapid technological change is essential requires extending beyond traditional AROP and S80/S20 indicators. Additionally, investigating disparities between high- and low-skilled workers could help assess the wage polarisation hypothesis within the EU. From a methodological perspective, geographic regressors will be crucial, as they account for time-invariant characteristics that may exhibit non-linear relationships with poverty and inequality clubs. Greater focus on interaction terms with other variables will enhance the understanding of these dynamics.

5. Conclusions

The aim of this paper is twofold. First, it explores regional convergence in the EU-27 by examining multiple indicators of living standards, expanding beyond the traditional measure of GDP per capita to include poverty (AROP) and inequality (S80/S20 ratio). Second, it assesses the extent to which convergence is shaped by major trends, specifically: technological change, globalisation, and regional migration. While these trends are traditionally viewed in economic literature as catalysts for growth and, as a consequence, drivers of lower inequality and poverty, recent policy debates have raised concerns that they may in fact contribute to the opposite effects.

The analysis employs a two-stage empirical approach. First, the concept of club convergence is tested using the time-varying factor model by Phillips and Sul (2007a, 2007b, 2009), which accounts for regional heterogeneity and transitional dynamics. In the second stage, an ordered logit model is used to identify the determinants that influence the formation of convergent clubs.

To conduct this analysis at the regional level, gaps in readily available indicators of poverty and income inequality, have been closed, to the extent possible, using various statistical strategies mainly exploiting the additional information available in the EU-SILC microdata. Overall, coverage of approximately 90% (70%) of the NUTS 2 regions for AROP (S80/S20) over the period 2005-2023 (2008-2023) has been achieved.

The paper presents a large set of findings. Firstly, the paper finds that the hypothesis of overall income regional convergence over the period 2000-2023, as measured by GDP per capita, is rejected, whereas that of club convergence is supported. The club convergence analysis of the GDP per capita in PPS reveals three clubs with Club 2, which has a medium level of GDP per capita, counting the highest number of regions. After 2007, the clubs show moderate diverging tendencies. This finding is in line with ascertained findings in the literature that the EU regional convergence process was very strong (and fast) until 2007 and then was interrupted by the crisis. Club 1, which is systematically above the cross-country mean, slightly diverges from the mean upwards. Club 2 presents a more constant path by marginally diverging from the mean downwards. Club 3 diverges from the mean downwards. Capital regions, those including a large number of metropolitan areas and those prevalently urban, are generally concentrated in the highest club, suggesting a tendency towards spatial polarisation following an urban-rural logic, which results in a substantial disparity in terms of GDP per capita between a smaller club of high-income metropolitan regions and a larger club with lower income, mostly rural, regions.

Secondly and similarly to GDP per capita, the hypothesis of overall regional convergence in income poverty and inequality is rejected, whereas club convergence is confirmed. For both indicators, five clubs are identified, hence more than for income. However, the two largest clubs—encompassing the large majority of EU-27 regions—remain relatively stable and close to the mean, which is a broad encouraging finding. The comparison of the transition paths indicates that the AROP clubs show separating tendencies more marked than in the GDP per capita, but marginally less evident than in S80/S20. The S80/S20 clubs exhibit the most marked separating tendencies, higher than in the GDP per capita and AROP. Capitals and metropolitan regions tend to belong to the club with a medium level of both AROP and inequality, suggesting that the spatial polarisation (urban/rural) emerging from

income is not a key feature of poverty and inequality. In other words, regions with high growth are not necessarily the ones with the lowest inequality/poverty, nor the highest. Interestingly, while poverty and inequality indicators are available for different periods, and there is not a full match between the composition of the clubs associated with the two variables, most regions in the middle clubs are the same. This is also confirmed by a relatively high and (statistically significant) correlation among those clubs.

As an additional finding, it is worth highlighting that the conclusions coming from convergence analysis can vary substantially depending on the period considered, with the inclusion of the period around the euro area debt crisis changing drastically the results. In the club convergence analysis, the number and the composition of clubs are significantly influenced by the period considered and the length of the time series, but the broad consideration holds also for other measures of convergence. This is important to keep in mind when comparing results and when drawing policy implications.

As far as the factors affecting convergent clubs are concerned a few findings stand out.

We find that the likelihood of being part of the high-income club is positively affected by the share of manufacturing and high-end/high-skill services (e.g. finance and ITC). By contrast, a large share of the low-skill service sector (wholesale and retail trade, transport and storage and accommodation and food service activities) negatively affects such a likelihood. More interestingly, we find that digitalisation, globalisation and regional migration are all associated with a higher probability of being in the high-income club. More specifically, for the digital technology proxied by i) a '4.0 technology creation degree' ii) the share of regional jobs at high risk of job automation; iii) the 'degree of green patent and green technology', it is found that regions with higher values for these variables are more likely to belong to a club with a higher GDP per capita. For globalisation that is proxied by financial integration in the EU as measured by: i) a composite indicator of 'openness incoming EU Foreign Direct Investments (FDI); and ii) a composite indicator of the degree of "FDI attractiveness", is found that regions with higher values for openness of incoming FDI and degree of FDI attractiveness are more likely to belong to a club with a higher GDP per capita converging level. Data on extra EU FDI, which suffer limitations in terms of regional coverage and reliability, are not statistically significant. Finally, for regional migration measured by the 'crude rate of net migration plus statistical adjustment' and the 'migration regional weighted intensity', it is found that only the latter has a positive and significant coefficient.

For the formation of the poverty and inequality convergence club, globalisation does not appear to significantly increase the likelihood of belonging to any specific poverty or inequality convergence club. This was expected as, following the literature, the link with macroeconomic trends is usually insignificant, whereas individuals' characteristics, such as the level of education or adult learning, and labour market outcomes, such as employment and unemployment rates play an important role. Consistent with this, we find that employment rate and high educational attainment are associated with a higher probability of a region of being in the low-inequality and low-poverty clubs. However, technological and digital transformation seems to increase the likelihood of belonging to higher-poverty or higher-inequality clubs. Technological transformation can influence employment and wage outcomes in different directions, either resulting in the displacement of workers and a decrease in employment and wages or generating job creation, employment, and wage increases. A higher risk of job automation and robotisation are both associated with a higher probability of being in clubs where the percentage of individuals below the poverty line, as well as the inequality index, is higher. Similarly, although the results are less robust, regional migration, under certain specifications, is associated with a higher probability of being in clubs with higher inequality and poverty.

Overall, the paper suggests that the process of EU convergence has not stopped, however it is heterogeneous. While the largest number of regions slowly move together, some regions are drifting apart, making the process uneven and the distance between higher and low-income regions bigger. A similar pattern holds for inequality and poverty, but regions drifting apart are not necessarily the same.

While for income the rural-urban divide seems the key factor for understanding income convergence patterns, for poverty and inequality, no clear distinctive factors could be identified. Finally, digital transformation appears to be associated with upward income convergence but also convergence towards higher inequality and poverty. This deserves careful policy consideration.

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Annexes

A1. NUTS classification

Table A1.1 List of the 27 EU Member States with the number of regions at NUTS 2 level

AT	Austria (9 regions)	ES	Spain (19 regions)	LV	Latvia (1 region)
BE	Belgium (11 regions)	FI	Finland (5 regions)	MT	Malta (1 region)
BG	Bulgaria (6 regions)	FR	France (27 regions)	NL	Netherlands (12 regions)
CY	Cyprus (1 region)	HR	Croatia (5 regions)	PL	Poland (17 regions)
CZ	Czechia (8 regions)	HU	Hungary (9 regions)	PT	Portugal (7 regions)
DE	Germany (38 regions)	IE	Ireland (5 regions)	RO	Romania (8 regions)
DK	Denmark (5 regions)	IT	Italy (21 regions)	SE	Sweden (8 regions)
EE	Estonia (1 region)	LT	Lithuania (3 regions)	SI	Slovenia (4 regions)
EL	Greece (13 regions)	LU	Luxembourg (1 region)	SK	Slovakia (4 regions)

Note: In parenthesis the number of regions at NUTS 2 level according to the 2021 classification.

The analysis framework of the study consists of NUTS 2 regions, a statistical system regulated in the European Union by the Directorate of Statistics (EUROSTAT). NUTS (Nomenclature Units for Territorial Statistics) are a common statistical information system used to sustain cohesion and regional development policy (after the '80s). After the reform of structural funds, the NUTS 2 level became increasingly significant, serving as the foundation for the formulation of and implementation of specific actions in regions with developmental challenges. The NUTS 2 regions are eligible to access structural funds for objective 1, which is considered the most optimal level for community action and the most effective application of the subsidiary principle within the cohesion policy.

The 2021 NUTS⁸⁷ 2 classification we are referring to in this report is valid from 1 January 2021 and, for the EU-27, lists 92 regions at NUTS 1, 242 regions at NUTS 2 and 1166 regions at NUTS 3 level⁸⁸. Amendments were established in 2006, 2010, 2013 and 2016. Another extraordinary amendment was organised in 2014 following a substantial reorganisation of the administrative structure in Portugal. In order to obtain a balanced panel, in some cases, it was necessary to reclassify NUTS 2 from previous years into NUTS 2021 according to the available crosswalks provided by Eurostat.⁸⁹

⁸⁷ Nomenclature Units for Territorial Statistics are a common statistical information system used to sustain the cohesion and regional development policy (after the '80s).

⁸⁸ Eurostat (2022a), "Statistical regions in the European Union and partner countries NUTS and statistical regions 2021 – 2020 Edition", Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

Retrieved at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-manuals-and-guidelines/-/KS-GQ-20-092>

Eurostat (2022b), "Statistical regions in the European Union and partner countries NUTS and statistical regions 2021 – 2022 Edition", Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

Retrieved at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-manuals-and-guidelines/-/KS-GQ-22-010>

⁸⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/history>

Recently a NUTS converter tool has been offered. "The 'NUTS Converter' is an open, web-based tool enabling the conversion of European regional statistical data between different versions of the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) classification". <https://urban.jrc.ec.europa.eu/tools?lng=en>

A2. Empirical methodology and data

A2.1 Details on the Ordered Logit Model

In the Ordered Logit Model regression results can be presented in various formats among which, in this study, are used the ‘log-odds (logit) coefficients’⁹⁰ and the ‘marginal effects’. The interpretation of the ordered logit coefficient is as follows: for one unit variation of the independent variable level, the dependent variable is expected to vary by its respective regression coefficient in the ordered log-odds scale, ceteris paribus, namely while the other variables in the model are kept constant. Nevertheless, when considering the logit coefficients, it is difficult to get a tangible feel for how large and important the differences between the independent variables are, whereas much more importance must be given to their sign and statistical significance⁹¹. Instead, the marginal effects are computed for each level of the dependent variable (in this case, the different clubs). They represent the change in the probability of each outcome category (namely the change in the probability of being in a certain club) due to a small change in a predictor variable, holding other variables constant. As suggested by (Long and Freese, 2014) the marginal effects are instantaneous rate of change in the probability of belonging to a specific club given a small change in explanatory variables. The ordinal logistic model assumes a monotonic relationship between predictors and the latent variable. However, the marginal effects on the probability of being in specific categories are not guaranteed to be monotonic⁹². Furthermore, the total of the marginal coefficients must be equal to 0. In this study, the marginal effects at the mean (MEM) are used. McFadden's r squared is used. and is a measure of goodness of fit. Usually, 0.2 - 0.4 indicates a very good fit. While pseudo-R-squares cannot be interpreted independently or compared across datasets, they are valid and useful in evaluating multiple models predicting the same outcome on the same dataset. In other words, a pseudo-R-squared statistic without context has little meaning. A pseudo-R-squared only has meaning when compared to another pseudo-R-squared of the same type, on the same data, predicting the same outcome. In this situation, the higher pseudo-R-squared indicates which model better predicts the outcome.

A2.2 Methodology for missing data integration in NUTS 2 level (AROP and S80/S20).

Readily available data at the NUTS 2 level for the indicators AROP⁹³ and S80/S20⁹⁴ are limited both in the cross-region and time-series dimensions. To enhance the representativeness of the sample the following steps have been adopted in the order specified below:

- a. EU-SILC microdata based on the variable “region of residence”⁹⁵ only when it is available at the NUTS 2 level. This allows computing:

⁹⁰ Alternatively, it can be obtained the ‘odds-ratios’ that when greater than 1 correspond to ‘positive effects’ because they increase the odds. Those an ‘odds-ratio’ between 0 and 1 correspond to ‘negative effects’ because they decrease the odds. Odds ratios of exactly 1 correspond to ‘no association’ An odds ratio cannot be less than 0. The odds ratios can be obtained by exponentiating the ordered logit coefficients.

⁹¹ Long and Freese (2014 pag. 228): “Consequently, tables of logit coefficients typically have little value for conveying the magnitude of effects”.

⁹² If this was the case, for some predictors, the marginal effect on the probability of being in a particular category may not be monotonic. For example, increasing a predictor might increase the probability of being in a middle category while decreasing the probability of being in the lowest and highest categories.

⁹³ Eurostat code: ilc_li41 and tgs00103.

⁹⁴ Eurostat code: ilc_di11_r.

⁹⁵ EU SILC code: db040 refers to the region of the residence of the household at the date of the interview and depending on the MS can be recorded at NUTS 0, 1 or 2 level.

- The at-risk-of-poverty rate based on the variable “poverty indicator” – hx080.
 - The inequality index S80/S20 based on the variable “equivalised disposable income” – hx090
- b. EU-SILC microdata based on the combination of the variable “region of residence” when it is available at NUTS 1 level only and the variable “degree of urbanisation”⁹⁶. In some cases, combining the two variables allows us to uniquely identify a region at the NUTS 2 level.

Under points a. and b. the following variables are used:

- The at-risk-of-poverty rate based on the variable “poverty indicator” – hx080.
 - The inequality index S80/S20 based on the variable “equivalised disposable income” – hx090
- c. Various methodologies for backcasting and interpolation when point a. and point b. are not feasible, given a certain availability of the regional data in the time-series dimension.

The computations have been recorded in the NUTS 2 2021 classification. Nevertheless, the conversion between various classifications of NUTS 2 is not always possible, without having access to the more detailed level NUTS 3, for example, due to changes in boundaries.⁹⁷

A2.3 Description of dependent and independent variables

Table A2.3.1 Description of dependent variables

Dependent variables
<p>Variable: GDP per capita in PPS Definition: Real GDP per capita is the total value of all the goods and services produced by a country in a particular year (controlled for inflation rates), divided by the number of people living there and expressed in PPS. Period available: 2000-2025 (2024 and 2025 are forecast) Source: ARDECO, code (SUVGDP)</p>
<p>Variable: AROP Definition: The at-risk-of-poverty rate is the share of people with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers. Period available: 2005-2023 with gaps. Source: Eurostat, code (ilc_li41 and tgs00103)</p>
<p>Variable: S80/S20 Definition: income quintile share (S80/S20) ratio, which is the ratio of total income received by the 20% of the population with the highest income (the top quintile) to that received by the 20% of the population with the lowest income (the bottom quintile). Period available: 2005-2023 with gaps. Source: Eurostat, code (ilc_di11_r)</p>

⁹⁶ EU SILC code: DB100. The Degree of urbanisation (DEGURBA) is a classification that indicates the character of an area. Based on the share of the local population living in urban clusters and in urban centres, it classifies local administrative units level 2 (LAU2) into three types of area: thinly populated area (rural area); intermediate density area (towns and suburbs/small urban area), and densely populated area (cities/large urban area). Eurostat (2023), “Degree of urbanisation classification - 2011 revision”, Statistic Explained, retrieved at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/SEPDF/cache/31486.pdf>

⁹⁷ For the changes that occurred through the different classifications of NUTS 2 see: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/history>

Table A2.3.2 Description of independent variables used in the ordered logit regressions, NUTS 2 level

Economic control variables (economic structure, employment rate and human capital)
<p>Name: Employment share⁹⁸</p> <p>Subcategories: <u>Manufacturing employment share</u> (NACE C); <u>Routine employment share</u> includes Wholesale and retail commerce (NACE G), Transport and storage (NACE H), and Accommodation and food service activities (NACE I); <u>Information and communication employment share</u> (NACE J); <u>Financial sector employment share</u> (NACE K).</p> <p>Definition: Employment by industry is a workplace-based measure and therefore attributes people to the region in which they work rather than where they live. This variable measures the number of jobs available in a region, rather than the employed persons living in that region.</p> <p>Period available: 2000-2023</p> <p>Source: Eurostat, code (nama_10r_3empers)</p>
<p>Variable: Employment rate</p> <p>Definition: Employment rate of the population aged 23 to 34 years old.</p> <p>Period available: 2000-2023</p> <p>Source: Eurostat, code (lfst_r_lfe2emprr)</p>
<p>Name: Education</p> <p>Definition: Percentage of people aged 25–64 with upper secondary, postsecondary, non-tertiary, and tertiary education (ISCED levels 3–8).</p> <p>Period available: 2000-2023</p> <p>Source: Eurostat, code (edat_lfse_04)</p>
Geographical
<p>Variable: Metro</p> <p>Definition: Number of metropolitan areas in a region. These regions are defined as urban agglomerations (NUTS level 3 regions or groups of NUTS level 3 regions) where at least 50 % of the population lives inside a functional urban area (FUA) that is composed of at least 250,000 inhabitants.</p> <p>Period available: 2021 – time-invariant</p> <p>Source: Eurostat retrievable at https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/history</p>
<p>Variable: Urban/rural typology</p> <p>Definition: Type of region identified as belonging to three categories: i) predominantly urban, ii) intermediate, and iii) predominantly rural. The original variable has three categories: predominantly urban, intermediate and predominantly rural.⁹⁹ From this, a simple index varying between 1 and 3 is constructed. Specifically, for values ≤ 1.67 the region is considered ‘predominantly urban’, for values > 1.67 and ≤ 2.34 the region is considered ‘intermediate’ and for values > 2.34 the region is considered ‘predominantly rural’. As the information on these characteristics is provided at the more granular spatial level of the NUTS 3 regional classification, we constructed the corresponding variables by computing an average at the NUTS 2 regional classification.</p> <p>Period available: 2021 – time-invariant</p> <p>Source: Eurostat retrievable at https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/history</p>
<p>Variable: Urban/rural remoteness typology</p> <p>Definition: Type of region identified as belonging to five categories: i) predominantly urban, ii) intermediate, close to a city, iii) intermediate, remote, iv) predominantly rural, close to a city, and v) predominantly rural, remote. From this, a simple index varying between 1 and 5 is constructed. Specifically, for values ≤ 1.8 the region is considered ‘predominantly urban’, for values > 1.8 and ≤ 2.6 the region is considered ‘intermediate, close to a city’, for values > 2.6 and ≤ 3.4 the region is considered ‘intermediate, remote’, for values > 3.4 and ≤ 4.2 the region is considered ‘predominantly rural, close to a city’, and for values > 4.2 the region is considered ‘predominantly rural, remote’. As the information on these characteristics is provided at the more granular spatial level of the NUTS 3 regional classification, we constructed the corresponding variables by computing an average at the NUTS 2 regional classification.</p> <p>Period available: 2021 – time-invariant</p>

⁹⁸ Sectoral composition of the economy is used also in Bartowska and Riedl (2012) which employs the share of GVA in high-tech production and the share of GVA in services, Cutrini (2019) adds also further sectors.

⁹⁹ As the information on these characteristics is provided at the more granular spatial level of the NUTS 3 regional classification, we constructed the corresponding variables by computing an average at the NUTS 2 regional classification.

<p>Source: Eurostat retrievable at https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/history</p>
<p>Digital/Technology</p>
<p>Variable: 3.0 and 4.0 technology creation degree</p> <p>Definition: <u>Index (1 is the lowest value and 4 is the highest value) based on the ESPON ‘taxonomy of the 4.0 inventing regions’</u> that classifies the regions as: “low-tech regions, i.e. regions creating neither 3.0 nor 4.0 technologies (code 1); technology falling behind regions, regions leading the creation of 3.0 technologies but not 4.0 technologies (code 2); new islands of innovation, i.e. regions leading the creation of 4.0 technologies with little if not nil experience in 3.0 technologies (code 3); technology leader regions, i.e. regions leading the creation of both 3.0 and 4.0 technologies (code 4)”.¹⁰⁰ As specified in ESPON: “Regions have been classified in terms of their patent specialisation and their patent intensity in the creation of 4.0 technologies in the period 2010-2015 and in terms of their patent specialisation and their patent intensity in the creation of 3.0 technologies in the period 2000-2009. The two classifications have been compared to obtain the taxonomy of 4.0 inventing regions”. As described in the main text for the definition of 3.0 and 4.0 technologies are, respectively “High-tech technologies according to EUROSTAT definition” and “Set of wide-ranging technological fields including artificial intelligence, robotics, internet of things, autonomous vehicles, additive manufacturing, virtual reality, 3D printing, nano-technologies, biotechnology, energy storage with an application such as smart home, smart transport, smart energy grids, intelligent robotics, smart factories”</p> <p>Period available: computed to cover 2000-2015</p> <p>Source: ESPON project “T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation”, code (1961, t_4_5) https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1961/#metadata-download https://archive.espon.eu/transregecon “ESPON / T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation / Final Report – Scientific Annex” retrievable at https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/Final_Report%20Scientific.pdf</p>
<p>Variable: Green patent & tech</p> <p>Definition: ‘Composite index of access to technology’ that, varying between 0.5 and 1.5, is a weighted average of: “i) the accumulated patents in selected environmental technologies per million inhabitants at NUTS 2 level (2005-2010) from OECD Regions and cities database; ii) the share of patents in selected environmental technologies over the total number of patents (2005-2010), from OECD Regions and cities database; iii) the number of green-tech clusters per million inhabitants (2013) generated in the GRECO project relying on data from the Cluster Observatory (http://www.clusterobservatory.eu). Weights have been assigned as follows: Variable 1 accounts for 50%, and variables 2 and 3 account for 25% each”.</p> <p>Period available: computed to cover 2005-2010 and 2013</p> <p>Source: ESPON, code (542, TECH) https://database.espon.eu/indicator/542/#metadata-download</p>
<p>Variable: High risk of job automation</p> <p>Definition: <u>Indexed share of regional jobs at high risk of automation (indexed with respect to ESPON countries' average)</u>¹⁰¹.</p> <p>Period available: 2011</p> <p>Source: ESPON project “T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation”, code (1971, T4_9_b) https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1971/#metadata-download https://archive.espon.eu/transregecon “ESPON / T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation / Final Report – Scientific Annex” retrievable at https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/Final_Report%20Scientific.pdf</p>
<p>Variable: Average risk of job automation</p> <p>Definition: <u>Indexed average risk of job automation across occupations in regional labour markets (indexed with respect to the ESPON countries' average)</u>¹⁰².</p> <p>Period available: 2011</p> <p>Source: ESPON project “T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation”, code (1970, T4_9_a) https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1970/#metadata-download https://archive.espon.eu/transregecon “ESPON / T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation / Final Report – Scientific Annex” retrievable at https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/Final_Report%20Scientific.pdf</p>

¹⁰⁰ For more details see also Capello and Lenzi (2021a, 2021b).

¹⁰¹ The so-called “ESPON” countries include the 28 EU Member States plus Switzerland, Lichtenstein, Norway and Iceland.

¹⁰² See previous note.

<p>Variable: Robot adoption</p> <p>Definition: Yearly average of the number of robots per employee (indexed with respect to ESPON countries' average)¹⁰³ in the specific manufacturing sectors: i) technology manufacturing sectors (“Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products (C26) Manufacture of machinery and equipment (C28)”); ii) carrier manufacturing sectors (“group of sectors comprising the most visible and active users of digital solutions and automation”); iii) induced manufacturing sector (“group of sectors taking limited advantages from the technological revolution because of their specific production structure”)</p> <p>Period available: computed to cover 2009 – 2016</p> <p>Source: ESPON project “T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation”, codes (T_11_a, T_11_b, T_11_c) https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1974/ https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1975/ https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1976/ https://archive.espon.eu/transregecon “ESPON / T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation / Final Report – Scientific Annex” retrievable at https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/Final_Report%20Scientific.pdf</p>
<p>Variable: Displacement/creation of jobs for high-skill and displacement/creation of jobs for low-skilled</p> <p>Definition: Ordinal index (1 to 6 for high-skilled and 1 to 5 for low-skilled) based on the ESPON classification of regions depending on the degree of technological adoption and the adoption impact on high-skill (low-skill) employment share.</p> <p>More specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the indicator for high skilled includes six categories: i) “High displacement”, ii) “High adoption and moderate displacement”, iii) “Low adoption, low displacement”, iv) “Low adoption, low creation”, v) “High adoption, moderate creation”, and vi) “High adoption, high creation”. From the original ESPON indicator, a unique categorical variable ranging from 1 to 6 and, alternatively, six dummy variables were created. - the indicator for low skilled includes five categories i) “High displacement”, ii) “High adoption and moderate displacement”, iii) “Low adoption, moderate displacement”, iv) “Low adoption, low creation”, and v) “High adoption, high creation”. From the original ESPON indicator, a unique categorical variable ranging from 1 to 5 and, alternatively, five dummy variables were created. <p>Period available: computed to cover 2013 – 2018</p> <p>Source: ESPON project “T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation”, codes (1998 T_4_30, 1999 T_4_31) https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1998/ , https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1999/ https://archive.espon.eu/transregecon “ESPON / T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation / Final Report – Scientific Annex” retrievable at https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/Final_Report%20Scientific.pdf</p>
<p>Variable: Regional job creation and job displacement by skill level¹⁰⁴</p> <p>Definition: Dummy variable based on ESPON Classification of regions by the intensity of displacement and creation of both low- and high-skill jobs and includes 8 categories: i) “High displacement of manual and cognitive jobs”, ii) “Displacement of cognitive jobs”, iii) “Displacement of manual jobs”, iv) “Moderate displacement of manual and cognitive jobs”, v) “Moderate polarization”, vi) “Deskilling¹⁰⁵ (gig jobs¹⁰⁶</p>

¹⁰³ See previous note.

¹⁰⁴ <https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1997/> Specifies that:

“For what concerns manufacturing-related transformation patterns, regions show different processes in the labour market, namely: displacement of manual routine jobs, when the displacement of low-skill jobs is above the group average and that of the high-skill job is below the group average; displacement of cognitive non-routine jobs (deskilling), when the displacement of high-skill jobs is above the average and that of the low-skill job is below the group average; displacement of manual and cognitive (routine and non-routine) jobs, when the displacement of low-skill jobs is above the group average and that of the high-skill job is above the group average; moderate displacement, when the displacement of low- and high-skill jobs is below the group average. For what concerns service-related transformation patterns, classifies regions as follows: deskilling (gig-job creation), when the creation of low-skill jobs is above the group average and that of the high-skill job is below the group average; upskilling (élite-job creation), when the creation of high-skill jobs is above the average but that of the low-skill job is below the group average; high polarisation, when the creation of low- and high-skill jobs is above the group average; moderate polarisation, when the creation of low- and high-skill jobs is below the group average.”

¹⁰⁵ Deskilling is the “process of reduction of jobs’ skill content”.

creation”); vii “Upskilling (élite job¹⁰⁷ creation)”, and viii “High polarization¹⁰⁸” From the original ESPON indicator, it has been created some dummy variables for the most relevant categories.

Period available: computed to cover 2013 – 2018

Source: ESPON project “T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation”, codes (1997 T_4_29,)

<https://database.espon.eu/indicator/1997/>

<https://archive.espon.eu/transregecon>

“ESPON / T4 – Territorial trends in technological transformation / Final Report – Scientific Annex” retrievable at https://archive.espon.eu/sites/default/files/attachments/Final_Report%20Scientific.pdf

Globalisation

Variable: FDI class

Definition: Ordinal index (1 lowest value, 6 highest value) based on the ESPON “Incoming FDI regional typologies” which identifies five regional typologies through a k-means clustering technique plus an outlier group. The five clusters are constructed based on six dimensions (“connectivity”, “intensity”, “weighted intensity”, “interregional balance”, “external influence” and “send-receive balance”).¹⁰⁹ The indicator takes into account only intra-EU FDI. In brief, the clusters are described as follows: “Cluster A (incoming FDI ESPON-wide hubs) contains the topmost connected, absolute, and influencing FDI receivers, cluster B (incoming FDI national-wide hubs) contains the topmost national and net absolute FDI receivers, cluster C (third-level incoming FDI national-wide hubs) contains the bottommost net and relative FDI receivers, cluster D (second-level incoming FDI influencers) contains the bottommost national FDI receivers, and cluster E (incoming FDI ESPON-wide relative hubs) contains the topmost relatively absolute FDI receivers, and the bottommost connected, absolute, and influencing FDI receivers.” For more details see Adamakou et al. (2024).

Period available: computed to cover 2010 – 2018

Source: ESPON project 'FDI - World in Europe: Global FDI Flows towards Europe', code (2489, FDI_03)

<https://database.espon.eu/indicator/2489/>

<https://archive.espon.eu/fdi>

<https://www.espon.eu/projects/world-europe-global-fdi-flows-towards-europe>

Variable: FDI Potential Index

Definition: Index of FDI attractiveness computed with a regional approach as computed in Maza al Villaverde (2015) the index employs a sound way of selecting the variables involved in its construction, for which a factor analysis is performed. Accordingly, six factors¹¹⁰ (“economic potential”, “market size”, “labour situation”,

¹⁰⁶ Are “Short-term (low value-added) work” and Gig-economy is: “A free market system where organisations and independent (freelance) workers engage in short-term (low value-added) work arrangements”.

¹⁰⁷ Élite jobs: “High-skill, high-wage jobs”.

¹⁰⁸ Polarisation of labour markets: “Increase in the number of low-skill (low-wage) and high-skill (high-wage) jobs at the detriment of mid-skill jobs”.

¹⁰⁹ “CONNECTIVITY measures the number of nodes each region is connected to. Regardless of the intensity of the connections, this indicator differentiates between regions which are focused on a small set of partners, and those which have many dispersed connections across European space. Intensity is a measure of the strength of each region as a destination or as an origin of FDI (thousands of euros). Although it is biased in favor of larger regions (e.g., in terms of GDP), the indicator is important to assess the level of dominance of these regions, establish the scale of regional hierarchies and build rank-size tables. WEIGHTED INTENSITY looks at intensity in relation to the total FDI flows. This corrects the bias of the previous indicator and allows for the assessment and comparison of the performance of regions according to their own capacity. INTERREGIONAL BALANCE assesses the level of dominance vs. decentralization of a region within its country. Some regions capture a vast majority of the flows in their country (i.e., centralized national pattern), whereas other regions do not. EXTERNAL INFLUENCE measures the importance of a destination or an origin region from the perspective of the corresponding top origin region or the corresponding top destination region, respectively. Even though a region may be dependent on a single destination or on a single origin, this may not hold from the perspective of the corresponding origin or destination region, respectively. If this is the case, the influence of a region on its corresponding top destination or top origin region is, rather, limited. SEND-RECEIVE BALANCE tests whether regions are specialized senders or receivers, or whether they have balanced incoming and outgoing flows.” Adamakou et al. (2024) page 22.

¹¹⁰ As explained in Maze and Villaverde (2028, p.11) The first factor called “economic potential” and including labour productivity, per capita GDP, wages, air and multimodal accessibility, and market potential—explains more than 35.6% of the entire variance. The second factor, “market size”, comprises GDP, population and investment variables. The third factor, “labour situation”, includes the employment, activity, inverse of unemployment and inverse of long-term unemployment rates. The fourth factor, “technological progress”, contains four indicators: R&D investment, R&D personnel, high technology sector and human capital. The fifth factor, “labour regulation”, encompasses labour market regulation and the inverse of

“technological progress”, “labour regulation” and “competitiveness”). Two versions of the index “Spatial-Relative FDI Potential Index” and “Spatial-Relative FDI Performance Index” is computed. **Period available:** computed to cover 2000-2006

Source: Maza, A. and Villaverde, J. (2015). ‘The determinants of inward foreign direct investment: Evidence from the European regions’, *International Business Review*, 24(2), pp. 209-223.

Variable: Extra-EU FDI number and Extra-EU FDI volume

Definition: total deal value and the total number of incoming FDI projects originating from extra EU.

- FDI projects (total deal value) - from extra-EU is the “deal value originating from outside Europe, both Greenfield projects and M&A deals (around half of the M&A deals did not have a reported deal value – the total deal value is reported for the GF and M&A projects that had a reported deal value). A Greenfield project is a cross-border investment in a new physical project or expansion of an existing investment which creates new jobs and capital investment. M&A deals include merger, acquisition, initial public offering (IPO), private equity and venture capital deals. Deal values have been corrected for inflation and are reported in 2015 value”.
- FDI projects (total number) - from extra-EU is the “number of projects originating from outside Europe, both Greenfield projects and M&A deals. A Greenfield project is a cross-border investment in a new physical project or expansion of an existing investment which creates new jobs and capital investment. M&A deals include merger, acquisition, initial public offering (IPO), private equity and venture capital deals”.

Period available: computed to cover 2003-2015

Source: ESPON project 'FDI - World in Europe: Global FDI Flows towards Europe', codes (eEU-vfdi, eEU-pfdi) <https://database.espon.eu/indicator/395/>, <https://database.espon.eu/indicator/409/> <https://database.espon.eu/project-data-package/986/> <https://archive.espon.eu/fdi> <https://www.espon.eu/projects/world-europe-global-fdi-flows-towards-europe>

EU regional migration

Variable: Net migration

Definition: crude rate of net migration plus statistical adjustment¹¹¹

Period: available 2001-2023

Source: Eurostat, code (demo_r_gind3)

Variable: Migration regional weighted intensity (MRWI)

Definition: The index of intensity expresses the volume of flow within a given relation of all relations of a given spatial unit in absolute units of phenomenon (in the case of migration - persons). Weighted intensity is a value of the intensity index, related to the population of the given region. It supplements the intensity index by the consideration of the context of the demographic size of the region. A much smaller volume of flows can have a relatively higher importance in the case of a small region.

Period available: computed to cover 2010-2018

Source: ESPON, project 'IriE – Interregional relations in Europe', code (2242, migra_03) <https://database.espon.eu/indicator/2442/#metadata-download> <https://irie.espon.eu/>

Variable: Commuters flow

Definition: “Labour regional interregional balance (inflows)” is the share of commuters into region *i* with respect to total commuters into the country.

Period available: computed to cover 2010-2018

Source: ESPON, project 'IriE – Interregional relations in Europe', code (2458, labou_06) <https://database.espon.eu/indicator/2458/#metadata-download> <https://irie.espon.eu/>

labour law rigidity and tax wedge. Finally, the sixth factor, “competitiveness”, combines the openness degree (exports plus imports over GDP) and the manufacturing share”.

¹¹¹ “Net migration is the difference between the number of immigrants and the number of emigrants. In the context of the annual demographic balance, however, Eurostat produces net migration figures by taking the difference between total population change and natural change; this concept is referred to as net migration plus statistical adjustment. The statistics on 'net migration plus statistical adjustment' are therefore affected by all the statistical inaccuracies in the two components of this equation, especially population change. Crude rate of net migration plus statistical adjustment is the ratio of net migration plus statistical adjustment during the year to the average population in that year. The value is expressed per 1,000 inhabitants.” Eurostat glossary: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Migration>

Table A2.3.3a Club averages of independent variables used in the regression for GDP per capita

	Club 1	Club 2	Club 3
Employment share in manufacturing	6.1	14.9	15.1
Employment share in routine sectors	35.4	24.5	23.9
Employment share in ICT	1.1	1.7	2.8
Employment share in finance	1.0	1.7	3.5
3.0 and 4.0 technology creation degree	1	2	3
Green patent and tech	0.52	0.61	0.77
High risk of job automation	1.3	1.1	1.0
Average risk of job automation	1.1	1.0	1.0
FDI typeclass	1.3	1.6	3.1
FDI performance index	0.1	0.8	1.4
Extra EU FDI number	3.4	60.4	236.7
Extra EU FDI value	72,846	2,860,954	13,000,000
Net migration	-1.4	2.5	5.0
Migration weighted intensity	4.7	3.1	4.7
Incoming commuting flow	0.13	0.09	0.13
Urban/rural/remote index	3.84	2.81	2.19

Source: Authors' calculation

Table A2.3.3b Club averages of independent variables used in the regression for AROP

	Club 1	Club 2	Club 3	Club 4	Club 5
Empl. rate 25-34	69.6	75.5	78.2	79.3	82.7
Education (3-8)	71.1	79.4	83.8	83.3	80.3
High risk of job automation	1.19	1.12	1.02	1.01	1.09
Average risk of job automation	1.04	1.04	1.01	1.00	1.03
Robot adoption (a)	1.50	1.89	1.24	1.24	0.78
Robot adoption (b)	0.91	1.67	1.10	0.91	1.59
Robot adoption (c)	1.42	1.61	1.22	1.46	1.32
Displ./creation HS	3.4	3.1	2.2	2.7	5.3
Displ./creation LS	3.4	3.0	2.4	2.6	5.0
FDI typeclass	1.97	2.30	1.94	2.08	2
Migration weighted intensity	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04
Urban/rural/remote index	2.50	2.64	2.83	2.18	3

Source: Authors' calculation

Table A2.3.3c Club averages of independent variables used in the regression for AROP

	Club 1	Club 2	Club 3	Club 4	Club 5
Empl. rate 25-34	70.2	65.7	74.3	78.0	77.2
Education (3-8)	72.8	70.2	74.3	84.5	86.3
High risk of job automation	1.9	1.5	1.1	1.0	1.3
Average risk of job automation	1.2	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.1
Robot adoption (a)	0.0	0.7	1.4	0.8	0.3
Robot adoption (b)	0.0	0.8	0.9	0.8	1.3
Robot adoption (c)	0.0	1.3	1.4	1.0	0.8
Displ./creation HS	2	4	2.8	2.4	3.6
Displ./creation LS	2	3.6	2.8	2.4	3.4
FDI typeclass	1.8	2.1	2.1	1.6	1.6
Migration weighted intensity	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.02
Urban/rural/remote index	2.7	2.5	2.7	2.9	3.0

Source: Authors' calculation

A3. Additional figures of club convergence

Fig 3.1.2a Overall set of regional transition paths¹¹², GDP per capita in PPS, NUTS 2 level, 2000-2025

Fig 3.1.2b Final clubs and within-club convergence, GDP per capita in PPS, NUTS 2 level, 2000-2025

Fig 3.1.2c Transition Paths of the Convergence Clubs, GDP per capita in PPS, NUTS2 level, 2000-2025

Source: Authors' calculation

¹¹² As the variable under study is normalized by the cross-sectional mean of each year, the convergence approach of Phillips and Sul (2007) is also referred to as relative convergence (Sul 2019).

Table A3a Phillips and Sul clustering algorithm's results for GDP per capita in PPS (2000-2023) – NUTS 2

Club	Members
1 (82)	<u>Austria</u> : AT13, AT21, AT22, AT31, AT32, AT33, AT34; <u>Belgium</u> : BE10, BE21, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31; <u>Bulgaria</u> : BG41; <u>Czechia</u> : CZ01; <u>Germany</u> : DE11, DE12, DE13, DE14, DE21, DE22, DE23, DE24, DE25, DE26, DE27, DE30, DE50, DE60, DE71, DE91, DE92, DEA1, DEA2, DEA4, DEB3; <u>Denmark</u> : DK01, DK03, DK04; <u>Estonia</u> : EE00; <u>Spain</u> : ES30; <u>Finland</u> : FI1B; <u>France</u> : FR10; <u>Croatia</u> : HR05; <u>Hungary</u> : HU11; <u>Ireland</u> : IE05, IE06; <u>Italy</u> : ITC2, ITC4, ITH1, ITH2, ITH5; <u>Lithuania</u> : LT01, LT02; <u>Luxembourg</u> : LU00; <u>Malta</u> : MT00; <u>The Netherlands</u> : NL11, NL31, NL32, NL33, NL41, NL42; <u>Poland</u> : PL21, PL22, PL41, PL51, PL63, PL71, PL91, PL92; <u>Romania</u> : RO11, RO12, RO22, RO31, RO32, RO41, RO42; <u>Sweden</u> : SE11, SE23, SE33; <u>Slovenia</u> : SI04; <u>Slovakia</u> : SK01
2 (151)	<u>Austria</u> : AT11, AT12; <u>Belgium</u> : BE22, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35; <u>Bulgaria</u> : BG31, BG32, BG33, BG34, BG42; <u>Cyprus</u> : CY00; <u>Czechia</u> : CZ02, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ07, CZ08; <u>Germany</u> : DE40, DE72, DE73, DE80, DE93, DE94, DEA3, DEA5, DEB1, DEB2, DECO, DED2, DED4, DED5, DEE0, DEF0, DEG0; <u>Denmark</u> : DK02, DK05; <u>Greece</u> : EL30, EL42, EL53, EL64, EL65; <u>Spain</u> : ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES63, ES64, ES70; <u>Finland</u> : FI19, FI1C, FI1D, FI20; <u>France</u> : FRB0, FRC1, FRC2, FRD1, FRD2, FRE1, FRE2, FRF1, FRF2, FRF3, FRG0, FRH0, FRI1, FRI2, FRI3, FRJ1, FRJ2, FRK1, FRK2, FRL0, FRM0, FRY1, FRY2, FRY4, FRY5; <u>Croatia</u> : HR02, HR03, HR06; <u>Hungary</u> : HU12, HU21, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33; <u>Ireland</u> : IE04; <u>Italy</u> : ITC1, ITC3, ITF1, ITF2, ITF3, ITF4, ITF5, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITH3, ITH4, ITI1, ITI2, ITI3, ITI4; <u>Latvia</u> : LV00; <u>The Netherlands</u> : NL12, NL13, NL21, NL22, NL23, NL34; <u>Poland</u> : PL42, PL43, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL72, PL81, PL82, PL84; <u>Portugal</u> : PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, PT20, PT30; <u>Romania</u> : RO21; <u>Sweden</u> : SE12, SE21, SE22, SE31, SE32; <u>Slovenia</u> : SI03, <u>Slovakia</u> : SK02, SK03, SK04
3 (9)	<u>France</u> : FRY3; <u>Greece</u> : EL41, EL43, EL51, EL52, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL63.

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: In parenthesis the number of regions for each club

Table A3b Phillips and Sul clustering algorithm's results for AROP, NUTS2 (2005-2023)

Club	Members
1 (38)	<u>Austria</u> : AT13, AT34; <u>Belgium</u> : BE10; <u>Bulgaria</u> : BG31, BG34, BG42; <u>Germany</u> : DE50; <u>Estonia</u> : EE00; <u>Greece</u> : EL41, EL63; <u>Spain</u> : ES12, ES43, ES52, ES61, ES63, ES64, ES70; <u>Italy</u> : ITF1, ITF3, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITI4; <u>Luxembourg</u> : LU00; <u>Netherlands</u> : NL11, NL13, NL22, NL33, NL34, NL42; <u>Romania</u> : RO12, RO21, RO22, RO41; <u>Sweden</u> : SE22, SE31, SE32; <u>Slovakia</u> : SK04.
2 (91)	<u>Austria</u> : AT12, AT22, AT33; <u>Bulgaria</u> : BG32, BG33, BG41; <u>Germany</u> : DE12, DE13, DE22, DE25, DE30, DE40, DE60, DE71, DE72, DE73, DE80, DE91, DE92, DE93, DE94, DEA1, DEA2, DEA3, DEA4, DEA5, DEB1, DECO, DED4, DED5, DEE0, DEF0, DEG0; <u>Denmark</u> : DK01; <u>Greece</u> : EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL61, EL62, EL64, EL65; <u>Spain</u> : ES11, ES13, ES22, ES24, ES30, ES42, ES51, ES62; <u>Finland</u> : FI19; <u>France</u> : FRE1, FRE2, FRF2, FRI2, FRJ1, FRL0, FRM0; <u>Croatia</u> : HR03; <u>Hungary</u> : HU23, HU32; <u>Ireland</u> : IE04; <u>Italy</u> : ITC1, ITC3, ITC4, ITF2, ITF4, ITF5, ITI1; <u>Lithuania</u> : LT01, LT02; <u>Latvia</u> : LV00; <u>Malta</u> : MT00; <u>Netherlands</u> : NL12, NL21, NL23, NL32, NL41; <u>Poland</u> : PL61, PL62, PL81, PL82, PL84, PL92; <u>Romania</u> : RO31, RO42; <u>Sweden</u> : SE11, SE12, SE21, SE23; <u>Slovakia</u> : SK03.
3 (72)	<u>Austria</u> : AT21, AT31, AT32; <u>Cyprus</u> : CY00; <u>Czechia</u> : CZ01, CZ03, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ07, CZ08; <u>Germany</u> : DE11, DE14, DE21, DE23, DE24, DE26, DE27, DEB2, DEB3, DED2; <u>Denmark</u> : DK02, DK03, DK04, DK05; <u>Greece</u> : EL30, EL42, EL43; <u>Spain</u> : ES21, ES23, ES41, ES53; <u>Finland</u> : FI1C, FI1D; <u>France</u> : FR10, FRB0, FRC1, FRC2, FRD1, FRD2, FRF1, FRF3, FRG0, FRH0, FRI1, FRI3, FRJ2, FRK1, FRK2; <u>Hungary</u> : HU11, HU12, HU22, HU31, HU33; <u>Ireland</u> : IE05; <u>Italy</u> : ITH3, ITH4, ITI3; <u>Netherlands</u> : NL31; <u>Poland</u> : PL21, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL63, PL71, PL72; <u>Romania</u> : RO11; <u>Sweden</u> : SE33; <u>Slovenia</u> : SI03, SI04.
4 (12)	<u>Austria</u> : AT11; <u>Czechia</u> : CZ02; <u>Finland</u> : FI1B; <u>Hungary</u> : HU21; <u>Ireland</u> : IE06; <u>Italy</u> : ITH1, ITH2, ITH5, ITI2, PL22, PL91, SK02.
5 (3)	FI20, ITC2, SK01
	RO32 = non convergent group

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: are excluded from the sample Belgium: BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35; France: FRY1, FRY2, FRY3, FRY4, FRY5; Croatia: HR02, HR05, HR06; Portugal: PT11, PT15, PT16, PT17, PT18, PT20, PT30.

Table A3c Phillips and Sul clustering algorithm's results for S80/S20 (2008-2023) – NUTS 2

Club	Members
1 (4)	<u>Bulgaria</u> : BG41; <u>Spain</u> : ES63; <u>Romania</u> : RO21, RO41.
2 (19)	<u>Bulgaria</u> : BG31, BG33, BG34, BG42; <u>Spain</u> : EL42, ES12, ES30, ES61, ES70; <u>France</u> : FR10; <u>Italy</u> : ITF3, ITF6, ITG1, ITG2, ITI4; <u>Lithuania</u> : LT01; <u>Latvia</u> : LV00; <u>Romania</u> : RO12, RO22.
3 (78)	<u>Austria</u> : AT12, AT13, AT22, AT34; <u>Belgium</u> : BE10; <u>Bulgaria</u> : BG32; <u>Cyprus</u> : CY00; <u>Czechia</u> : CZ01; <u>Denmark</u> : DK01, DK05; <u>Estonia</u> : EE00; <u>Greece</u> : EL30, EL41, EL51, EL52, EL53, EL54, EL62, EL63, EL64, EL65; <u>Spain</u> : ES11, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES62; <u>Finland</u> : FI1B; <u>France</u> : FRC2, FRD1, FRF1, FRI2, FRJ1, FRL0; <u>Hungary</u> : HU11, HU12, HU22, HU23, HU31, HU32, HU33; <u>Italy</u> : ITC1, ITC2, ITC3, ITC4, ITF1, ITF2, ITF4, ITF5, ITH1, ITH2, ITH3, ITH4, ITH5, ITI1, ITI2; <u>Lithuania</u> : LT02; <u>Luxembourg</u> : LU00; <u>Malta</u> : MT00; <u>Poland</u> : PL21; <u>Romania</u> : RO11, RO31, RO42; <u>Sweden</u> : SE11, SE12, SE21, SE22, SE23, SE31, SE32, SE33.
4 (59)	<u>Austria</u> : AT11, AT21, AT31, AT32, AT33; <u>Belgium</u> : BE21, BE22, BE23, BE24, BE25, BE31, BE32, BE33, BE34, BE35; <u>Czechia</u> : CZ02, CZ04, CZ05, CZ06, CZ07, CZ08; <u>Denmark</u> : DK02, DK03, DK04; <u>Greece</u> : EL43, EL61; <u>Finland</u> : FI19, FI1C, FI1D, FI20; <u>France</u> : FRB0, FRC1, FRE1, FRE2, FRF2, FRF3, FRG0, FRH0, FRI1, FRI3, FRJ2, FRK1, FRK2; <u>Hungary</u> : HU21; <u>Italy</u> : ITI3; <u>Poland</u> : PL22, PL41, PL42, PL43, PL51, PL52, PL61, PL62, PL63; <u>Romania</u> : RO32; <u>Slovenia</u> : SI03, SI04; <u>Slovakia</u> : SK03, SK04.
5 (5)	<u>Czechia</u> : CZ03; <u>France</u> : FRD2, FRM0; <u>Slovakia</u> : SK01, SK02.
	ES74 = non convergent group

Source: Authors' calculation.

Note: are excluded from the sample Germany (37 regions), Croatia (5 regions), Ireland (5 regions), the Netherlands (12 regions), and Portugal (7 regions).

A4. Additional ordered logit regression tables

Table 4.2b Ordered logit regression results (logit coefficients), clubs in AROP and S80/S20, economic, digital/technological, globalization, migration and geographical/locational predictors

	Model 1 Logit coeff. AROP	Model 2 Logit coeff. S80/S20	Model 3 Logit coeff. AROP	Model 4 Logit coeff. S80/S20	Model 5 Logit coeff. AROP	Model 6 Logit coeff. S80/S20
Empl. rate 25-34	0.139*** (0.0323)	0.0998*** (0.0316)	0.132*** (0.0315)	0.0942*** (0.0296)	0.126*** (0.0316)	0.0864*** (0.0301)
Education (3-8)	0.0448*** (0.0172)	0.0823*** (0.0229)	0.0418** (0.0171)	0.0733*** (0.0209)	0.0375** (0.0170)	0.0536** (0.0221)
H-R of job automat.	-1.549*** (0.413)	-3.073*** (0.561)	-0.674** (0.343)	-1.348*** (0.407)	-0.869** (0.391)	-2.402*** (0.539)
Robot adoption (a)	-0.615*** (0.149)	-0.964*** (0.196)				
Robot adoption (b)			-0.180 (0.154)	-0.213 (0.358)		
Robot adoption (c)					-0.305^ (0.209)	-1.025*** (0.321)
H creation HS	1.576*** (0.597)	-0.154 (0.745)	1.822*** (0.656)	0.221 (0.688)	1.625*** (0.599)	-0.0574 (0.711)
H creation LS	-1.938*** (0.555)	-0.226 (0.647)	-2.076*** (0.578)	-0.104 (0.596)	-1.878*** (0.548)	0.237 (0.624)
FDI type class	-0.0647 (0.122)	-0.729*** (0.185)	-0.0688 (0.120)	-0.618*** (0.170)	-0.0628 (0.120)	-0.648*** (0.174)
Migration (RWI)	-10.98 (8.955)	0.221 (11.27)	-24.98*** (8.531)	-13.73 (10.20)	-24.98*** (8.134)	-7.330 (10.39)
Remoteness	-0.717 (0.788)	-1.345 (0.935)	-0.596 (0.821)	-1.496* (0.894)	-0.489 (0.797)	-1.688* (0.898)
Observations	183	144	183	144	183	144
Pseudo R2	0.188	0.348	0.150	0.248	0.152	0.284

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. For the regressions in the case of AROP, Club 5 (with 3 regions) has been merged with Club 4. In the case of S80/S20 Club 1 (with 4 regions) has been merged with Club 2 and Club 5 (with 7 regions) has been merged with Club 4. In the context of the ordinal logistic regression model, it is recommended that the categories should be not less than 5% each. H-R stays for high-risk, Robot adoption (a) is in technology manufacturing sectors, robot adoption (b) is in carrier manufacturing sectors and robot adoption (c) is in induced manufacturing sectors. HS and LS stay for high-skilled and low-skilled, respectively. Remoteness is the urban/rural/remote index

A4.1. Marginal effects tables for GDP

Table A4.1 Model 1 – Model 4 (GDP per capita) – marginal effects on probabilities

	Model 1 Club 1	Model 2 Club 1	Model 3 Club 1	Model 4 Club 1
Empl. share Manufacturing	1.988*** (0.565)	1.725*** (0.645)	1.594** (0.709)	1.119^ (0.750)
Empl. share Routine	-2.485*** (0.901)	-2.535** (1.206)	-2.778* (1.444)	-2.649* (1.434)
Empl. share Finance	18.490*** (5.604)	10.605^ (6.547)	12.362* (7.457)	11.889^ (7.464)
Empl. share ICT	19.628*** (4.925)	11.378** (5.228)	11.718** (5.954)	11.312* (6.034)
FDI type class		0.109*** (0.041)	0.091** (0.041)	0.086** (0.042)
FDI potential			0.073^ (0.048)	0.081^ (0.050)
3.0 4.0 Creation degree		0.110*** (0.035)	0.121*** (0.040)	0.110*** (0.041)
High risk of job automation			0.125 (0.101)	0.201* (0.108)
Green patent & tech				0.642** (0.318)
Migration (RWI)		3.969* (2.069)	4.204* (2.190)	2.130 (2.421)
Remoteness		-0.386* (0.203)	-0.302 (0.228)	-0.364^ (0.234)
Observations	82	71	69	68

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: Marginal effects are computed at the mean of all variables. Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. RWI stays for 'relative weighted index'. Remoteness is the urban/rural/remote index. Club 1 is the one with the highest GDP per capita. Clubs 2 and 3 have been merged for the logit regressions in Table 4.1

A4.2. Marginal effects tables for AROP and S80/S20

Table A4.2a Model 1 (AROP) – marginal effects on probabilities

	Club 1	Club 2	Club 3	Club 4
Empl. rate 25-34	-0.013*** (0.004)	-0.015*** (0.005)	0.024*** (0.006)	0.004*** (0.001)
Education (3-8)	-0.005** (0.002)	-0.005** (0.002)	0.009** (0.004)	0.001** (0.001)
H-R of job autom.	0.169*** (0.048)	0.195*** (0.068)	-0.316*** (0.088)	-0.048*** (0.018)
Robot adoption (a)	0.065*** (0.017)	0.075*** (0.025)	-0.121*** (0.031)	-0.018*** (0.007)
Displ./creation HS	-0.040* (0.024)	-0.046^ (0.028)	0.075* (0.044)	0.011^ (0.007)
Displ./creation LS	0.064** (0.030)	0.074** (0.036)	-0.120** (0.053)	-0.018** (0.009)
FDI type class	0.012 (0.013)	0.013 (0.015)	-0.022 (0.024)	-0.003 (0.004)
Migration (RWI)	0.968 (0.951)	1.113 (1.101)	-1.805 (1.759)	-0.276 (0.276)
Remoteness	0.086 (0.083)	0.099 (0.097)	-0.160 (0.155)	-0.024 (0.024)
Observations	34	76	61	12

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: Marginal effects are computed at the mean of all variables. Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. H-R stays for high-risk, Robot adoption (a) is in technology manufacturing sectors. HS and LS stay for high-skilled and low-skilled, respectively. RWI stays for 'relative weighted index'. Remoteness is the urban/rural/remote index. Club 1 is the one with the highest AROP, Club 4 is the one with the lowest AROP.

Table A4.2a Model 3 (AROP) – marginal effects on probabilities

	Club 1	Club 2	Club 3	Club 4
Empl. rate 25-34	-0.013*** (0.004)	-0.012*** (0.004)	0.021*** (0.006)	0.004*** (0.002)
Education (3-8)	-0.005** (0.002)	-0.004** (0.002)	0.008** (0.003)	0.002** (0.001)
H-R of job autom.	0.073* (0.041)	0.069^ (0.043)	-0.118* (0.067)	-0.024^ (0.014)
Robot adoption (b)	0.005 (0.017)	0.005 (0.016)	-0.008 (0.027)	-0.002 (0.005)
Displ./creation HS	-0.039 (0.027)	-0.036 (0.026)	0.063 (0.044)	0.013 (0.009)
Displ./creation LS	0.065** (0.033)	0.061* (0.033)	-0.105** (0.052)	-0.021* (0.011)
FDI type class	0.014 (0.014)	0.013 (0.014)	-0.022 (0.023)	-0.004 (0.005)
Migration (RWI)	3.152*** (1.058)	2.966** (1.155)	-5.099*** (1.662)	-1.019** (0.404)
Remoteness	0.058 (0.096)	0.055 (0.091)	-0.094 (0.155)	-0.019 (0.031)
Observations	34	76	61	12

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: Marginal effects are computed at the mean of all variables. Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. H-R stays for high-risk, Robot adoption (b) is in carrier manufacturing sectors and robot adoption (c). HS and LS stay for high-skilled and low-skilled, respectively. RWI stays for 'relative weighted index'. Remoteness is the urban/rural/remote index. Club 1 is the one with the highest AROP, Club 4 is the one with the lowest AROP.

Table A4.2a Model 5 (AROP) – marginal effects on probabilities

	Club 1	Club 2	Club 3	Club 4
Empl. rate 25-34	-0.012*** (0.004)	-0.012*** (0.004)	0.020*** (0.006)	0.004** (0.002)
Education (3-8)	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.004** (0.002)	0.007** (0.003)	0.001** (0.001)
H-R of job autom.	0.103** (0.047)	0.099* (0.051)	-0.169** (0.078)	-0.033** (0.017)
Robot adoption (c)	0.034 (0.024)	0.033 (0.025)	-0.056 (0.040)	-0.011 (0.008)
Displ./creation HS	-0.042^ (0.027)	-0.041^ (0.026)	0.070^ (0.043)	0.013^ (0.009)
Displ./creation LS	0.066** (0.032)	0.063* (0.033)	-0.108** (0.052)	-0.021* (0.011)
FDI type class	0.012 (0.014)	0.012 (0.014)	-0.021 (0.024)	-0.004 (0.005)
Migration (RWI)	2.709*** (0.997)	2.612** (1.092)	-4.459*** (1.608)	-0.862** (0.367)
Remoteness	0.068 (0.093)	0.065 (0.090)	-0.112 (0.152)	-0.022 (0.030)
Observations	34	76	61	12

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: Marginal effects are computed at the mean of all variables. Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. H-R stays for high-risk, Robot adoption (c) is in induced manufacturing sectors. HS and LS stay for high-skilled and low-skilled, respectively. RWI stays for 'relative weighted index'. Remoteness is the urban/rural/remote index. Club 1 is the one with the highest AROP, Club 4 is the one with the lowest AROP.

Table A4.2a Model 2 (S80/S20) – marginal effects on probabilities

	Club 1	Club 2	Club 3
Empl. rate 25-34	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.019*** (0.006)	0.023*** (0.007)
Education (3-8)	-0.003*** (0.001)	-0.016*** (0.005)	0.020*** (0.005)
H-R of job autom.	0.120*** (0.039)	0.612*** (0.142)	-0.732*** (0.137)
Robot adoption (a)	0.036*** (0.012)	0.185*** (0.046)	-0.221*** (0.046)
Displ./creation HS	-0.011 (0.011)	-0.055 (0.055)	0.065 (0.066)
Displ./creation LS	0.018 (0.013)	0.090 (0.064)	-0.108 (0.075)
FDI type class	0.026*** (0.010)	0.132*** (0.040)	-0.157*** (0.042)
Migration (RWI)	-0.021 (0.424)	-0.109 (2.164)	0.131 (2.588)
Remoteness	0.052 (0.038)	0.268^ (0.184)	-0.320^ (0.215)
Observations	20	64	60

Source: Authors' calculation

Note: Marginal effects are computed at the mean of all variables. Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10, ^ p<0.15. H-R stays for high-risk, Robot adoption (a) is in technology manufacturing sectors. r HS and LS stay for high-skilled and low-skilled, respectively. RWI stays for 'relative weighted index'. Remoteness is the urban/rural/remote index. Club 1 is the one with the highest S80/S20, Club 3 is the one with the lowest S80/S20.

D6.4- Part II

Patterns of divergence and convergence, distribution and institutional capacity

Convergence and divergence and how it links to institutional features.

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Convergence and divergence and how it links to institutional features:

Are regions in Europe converging and diverging?

Hans Chr. Garmann Johnsen, Jon P. Knudsen, Terese Birkeland, Tore Bersvendsen, Eirin Mølland and Roger Normann

UiA

Abstract

This report is UiA's contribution to GI-NI WP 6, task 4: D6.4: Research paper on patterns of divergence and convergence, and on the distribution of institutional capacity around EU. It addresses three research questions: A) How are regions in Europe (at NUTS-2 level) performing in terms of socio/economic variables. B) What is the development pattern when comparing NUTS-2 regions within different varieties of capitalism on some key social/economic indicators. C) What is the development trend when calculating sigma and beta convergence of NUTS-2 regions on key social/economic indicators? These three questions are addressed in three steps.

Thus, this paper provides an empirical analysis of the development of NUTS-2 regions in Europe, focusing on the past 10 to 15 years. Our findings are somewhat mixed and vary depending on the indicators studied. In some cases, there has been relatively parallel development over the last decade. High-performing regions are not pulling away significantly, even though disparities may be increasing, and low-performing regions are not falling further behind. Moreover, there are indications that regions have generally navigated the recent pandemic crisis more effectively than the 2008 financial crisis. The paper reflects on this broader picture in the context of different social models in Europe. Finally, the paper presents some policy areas relevant for regional development, and we discuss if there are policy options to foster regional cohesion.

Keywords: EU integration, Inequality, Poverty

JEL: R11, O47, C21, I32

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Abbreviations

CoR – Committee of the Regions

DG – Directorate General

DG EAC- Directorate General of Education, Youth, Sport, and Culture

DG EMPL- Directorate General of Employment, Social Affairs, and Inclusion

DG Grow- Directorate General of Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs

DG HOME- Directorate General of Migration and Home Affairs

EASE – Effective Active Support to Employment

ELA – European Labour Authority

EU – European Union

EURES – EUROpean Employment Services

European Commission – Commission

GDP – Gross domestic product

R&D – Research and development

RIS – Regional Innovation Scoreboard

UVDL – Ursula von der Leyen

VoC – Varieties of Capitalism

CEC- Continental European capitalism

EAST - Eastern and Central Europe capitalism

LME - Liberal Market economies

MED- Mediterranean capitalism

SDE- Social-democrat economies

SD – Standard derivation

CV- Coefficient of variation

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1. Introduction: Why regions?

There is widespread recognition that regions play an important role in the economic and political shaping of advanced societies and that they differ significantly from one another in social structure, governance systems and capacity for change. However, there is little consensus on how regions should be classified. Over the years, studies on regions have offered varying classifications, influenced by different disciplinary approaches. Krugman (1991) challenged his fellow neo-classical economists by suggesting that even under general equilibrium conditions, the economics of spillovers could explain why certain industries concentrate in specific regions. However, this argument was overshadowed by the growing body of research in the 1990s, which introduced concepts such as regional innovation systems (Cooke, 1992), learning regions (Florida, 1995), and the idea that institutions within regions matter (Rodríguez-Pose, 2013). More broadly, the 1990s and 2000s saw increasing attention to the endogenous economic growth potential at the regional level (Storper, 1997; Johnsen & Ennals, 2012) as well as the challenges and potentials stemming from different varieties of capitalism (VoC) (Hall & Soskice, 2001; Hancké et al., 2008). This shift may have contributed to the emphasis on regional policy in the Treaty of Lisbon (see: Karmer, 2010), which laid the foundation for reshaping the regional funds, first introduced in 1975, and later the smart specialisation strategy (S3) as part of the European Union's (EU) efforts to promote social and economic development and cohesion.

Initially, the analysis of VoC focused on the division of the Western world into the Anglo-American, liberalist sphere and a more blended, continental European response pattern (Albert, 1993; Hall & Soskice, 2001). Over time, however, this literature expanded to encompass a variety of models and sub-models addressing different regions and time periods (Thelen & Mahoney, 2015), ranging from the NUTS-3 level (Duranton et al., 2009) to broader macro-regional analyses (Todd, 2019). These regional models can generally be categorized under the umbrella of the VoC framework. This cross-disciplinary research tradition draws on insights from economics, political science, sociology, and cultural studies, aiming to provide typologies of institutional configurations across different geographical scales and to explain why societies respond differently to similar external trends and challenges.

Pinto et al. (2019) explored the connection between socio-economic resilience and VoC, acknowledging the influence of national macroeconomic conditions and power on resilience outcomes. They measured regional socio-economic resilience by examining variations in gross domestic product (GDP) and unemployment, while innovation efforts were assessed through research and development (R&D) variations across EU regions. Using cluster analysis, Pinto et al. (2019) identified groups of resilient regions as we will refer below. Their study suggested “a link between the types of clusters created with different levels of resilience and the varieties of capitalism” (Pinto et al., 2019, p. 920). This divided into macro-regions based on the VoC literature, has shown merit in interpreting recent data at both the national and sub-national (NUTS-2) levels.

Building on the link between regional resilience and VoC typology, this paper focuses on how key megatrends in three areas—technology, globalization, and migration—will shape Europe. The relationship between these trends and regions is reciprocal: trends affect regions differently, and the way regions respond to challenges varies. It examines regional convergence and divergence in Europe since the financial crisis and takes a deeper look into 13 selected European regions. In the context of the EU/EEA, the complexity and size of these entities require subdivision for effective analysis. While national data is often used in research, states can be too large or too small to meaningfully capture social change. This paper also examines how social changes over the last decade have implications for EU cohesion policy. A report by the European Commission's high-level group on the future of cohesion policy. *Forging a sustainable future together: Cohesion for a competitive and inclusive Europe* (2024), highlights the growing regional disparities in Europe and calls for more tailored policies. The report emphasizes that, in the future, “Cohesion Policy will have to pay more attention to the nature of challenges and the responses needed in every region” (European Commission 2024, p. 39).

Thus, building on the VoC model, this paper asks: A) How are regions in Europe (at NUTS-2 level) performing in terms of socio/economic variables. B) What is the development pattern when comparing NUTS-2 regions within different varieties of capitalism on some key social/economic indicators. C) What is the development trend when calculating sigma and beta convergence of NUTS-2 regions on key social/economic indicators?

These three questions are addressed in three steps. In the first step, we consider a wide range of indicators and do some case studies of regions in order to capture the overall picture of how they are performing in terms of social/economic indicators. In the second step, we concentrate on fewer indicators but look at the pattern of development of all regions and of regions within the various VoC categories. In the third step we do a sigma and beta convergence analysis of all regions on three indicators.

This report is organised as follows. First, in chapter 2, we review the discussion on regional development in Europe and try to argue why we have chosen the framework of VoC for our discussion. Second, in chapters 3-6, we present our empirical findings. Thirdly and finally, in chapter 7 and 8, we present some policy areas relevant for regional development, reflect on extension of current regional policy and conclude our analysis.

2. The regional dimension

2.1 Are European regions converging or diverging?

The literature on European regional development, specifically on regional convergence and divergence, has evolved over time, addressing various factors influencing regional growth, such as economic development, labour market structure, institutional factors, innovation, and resilience across regions. Initially, the focus was on Western Europe, but with the accession of Eastern European countries to the EU in the early 2000s, attention shifted towards examining the role of EU policies in reducing regional disparities across Europe. Prior to the financial crisis, scholars were primarily focused on European social models and measuring economic growth. In the aftermath, the discussion has increasingly centered on the explanatory power of institutional factors and regional clustering.

Numerous scholars have explored regional convergence and divergence within specific European countries, investigating factors such as regional migration and standards of living (Kosfeld et al., 2006; Kubis & Schneider, 2016; O'Leary, 2001). Additionally, the study of regional convergence and divergence extends beyond individual nations to include the broader context of the European Union (EU). Giannias et al. (1999) examined the convergence of quality of life among EU countries, while Horridge and Rokicki (2018) showed that the EU accession of the Visegrad countries led to regional income convergence. Maynou et al. (2016) explored the impact of structural and cohesion funds on the Eurozone, demonstrating regional convergence driven by positive GDP per capita growth in recipient regions. These studies add to a nuanced understanding of economic dynamics within specific European nations and the EU's role in reducing regional inequalities.

In examining regional convergence, inequality, and spatial factors, Rey and Janikas (2005) emphasized the importance of so-called spatial effects in analysing regional income convergence and inequality. Their study distinguishes between confirmatory and exploratory analyses in economic growth and calls for greater attention to the empirical methods used in econometric analyses of growth patterns. Other scholars have closely examined how labour market structures affect regional divergence. Sapir (2006) argued that Europe must reform its labour markets and social policies to adapt to globalization, criticizing traditional social models as inefficient and advocating for significant economic and social reforms to transition towards an innovation-driven economy. However, Liotti and Canale (2020) offered contrasting findings, showing that increased labour market flexibility correlates with higher levels of in-work poverty. Their empirical analysis of 15 European countries from 2005 to 2016 suggested that greater flexibility may exacerbate workers' economic hardship, particularly during economic crises. This underscores the complexity of labour market institutions and their impact on regional dynamics.

Additionally, Barbosa and Faria (2011) explored institutional differences across European countries to explain variations in innovation intensity at the industry level. Their study found that strict regulations in product and labour markets hinder innovation, while well-developed credit markets promote it. However, questions remain about the effectiveness of strengthening intellectual property rights as a strategy to stimulate innovation. These findings enhanced our understanding of regional divergence and the complex factors influencing innovation dynamics within Europe.

2.2 Endogenous growth in regions

Are there specific cultural or institutional features of regions that can help explain differences in regional development? Rodríguez-Pose (1998) highlighted the relationship between economic growth and local social forces, suggesting that traditional factors determining the location of economic activity have become more mobile due to socio-economic restructuring and structural changes. He further emphasized that no single social mix is uniquely associated with either low or high growth, implying that economic activity can thrive even in areas where growth was previously unlikely during the era of mass production. The study aimed to shed light on the complex connection between social forces and regional growth during the transition from mass production to a more flexible system in Western Europe. A year later, Rodríguez-Pose (1999) demonstrated that factors such as the method of measuring growth and the influence of national growth on regional patterns reveal a complex and varied picture of regional growth linked to socio-economic restructuring. His analysis revisited convergence trends in Western Europe, stressing the importance of national factors in determining growth and identifying key regional growth patterns associated with this restructuring process. The paper used standard deviation at the NUTS-2 level to classify regions and identifies five clusters: Capital regions and main financial centres; Declining industrial regions; Intermediate dynamic regions; Intermediate less dynamic regions; and Peripheral dynamic regions. The paper highlighted the need to consider national effects and measurement methods to understand the emergence of a complex and varied pattern of regional growth.

The significance of institutional quality in shaping regional economic performance ties into broader discussions on the need for coordinated policy responses, especially within the EU framework. Scharpf (2002) explored the constitutional imbalance between policies that promote market efficiencies and those that prioritize social protection and equality in the context of European integration. He advocated for the use of the ‘open method of coordination’ in social policy to enhance national choices through shared goals and comparative evaluations. Scharpf (2002) also proposed solutions for establishing constitutional balance with European economic integration rules while accommodating diverse national welfare regimes, suggesting a mix of differentiated ‘framework directives’ and the open method of coordination as possible approaches. Similarly, Pasimeni and Pasimeni (2016) examined whether institutional factors offer greater explanatory power than economic growth and public finance indicators. Using the Europe 2020 index, which comprises three thematic sub-indicators based on eight indicators representing the strategy’s growth dimensions, they quantitatively assessed country performances. Their analysis reaffirmed the pivotal role of institutions in shaping outcomes and explores the importance of economic growth and sustainability in public finances within the EU’s new macroeconomic framework. Key findings underscored the crucial role of both formal and informal institutions—particularly good governance and social capital—in explaining the varied performances of European countries within the Europe 2020 strategy. Notably, these institutional factors exert a greater influence than GDP-based economic variables, emphasizing their central role in determining countries’ success in implementing the strategy. This is in line with a study undertaken by Duranton et al (2009) showing historical patterns of institutional variety to be the strongest factor explaining present-day socio-economic performance at the NUTS-3 level in Europe

More recently, Rodríguez-Pose (2013), building on the study of Duranton et al (2009), explored the critical role of institutions in regional development, challenging traditional top-down approaches to regional policy. The common belief that economic growth and convergence can be driven by replicating policies on infrastructure, education, and industrialization is questioned, as it is vital to identify which types of institutions are genuinely influential, particularly focusing on property rights and the rule of law. In a subsequent study, Rodríguez-Pose (2020) measured the impact of institutional quality on regional economic development. He found that conventional strategies focused on capital and technology failed to address increasing territorial inequality and its complex consequences. Additionally, the returns on European investments in cohesion were mixed and fell short of expectations. As a result, he emphasized that institutional quality plays a critical role in shaping economic development and should be integrated into development policy frameworks. Furthermore, Rodríguez-Pose and Ketterer (2020) examined the impact of government quality on regional economic performance in the EU, particularly in its lagging regions. Their econometric analysis, covering 249 NUTS-2 regions from 1999 to 2013, provided insights into the nuanced relationship between government quality and regional economic dynamics. The study underscores the importance of institutions in shaping regional development and the need for tailored policy interventions to effectively address regional disparities. The

question can be asked whether going down to NUTS-3 would show even stronger variations or not, as going down in scale usually gives more heterogeneity to the empirical material studied.

2.3 Varieties of regional economics

Scholars have emphasized the intricate interplay of historical, cultural, and socio-economic factors in shaping local development and transformative innovation policies (Duranton et al, 2009), while also addressing regional clustering dynamics. Garofoli (2002) illustrated that successful local development relies on the collaborative generation of specialized knowledge and resources, which are essential for cultivating dynamic competitive advantages crucial for sustainable growth. By examining capacities, network relations, and the interaction between path dependency and best practices, Garofoli (2002) shed light on the nuanced process of fostering successful local development, with a particular focus on the diffusion of firm culture. Building on this foundation, Nahtigal (2013) explored the pressing issue of the widening gap between advanced and less developed regions in Europe, emphasizing its profound implications for the EU's future trajectory. Nahtigal (2013) criticised the shortcomings of the one-size-fits-all approach within EU policies and advocates for decentralized strategies that empower European regions to craft tailored solutions. He highlights the importance of economic, social, legal, and political reconstruction from the ground up, emphasizing the need for grassroots initiatives and close collaboration at the local and regional levels.

Complementing these perspectives, Haus-Reve and Asheim (2023) underscored the pivotal role of clusters in driving transformative innovation policies across Europe. Clusters are crucial in addressing challenges such as environmental sustainability, fostering diversified specialization, and facilitating reshoring strategies to enhance economic resilience. By advocating for the integration of clusters into national policy frameworks, supported by sustained funding and robust management structures, they highlighted the potential of clusters as catalysts for sustainable growth and resilience at both local and regional scales.

Reflecting the widening gap between advanced and less developed regions in Europe, Pinto et al. (2019), as mentioned above, identify a diverse pattern of socio-economic resilience across European regions. The variations in resilience outcomes are closely linked to the effectiveness of regional institutions in navigating the complexities introduced by socio-economic restructuring. They also examined the relationship between these patterns and the identified varieties of capitalism (VoC), acknowledging the influence of national macro-economic conditions and power on different resilience outcomes. Socio-economic resilience at the regional level was measured by variations in gross domestic product (GDP) and unemployment, while innovation efforts were assessed by variations in research and development (R&D) across EU regions in response to the financial crisis. Using cluster analysis, they identified types of resilient regions and suggest that a connection exists between the types of clusters formed, the varying levels of resilience, and the varieties of capitalism.

2.4 Our theoretical approach

Building on the aforementioned literature review, this study adopts the Varieties of Capitalism (VoC) framework as a foundational point of departure. Hall & Soskice (2001, p. 7) identify five key dimensions that determine the type of capitalism present in each society at the national level:

- Industrial relations
- Vocational training and education
- Corporate governance
- Inter-firm relations
- Employer-employee relations

Using these dimensions, the authors identify two distinct groups of economies, mainly within the OECD: Liberal Market Economies (LMEs) and Coordinated Market Economies (CMEs). The aim is to explain observed changes by applying the Pinto et al. (2019) model, supplemented by relevant VoC-related literature, particularly the socio-cultural typologies proposed by Todd (1990, 2019). The rationale for this choice lies in its utility for analysing the relationships between institutional factors, particularly social models, and regional economic performance. While this study does not explicitly engage in a recession-focused analysis, we argue that the

VoC framework offers a robust context for interpreting the findings of our empirical analysis. By utilizing this theoretical lens, we are better equipped to understand how institutional configurations influence economic outcomes across different regions.

3. Measuring the regional dimension

3.1 Methodology

In a growing body of literature comparing economic and institutional structures and performances, states are often grouped based on shared characteristics across one or more variables. Following this tradition, we use the VoC framework as a structural reference. For socio-economic analyses, three levels of regions are relevant, with NUTS-2 and NUTS-3 being the most applicable. NUTS-1 represents large socio-economic regions, while NUTS-2 and NUTS-3 consists of regions where most of the existing regional policies are targeted. Within EU 27 there are 92 regions at NUTS-1, 244 regions at NUTS-2 and 1 165 regions at NUTS-3 level., making NUTS-2 regions the most practical unit of analysis for this paper. Since we, in our analysis, also include non-EU countries, the number of regions will vary, as we will explain below.

EUROSTAT provides data on several factors relevant to this classification of regions, including demographics, education, skills, and labour market conditions. However, it covers to a lesser degree cultural factors or labour market institutions, which are crucial for identifying governance models. Furthermore, related to data, we are faced with the challenge that datasets for all regions over the time-period we consider, and for all the variables we have wanted to consider, are not complete. For some variables we have, in our qualitative analysis, looked at the development pattern, even if data are missing for some years. For others, as we will refer below, the number of regions considered is lowered due to missing data.

3.2 First step

Our research questions have been addressed in three steps. In the first step, we considered a wide range of indicators and did some case studies of regions in order to capture the overall picture of how they are performing in term of social/economic indicators. The 12 indicators we have considered are:

- Gross regional product per inhabitant
- Educational attainment in percentage
- Unemployment, ages 20-64, in percentage
- Employment in high and medium-high technology manufacturing, in percentage
- Employment in high-technology sectors, in percentage
- Knowledge-intensive high-technology services, in percentage
- Gross domestic expenditure on R&D for all sectors, adjusted for purchasing power per inhabitant, based on 2005 prices
- Purchasing power per inhabitant, in Euros
- At-risk-of-poverty rate, in percentage
- Internet access: daily and weekly, in percentage
- Net migration per 1,000 inhabitants
- Total population change per 1,000 inhabitants

Based on this, maps were created, covering the period from 2010/2011 to 2021/22 for all indicators. Below are illustrations of the maps for gross regional product for the years 2008 and 2021.

Figure 1: Gross domestic product at current market prices for 2008.

Figure 2: Gross domestic product at current market prices for 2021.

After having assessed the quality of these data, we ended up focusing on the following four indicators: educational attainment, gross domestic expenditures on R&D, purchasing power per inhabitant, and the unemployment rate for the 20-64 age group. In addition, we have done some case studies of single regions. Starting from a macro perspective, we have tried to explore sub-national regions to understand the processes at work, using a Porterian framework of regional entities striving for excellence and well-being (Porter, 1990). This assumption still guides EU analyses of the Union's socio-economic challenges and its structural policy agenda (Haus-Reve & Asheim, 2023). Thirteen European regions at the NUTS-2 level, from all five VoC clusters identified earlier, were selected for further analysis. For information on regional performance, we used the Regional Innovation Scoreboard.¹ Twelve of the regions are within the EU and participate in EU cohesion policy to varying degrees, while one region is located in Norway. The criteria for selecting these regions were as follows:

- Represent a variety of macro-regions, as listed by Pinto et al. (2019)
- Reflect different levels of developmental progress (Rodríguez-Pose, 1998)
- Have been empirically and theoretically explored within relevant research traditions

The selected regions include Rhône-Alpes (FRK2), Bretagne (FRH0), Stuttgart (DE11), Noord-Holland (NL32), Southern Ireland (IE05), Länsi-Suomi (FI19), Vestlandet (NO), Andalucía (ES61), País Vasco (ES21), Puglia (ITF4), Észak-Magyarország (HU31), Praha (CZ01), and Vidurio ir Vakarų Lietuvos regionas (LT02).

¹ See: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/statistics/performance-indicators/regional-innovation-scoreboard_en

3.3 Second step

Social structures and human behaviour are regulated and guided by institutions, which in turn are shaped and modified by human actions. This reciprocal relationship between institutions, behaviour, and response patterns is incorporated into various models designed to monitor and explain social change and the responses to such changes. Both formal and informal institutional aspects to create typologies are historically and geographically relevant. These typologies serve as explanatory guides for the effects and response patterns we observe. Rather than focusing solely on the institutions themselves, they are treated methodologically as independent variables within explanatory models (such as the VoC model). When interpreting macro- and sub-regional response patterns, institutional configurations become dependent variables but are understood as bundled into specific configurations rather than investigated individually.

In the second step, we concentrate on a few indicators and look at the pattern of development first of all regions in EU together and second of regions within the different VoC's. The variables selected include macro indicators for demographic and socio-economic status, spanning from around 2010 to the most recent available data. These indicators are used to detect patterns of interest at both the macro-regional and NUTS-2 level. Essentially, two strategies are available: either using a quantitative model to test the strength of the variables or interpreting the observed values in light of existing literature and chosen models. This paper follows the latter approach. The typology of European capitalism is divided into the following categories:

- Continental European Capitalism (CEC): Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Switzerland, and the Netherlands
- Liberal Market Economies (LME): United Kingdom² and Ireland
- Social-Democratic Economies (SDE): Denmark, Finland, and Sweden
- Mediterranean Capitalism (MED): Portugal, Greece, Italy, Spain, Malta, and Cyprus
- Eastern and Central European Capitalism (EAST): Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia

Some adjustments have been made for better classification. Even if the Czech Republic often is classified in the CEC group, in the second step it has been moved from the CEC to the EAST group, and Norway has been added to the SDE group. While Denmark is increasingly considered a liberal market economy (Schneider & Paunescu, 2012; Todd, 2019), strong institutional links to other Nordic countries, especially in managing socio-economic responses like migration and labour force integration (Lee et al., 2022), support its retention in the SDE category. As for France, debates continue over whether it belongs in the CEC model, should be grouped with Mediterranean economies, or stands as a unique case (Amable, 2017; Le Bras & Todd, 2015; Peyrefitte, 1977). To avoid complicating matters, we have classified France within the CEC category.

3.4 Third step

In the third step we have performed a convergence/divergence analysis of all regions on three social/economic indicators. Convergence and divergence can be measured in different ways. Eurofond uses the following definitions: "Beta convergence is used to measure whether countries starting from initially low performance levels grow faster than better performing countries. This process is referred to as catching up. Sigma convergence refers to the overall reduction in disparities among countries over time and is measured by the evolution of the statistical measures of dispersion, such as the standard deviation or the coefficient of variation. A decrease in the standard deviation or coefficient of variation over time indicates convergence. Delta convergence is used to analyse countries' distance from the best performing country. Delta convergence is usually measured through the sum of the distances between the Member States and the top performer."³

² It should be important to retain the UK in the model as one of the prerequisites for the various VoC models, as of the current debates on institutional development, is the strong influence of liberalism on the world scene. Even if Ireland (and Denmark) can be used as empirical cases of LME societies, the main European case remains the UK, regardless of its relations with the EU.

³ Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts>

In our analysis, we have mainly use Beta and Sigma convergence, calculating standard derivations within each of the VoC's. This analysis tells us something about cohesion within each VoC. In chapter 6 we define more in detail how we have done the calculation.

4. Finding from step one: Descriptive analysis of regional development according to Varieties of Capitalism

4.1 The selected regions

Below we present findings from the study in step one. The selected regions are grouped according to the VoC types of regions as previously outlined. Below is a table indicating how the regions score on the Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2023 (RIS). The regions are colour coded according to the five groups of countries in VoC.⁴ The rank and change figure denotes: “For every country a table is included that shows the following information for each region and the country as a whole: RII or relative to EU performance in 2023; rank performance in 2023 across all regions; performance sub-group; and performance change calculated as the difference between the performance in 2023 and 2016 both relative to that of the EU in 2016.”⁵

NUTS	Region	RII	Rank	Group	Change
FRK2	Rhône-Alpes	111,4	67	Strong Innovator	-7,0
FRHO	Bretagne	103,3	92	Strong Innovator-	-1,5
DE11	Stuttgart	126,4	33	Innovation leader	2,8
FL32	Noord-Holland	137,1	12	Innovation leader	7,9
IE05	Southern	105,4	86	Strong Innovator	-6,7
FI19	Länsi-Suomi	123,7	43	Strong Innovator +	14,4
NO0A	Vestlandet?	113,4	61	Strong Innovator	15,4
ES61	Andalucia	71,1	172	Moderate innovator-	4,5
ES21	País Vasco	109,8	72	Strong Innovator	11,5
ITF4	Puglia	76,5	163	Moderate Innovator-	19,2
HU31	Észak-Magyarország	58,4	203	Emerging Innovator +	15,2
CZ01	Praha	127,6	30	Innovation Leader -	24,0
LT02	Vidurio ir Vakarų Lietuvos regionas	70,6	174	Moderate Innovator-	14,4

Table 1: Regional Innovation Scoreboard for selected regions.

As previously mentioned, the analysis conducted in this paper is based on data from both EUROSTAT and the Regional Innovation Scoreboard. For the EUROSTAT data, the selected regions are assessed using four indicators: educational attainment, gross domestic expenditures on R&D, purchasing power per inhabitant,

⁴ See: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/statistics/performance-indicators/regional-innovation-scoreboard_en

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c849333f-25db-11ee-a2d3-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>, page 17

and the unemployment rate for the 20-64 age group. For comparison, the EU mean is also provided in the tables. Regarding the Regional Innovation Scoreboard, we utilize regional data from 2023. The selected regions are evaluated in relation to the rest of their respective countries and the broader EU. Generally, these regions display varying scores across the different indicators, highlighting distinct regional strengths and challenges when compared to both their countries and the EU as a whole.

4.2 Continental European capitalism (CEC)

In this analysis we include four regions from the Continental European Capitalist (CEC) category: Rhône-Alpes, Bretagne, Stuttgart, and Noord-Holland. All regions except Bretagne are categorized as more developed, with Bretagne classified as a transition region.

- Educational Attainment: All four regions have shown an upward trend over time, with each region surpassing the European average.
- Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D: Data is missing for three regions; however, Stuttgart's expenditure increased significantly between 2014 and 2017, placing it well above the EU average.
- Purchasing Power per Inhabitant: This indicator mirrors the trend in educational attainment, showing a steady increase over time, with a slight downturn between 2019 and 2020. All regions exceed the EU average.
- Unemployment Rate: Unemployment has continually decreased across all regions, with notable declines, especially between 2013 and 2019.

Below we present the development chart for education attainment that shows that alle the regions we selected score above mean value for Continental European capitalist countries.

Table 2: Educational attainment for CEC regions in percentage.

Rhône-Alpes (FRK2): In this paper, France is grouped under Continental European Capitalist (CEC), although some classify it as a state-led capitalist country transitioning towards liberalization, while others see it as a unique case. Rhône-Alpes has long been viewed as a developed counterpoint to the Paris region in a highly centralized economy. It has also been cited as a European examples of economic shifts similar to the U.S. sunbelt theories (Cabrol & Nlemvo, 2009). Rhône-Alpes performs well compared to both the rest of France and the EU. Nationally, it excels in international scientific co-publications and public-private collaborations. Compared to the EU, Rhône-Alpes is strong in tertiary education, innovation expenditures per person, and collaboration among innovative SMEs.

Bretagne (FRH0): Brittany is often considered a peripheral region in France and is classified as a transition region (Rodríguez-Pose, 1998). Its socio-demographic structure resembles that of the UK (Todd, 1990), suggesting a potential inclination towards liberalism. Additionally, Brittany's horizontal network structures (Narvaiza et al., 2017), relatively low social inequality, and high education scores (Florence et al., 2021) make it an interesting case for further study. Compared to the rest of France, Bretagne excels in sales of innovative products and innovation expenditures per person.

Stuttgart (DE11): Germany is often seen as a representative of coordinated market economies (CME) in the Variety of Capitalism (VoC) literature (Hall & Soskice, 2001). Baden-Württemberg, where Stuttgart is located, is known for its strong industrial base and automotive industry, exemplifying the adaptive capacity of central European coordinated market economies (Strambach, 2002). Stuttgart performs well in several indicators, such as employment in knowledge-intensive sectors, design applications, PCT patent applications, public-private collaborations, and R&D expenditures in the business sector, compared to both Germany and the EU.

Noord-Holland (NL32): This region, part of the Amsterdam Randstad urban structure in the Netherlands, is often seen as a proxy for a liberal market economy in mainland Europe (Todd, 1990). It was significantly affected by the 2008 financial crisis (Engelen & Musterd, 2010) and should now be examined for its recovery capacity beyond circular economy challenges (Savini, 2019). Noord-Holland performs well on some indicators compared to the EU, including lifelong learning, international scientific co-publications, digital skills, and public-private collaborations.

4.3 Liberal Market economies (LME)

Because of Brexit, this analysis includes only one region from the Liberal Market Economy (LME) category: Southern Ireland. Southern Ireland is classified as a more developed region by the EU.

- Educational Attainment: The Southern region is experiencing an upward trend in educational attainment, surpassing the EU average.
- Gross Domestic Expenditure: Data was unavailable until 2019, but since then, there has been a slight increase in gross domestic expenditure, which now exceeds the EU average.
- Purchasing Power per Inhabitant: Purchasing power in the Southern region remains consistently above the EU average, with a substantial increase noted from 2014 onwards.
- Unemployment: Unemployment in the Southern region has been steadily decreasing. By 2016, it was below the EU average and has continued to remain lower in recent years.

Here we only have data for regions in Ireland. We illustrate our case with data on unemployment, showing both the decline in mean value, but also the further decline for the selected region.

Table 3: Unemployment, age group 20-64 for LME region in percentage.

Southern Ireland (IE05): Ireland, as a small English-speaking country within the EU, has leveraged its institutional capacity to drive economic benefits from globalization (O'Connor et al., 2017). Following the UK's exit from the EU, Ireland represents a typical Liberal Market Economy within the Union. Southern Ireland has achieved the status of a more developed region over the years (Van Egeraat & Curren, 2023), though its role in the broader EU context remains a topic of debate (Pegan, 2018). Southern Ireland performs well in sales of innovative products, tertiary education, and digital skills.

4.4 Social-democrat economies (SDE)

This analysis includes two regions from Social-Democrat Economies (SDE): Länsi-Suomi and Vestlandet. Länsi-Suomi is categorized as a transition region within the EU, while Vestlandet, located in Norway, participates in the EEA agreement but is not formally part of the EU.

- Educational Attainment: Both regions show an upward trend in educational attainment over time, consistently surpassing the EU average, similar to the previous VoC types of regions.
- Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D: Both regions exceed the EU average in gross domestic expenditure on R&D. However, there are differences in their development over time. Länsi-Suomi has seen a decline in expenditure over the years, though there has been a slight increase recently. In contrast, Vestlandet has experienced a steady increase in expenditure, particularly between 2014 and 2019.
- Purchasing Power per Inhabitant: Purchasing power in both regions is above the EU average. Länsi-Suomi follows a trend similar to the slightly increasing EU average, while Vestlandet has seen a slight decrease over time.
- Unemployment: Both regions have experienced a decline in unemployment. Länsi-Suomi aligns closely with the EU average, whereas Vestlandet has maintained an unemployment rate below the EU average.

We illustrate the Social-democrat economies with purchasing power. We see that it is above mean value for regions in this VoC, for the Norwegian case it is significantly above mean value.

Table 4: Purchasing power per inhabitant for SDE regions in Euros.

Länsi-Suomi (FI19): This region in Western Finland represents a transition region within the SDE category. It is diverse but includes the innovative centre of Tampere. Finland is known for its two-tier politico-administrative system, which supports innovation through a distinctive negotiating network culture (Sjöblom, 2018). The Tampere region is a key example of these mechanisms (Sotarauta & Suvinen, 2018). Länsi-Suomi performs very well in lifelong learning and digital skills, and shows notable collaboration among innovative SMEs compared to the EU.

Vestlandet (NO): Norway's society is known for its unique approach to modernization, distinct from many other European countries (Fagerberg et al., 2009). Western Norway, in particular, has attracted academic interest for its innovative networking capacities and its specific form of economic growth, termed "creative continuation" (Knudsen, 2023). This approach contrasts with the more traditional modernist model found in Oslo. Vestlandet performs well in international scientific co-publications, public-private collaborations, and innovative SME partnerships compared to the EU.

4.5 Mediterranean capitalism (MED)

This analysis covers three regions from the Mediterranean (MED): Andalucia, País Vasco, and Puglia. Among these, Andalucia and Puglia are classified as less developed regions, while País Vasco is considered a more developed region by the EU.

- Educational Attainment: All MED regions show an increasing trend in educational attainment over time. País Vasco exceeds the EU average, Andalucia matches it, and Puglia lags behind the EU average.
- Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D: R&D expenditure remains relatively stable over time, with a slight increase observed in País Vasco. País Vasco surpasses the EU average, while Andalucia and Puglia fall below it.
- Purchasing Power per Inhabitant: Purchasing power mirrors the EU average trend, with a slight increase over time. País Vasco is above the EU average, whereas Andalucia and Puglia remain below.
- Unemployment Rate: All regions exceed the EU average in unemployment rates. País Vasco is closest to the EU average, while Andalucia has the highest unemployment rates. However, all regions have seen a decrease in unemployment since 2013.

We have illustrated the development of Mediterranean capitalism with unemployment numbers. It clearly shows how all the regions we have studied are struggling with unemployment above the mean level of regions in the Mediterranean region. Andalucia, as mentioned above, stands out as in particularly struggling with high employment, however, the recent trends are encouraging.

Table 5: Unemployment, age group 20-64 for MED regions in percentage.

Andalucia (ES61): Andalucia is often cited as a typical less-developed Spanish region, with performance challenges (Diez-Minguela et al., 2015) and a large shadow economy (González-Fernández & González-Velasco, 2015). Comparing it with País Vasco and Puglia can highlight similarities and differences. Andalucia performs well in digital skills and lifelong learning compared to the EU but could improve in employment in innovative enterprises, knowledge-intensive jobs, design applications, collaboration among innovative SMEs, business process innovation, and product innovation.

País Vasco (ES21): The Basque Country, along with Catalonia, represents a well-performing northern periphery of Spain, standing out in an otherwise struggling Mediterranean region. It has been studied for its unique network-based social and political structures that support its economic performance (Larrea & Estensoro, 2021; Morgan, 2016; Narvaiza et al., 2017). País Vasco performs better than the rest of Spain and the EU in areas such as collaboration among innovative SMEs, innovation expenditures per person, R&D expenditures in the business sector, international scientific co-publications, employment in innovative enterprises, and knowledge-intensive jobs.

Puglia (ITF4): Italy is often used as a case study for regional socio-economic variations (Di Liberto & Sideri, 2015). Puglia is generally considered less developed, though not as frequently studied as other southern Italian regions. Preliminary studies suggest uncertainty about whether the region is on track to overcome its structural challenges or not (D’Adda, Iacobucci & Perrugini, 2019). Puglia performs well in air emissions of fine particulates, non-R&D innovation expenditures, most-cited scientific publications, and public-private collaborations.

4.6 Eastern and Central Europe capitalism (EAST)

This analysis includes three regions from the East (EAST): Észak-Magyarország, Praha, and Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas. Among these, Praha is considered a more developed region, while Észak-Magyarország and Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas are viewed as less developed regions in the EU.

- Educational Attainment: Educational attainment is rising across all EAST regions. Praha and Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas exceed the EU average, while Észak-Magyarország falls below it.
- Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D: Both Észak-Magyarország and Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas show stable development below the EU average. Praha exhibits an overall increase in expenditure over time, though there was a decrease between 2015 and 2016.
- Purchasing Power per Inhabitant: Purchasing power per inhabitant is increasing in all regions, with Praha showing the most significant rise compared to the other regions and the EU average. Praha is above the EU average, while the other two regions remain below it.
- Unemployment: All EAST regions have seen a decrease in unemployment over time. Észak-Magyarország has experienced a more substantial decrease compared to the other regions and the EU average, surpassing the EU average since 2014 with its unemployment rate consistently below it. Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas has an unemployment rate similar to or slightly above the EU average, while Praha's unemployment rate is substantially below the EU average.

For Eastern and Central Europe capitalism (EAST) we have illustrated the development with a chart on purchasing power. It shows that one of the regions we have selected (Praha) is scoring high above the two other regions. Észak-Magyarország and Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos are scoring well below mean value for regions in this group of nations.

Table 6: Purchasing power per inhabitant for EAST regions in Euros.

Észak-Magyarország (HU31): This Hungarian region is a representative of less developed areas among the new EU members, characterized by a communitarian socio-demographic structure typical of much of Eastern Europe (Todd, 2019). This structure often has limited capacity for social change, though recent studies suggest the region may be undergoing a socio-economic transformation (Čajka & Abrhám, 2019). Észak-Magyarország performs well in non-R&D innovation expenditures compared to both the rest of Hungary and the EU. Improvements are needed in tertiary education, international scientific co-publications, most-cited scientific publications, and employment of ICT specialists..

Praha (CZ01): The capital region of the Czech Republic contrasts with the Hungarian case, representing a more developed region among the new EU members (Blažek & Uhlíř, 2010). Although Pinto et al. (2019) classifies the Czech Republic as a Continental European Capitalist (CEC) country, this paper includes it in the EAST category. The case of Praha illustrates the challenges in categorizing regions, as its industrial history and current

dynamism (Špačková et al., 2016) complicate macro-regional classifications. Praha excels in international scientific co-publications and public-private collaborations compared to both the rest of Czechia and the EU.

Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas (LT02): This region, covering Central and Western Lithuania, contrasts with the more centralized Baltic states (Estonia and Latvia), as Lithuania has a more balanced regional structure. Cities like Kaunas and Klaipėda drive the western part of the country, contrasting with the capital region of Vilnius. The vitality of these cities is somewhat obscured in the overall figures for Central and Western Lithuania (Šneiderienė, 2018). Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas performs well in non-R&D innovation expenditures and tertiary education compared to the EU but could improve in PCT patent applications, knowledge-intensive employment, international scientific co-publications, R&D expenditures in the business sector, and ICT specialist employment.

4.7 Some reflections on the descriptive analysis

From the descriptive statistics, we see some general trends across Europe, illustrating overall progress. Educational attainment is rising, along with employment in high and medium-high technology manufacturing, as well as in high-technology and knowledge-intensive sectors. Meanwhile, unemployment rates have notably decreased. Gross domestic expenditure on research and development has remained relatively stable across all sectors over time. The risk of poverty has shown little fluctuation, while purchasing power per inhabitant has followed a steady upward trajectory. Internet access has significantly improved throughout Europe.

Our aim with this exercise was to see if we from a qualitative point of view could identify some patterns related the relation between scores on specific RIS dimensions and the overall performance of the region on socio/economic indicators. The conclusion of our attempt is that we could not find such a relation. Well performing regions differ on where they have their strength and weakness, as do also less well performing regions. We conclude that there is a variety of regional models in the sense that different configuration of resources, in wide sense, seen to be able to produce similar level of output.

At the same time the qualitative analysis support the impression the there are three dimensions structuring the EU territory in terms of regional performance on socio/economic indicators. There is a centre-periphery dimension, there is a west-east dimension, and there is a north-south dimension. Subsequently the likelihood of poor regional performance increases as we move towards the periphery in the southeast part of the EU.

5. Statistical analysis: Are regions converging or diverging?⁶

5.1 Descriptive statistics

In our descriptive statistical analysis, we have concentrated on three variables: Gross Regional Product per capita, defined as Purchasing Power Standard (PPS), education level and unemployment rate. The descriptive statistics below give the key figures for selected years. The purpose of the descriptive statistical analysis is to have a visual overview development in European regions. In the table below we see that both the overall purchasing power and the employment level have increased, while the unemployment level has decreased. We use standard deviation (SD) and change in SD, as a measure of whether there is divergence or convergence. Since mean value changes, we also look at relative change in SD for year to year. For unemployment there is a convergence (decreased standard deviation), for PPS and education, there is overall divergence, as standard deviation has increased. We also see from this table the sharp improvement of the east regions after they joined EU.

Descriptive statistics

		Mean			Median			SD			N			Min			Max		
		2000	2010	2022	2000	2010	2022	2000	2010	2022	2000	2010	2022	2000	2010	2022	2000	2010	2022
All	PPS	17253.5	23769.6	33399.6	17600	22700	31000	7792.3	9507.6	13379.7	232	250	243	3400	6200	10500	45800	68400	101200
	EDU	18.1	24.4	33.6	17.9	23.9	32.9	8.1	8.5	10.4	214	237	248	3.6	9.0	13.7	43.5	49.5	62.1
	UNEM	9.3	9.6	6.3	7.5	8.4	4.9	5.8	5.2	4.2	209	240	242	1.9	2.6	1.2	27.3	32.0	28.4
CEC	PPS	20712.6	27410.4	37607.6	20000	25950	34900	6766.0	9134.3	12237.9	95	106	106	3400	6300	10600	45800	68400	90900
	EDU	20.5	26.2	35.1	19.7	26.0	33.9	6.5	7.2	8.6	96	101	105	7.4	9.0	15.6	39.1	49.5	60.7
	UNEM	7.4	7.7	4.8	6.6	6.9	3.7	4.4	4.2	3.1	96	105	102	2.1	3.0	1.2	22.8	28.9	18.6
SDE	PPS	22861.1	30604.2	40816.7	21550	29050	37550	4594.3	5953.3	9236.3	18	24	18	17000	22200	30000	34900	44400	67800
	EDU	28.4	33.5	43.2	28.4	32.7	42.8	5.6	6.0	6.4	18	26	25	20.0	26.3	32.9	43.5	47.9	57.5
	UNEM	5.1	7.0	5.5	4.4	7.7	5.1	2.6	2.5	2.0	17	25	23	1.9	2.6	2.2	11.5	10.3	9.5
MED	PPS	18288.7	22866.1	29072.6	16550	20950	27750	5349.2	5977.1	8574.4	62	62	62	11400	15000	14500	32300	39000	56900
	EDU	14.2	20.6	29.4	12.4	17.6	27.5	7.0	8.4	10.2	60	62	62	3.6	9.9	15.2	32.0	43.7	56.4
	UNEM	11.3	12.6	10.5	10.8	12.6	9.9	6.5	5.9	5.0	56	62	62	1.9	43.7	2.3	27.3	28.6	28.4
EAST	PPS	7805.6	14487.3	25303.7	7050	12900	23100	3904.5	7558.8	11112.0	54	55	54	3400	6200	10500	21300	47200	62900
	EDU	13.1	19.8	30.0	10.8	19.3	28.2	7.3	6.3	11.0	38	46	53	6.5	9.9	13.7	42.4	35.5	62.1
	UNEM	12.9	11.1	4.8	13.6	10.3	4.1	5.9	4.7	4.8	38	46	52	4.4	4.7	1.7	24.6	32.0	11.8

Table 7: Descriptive statistics

In the following we are interested in plotting all regions over the whole time-period. For this purpose, we have used two types of visual presentations, as shown below.

5.2 Plotting overall score and mean values for regions

Below, we have plotted all regions using two different visual plots.

⁶ An earlier version of this analysis was presented as Paper for the WeLaR conference:

The Effects of Digitalisation, Globalisation, Climate Change and Demographic Shifts on Labour Markets and Welfare States in the European Union 23 May, 2024 | Leuven, Belgium.

GDP – Purchasing power standard per inhabitant (1)

Figure 3: Plotting PPS

Both the visual presentations above use the same data. The plot to the right (the violin plot) shows mean value for all EU regions and standard deviation. For PPS we see that mean value has increased, and so has standard deviation (SD). The plots indicate that the increased SD is due to more regions being in the upward end of the scale.

Below we have compared the violin plots for the EAST VoC group and for the SED VoC group. We see that the mean value is improving in both VoC groups. We also see an increased spreading for regions within each VoC. This corresponds with comments in the cohesion report (European Commission 2024, p. 39).

GDP – Purchasing power standard per inhabitant (2)

Figure 4: Comparing PPS for EAST and SDE

The figure above show that SDE over the whole time-period is performing better than EAST. However, Some EAST regions are performing really well, so it looks as if SD has been increasing in EAST relative to SDE.

Below we have plotted all regions on education attainment using two different visual plots. We see an overall increase in mean value on education. The spreading of the fields has increased, but there is significant improvement, in terms of higher education level, in regions with initially low tertiary education attainment.

Tertiary educational attainment, age group 25 -64 (1)

9

Figure 5: Tertiary education attainment

Below we have compared the Violin plots for the CEC VoC group and for the MED VoC group. We see that the mean value is improving in both VoC groups. Again, we also see an increased spreading of regions within each VoC.

Tertiary educational attainment, age group 25 -64 (1)

10

Figure 6; Tertiary education attainment comparing CEC and MED regions

Below we have plotted all regions on unemployment using two different visual plots. We see an overall decrease in mean value on unemployment.

Unemployment rates in percent, age group 15 -47 (1)

11

Figure 7: Unemployment

Below we have compared the Violin plots for the SDE VoC group and for the MED VoC group. We see that the mean value has recently been improving in both VoC groups. We also see a decreased spreading for regions within each VoC. The MED chart shows how severe unemployment was for certain regions after the financial crisis in 2008.

Unemployment rates in percent, age group 15 -47 (2)

12

Figure 8: Unemployment SDE and MED compared

5.3 Findings from descriptive statistics

Some overall findings from these descriptive statistics are:

- All in all, we observe an increased purchasing power, increased education level and fewer are unemployed. However, still large differences.
- Unemployment converges towards a lower level, especially driven by the EAST region. This also holds when looking at relative deviation (SD). MED has had large fluctuations during the period but is now on a lower level.
- Tertiary educational attainment has the opposite trend, where regions diverge, also when studying relative standard deviation (SD). However, tertiary educational attainment is overall improved. The trend is mostly driven by MED and EAST, but still signs of regions lagging.
- Purchasing power standard has overall increased. However, divergence has increased and still there are large differences. Trends suggest that there is increased difference between VoC classification.

One might reflect on what kind of spread-effects we are seeing: trickle down versus polarization. For instance, for education, we see the double tendency for an upward mean entailing a more distinct spread pattern. However, our analysis does not allow us to analyse this more in depth.

6. Statistical analysis of three factors.

6.1 Data and variables

In this analysis we include non-EU countries. This imply that we get a mor complete representation of LME countries (United Kingdom and Ireland.) All data is downloaded from the Annual Regional Database of the European Commission (ARDECO). NUTS 2 level, version 2021, is used throughout this paper. ARDECO relies on several data sources, however primarily from Eurostat and national or regional statistical offices. In addition, short-term projection based on the annual macro-economic database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs, is provided.

The following three variables is downloaded and included in this study (ARDECO code in parentheses): GDP per capita at current prices expressed in purchasing power standard (SUVGDP), GDP per capita at constant prices expressed in EUR2015 (SOVGDP) and Employment per capita (SNETDP). Countries included in the VoC classification (see table 8) are included. Only two regions are excluded due to missing data on observations prior 2008 on one or several variables. Respectively, NO0B Jan Mayen and Svalbard in Norway and ME00 Crna Gora in Montenegro. Since Montenegro only have this one NUTS-2 region, the study will therefore not include Montenegro.

Continental European Capitalism (CEC) VOC = 1	Austria	Social-democrat economics (SDE) VOC = 3	Denmark	Eastern and Central Europe capitalism (EAST) VOC = 5	Bulgaria
	Belgium		Finland		Hungary
	Czech Republic		Sweden		Poland
	France		Norway		Estonia
	Germany		Island		Latvia
	Luxembourg				Lithuania
	Netherlands		Romania		
Liberal market economics (LEM) VOC = 2	Ireland	Mediterranean capitalism (MED) VOC = 4	Portugal		Slovakia
	United Kingdom		Greece		Slovenia
			Italy		North Macedonia
			Spain		Serbia
			Malta		
			Cyprus		

Table 8: Countries included in the study and their VoC category

Based on the above, the sample covers 291 NUTS-2 regions with yearly data from 2000 – 2025. One region, UK13 Inner London – West, contains fairly extreme values on all variables in which influences the spread of the data. For robustness, analysis is also conducted without this region. If these results differ significantly from the initial results, they are commented.

In terms of sum NUTS-2 regions, CEC is the biggest with 106, whereas SDE is the smallest with 25. LEM includes 44 regions, MED 62 and EAST 54.

Table 9 presents mean value for different time periods for all three variables of interest. Both in total and by each VOC category. There is a clear tendency that all variables increase over time, which holds for alle VOC categories. The growth in employment seems less linear for MED and EAST, there is a slight drop in 2011-2015 before it increases after.

Variable		Time period					
		2000 -2005	2006 -2010	2011- 2015	2016 -2020	2021 -2025	2000 -2025
All	PPS ¹	2001 9.8	2404 8.2	2574 3.7	2874 5.4	3548 7.5	2654 7.8
	GDP ²	2578 7.1	2779 1.6	2802 5.8	2969 3.8	3132 3.0	2841 9.0
	Employment ³	0.440	0.452	0.447	0.464	0.478	0.456
CE	PPS ¹	2261 1.7	2679 0.1	2935 7.0	3259 4.0	3912 1.3	2980 7.0
	GDP ²	2933 2.7	3161 5.4	3254 3.8	3389 8.0	3497 8.4	3235 2.3
	Employment ³	0.446	0.458	0.465	0.476	0.488	0.466
LE	PPS ¹	2433 1.4	2780 4.5	2948 1.0	3305 6.7	3872 4.1	3043 5.4
	GDP ²	3639 0.2	3893 0.8	3964 5.2	4256 0.0	4558 0.2	4045 8.6
	Employment ³	0.476	0.481	0.476	0.494	0.498	0.484
SD	PPS ¹	2410 5.4	2985 1.2	3206 8.0	3462 4.6	4448 3.7	3268 3.5
	GDP ²	3954 0.6	4297 6.3	4360 0.2	4666 8.8	4758 8.3	4390 0.4
	Employment ³	0.487	0.498	0.490	0.497	0.505	0.495
ME	PPS ¹	1999 4.9	2344 7.1	2255 8.2	2464 2.9	3077 3.7	2411 8.4
	GDP ²	2302 2.8	2362 9.8	2165 2.2	2236 8.9	2401 7.1	2294 1.4
	Employment ³	0.424	0.435	0.404	0.425	0.445	0.426
EA	PPS ¹	9556. 0	1360 8.9	1633 5.1	1966 6.4	2696 4.4	1693 1.2
	GDP ²	6993. 9	8957. 4	9797. 1	1150 8.9	1339 4.7	1000 9.8
	Employment ³	0.398	0.418	0.417	0.446	0.469	0.429

¹ GDP per capita at current prices expressed in purchasing power standard (PPS)
² GDP per capita at constant prices expressed in EUR2015
³ Employment per capita

Table 9: Mean value for variables of interest by all VOC categories

6.2 Definitions and empirical strategy

We choose to use the definitions and methodology described by Eurofound in their work regarding EU convergence monitoring hub.⁷ More specifically, we seek out to measure two types of convergence, beta and sigma convergence.

⁷ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/publications/2018/upward-convergence-eu-concepts-measurements-and-indicators>. Eurofound base their approach on among others; Heichel, Pape & Sommerer (2005) and Phillips & Sul (2007;2009).

Beta-convergence, refers to whether those lagging behind catch up with the leaders in relation to a specific outcome. Whereas, *sigma-convergence*, is defined as a reduction in variation between countries/regions over time. Typically, one studies standard deviation (SD) or coefficient of variation (CV). We will focus on the latter as it is independent of the unit which it measures.

For both types, graphical presentations will be key to our analysis. However, we will also apply statistical methods for inference. As mentioned, *beta-convergence* relates to the catch-up process. Technically, this implies the computation of the following unconditional beta-convergence regression:

$$\Delta \log Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta \log Y_{it-1} + u_{it},$$

where $\Delta \log Y_{it}$ is the annual average growth rate for NUTS-2 region i over the whole time period t for the indicator of interest. Y_{it-1} is the indicator value at the start of the period, which in our case is the year 2000. Significant negative β indicates the existence of beta-convergence. For inference we will apply standard robust errors. We will not report regression results in table, but only comment in the text when relevant.

Sigma-convergence is often identified by a decrease in a function of variability, showing that a variable is becoming increasingly homogeneous over time (ref EUROSTAT). We calculate the coefficient of variation each year (CV_t) for all variables the following way:

$$CV_t = \frac{\sigma_t}{\mu_t}. \quad (1)$$

In (1), $\sigma_t = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{it} - \mu_t)^2 / N}$ is the standard deviation and $\mu_t = \sum_{i=1}^n x_{it} / N$ is the yearly population average. A decreasing CV over time indicates sigma-convergence. However, an increase in CV and also standard deviation suggest regions are diverging.

6.3 GDP per capita at current prices expressed in PPS

For beta-convergence we get the following results

Beta convergence: GDP at current market prices, expressed by PPS

Figure 9: Beta convergence all, GDP at current market prices

The slope coefficient is negative and significant, therefore signs of beta-convergence. The top-left graph shows all VOC's. In the rest of the graphs, we have cut out each VOC. EAST is clearly the one with highest growth rate, however some regions are behind. Also, it is EAST whom has the lowest starting value in 2000. This compared (in contrast) to SDE that start out at a higher level, but is less spread. For Beta-convergence within each VOC group, we get the following result:

Beta convergence within group: GDP, expressed by PPS

Figure 10: Beta-convergence within each VoC group for GDP

Here we see the following pattern:

- CEC: Significant and negative slope – beta convergence check
- LME: Significant at 90% and positive slope – no beta convergence. However, without Inner London West, the significance disappears, but still positive slope.
- SDE: Negative slope and significant at 90 % level
- MED: Negative slope and significant at 95 % level, good signs of beta convergence, but R2 low
- EAST: Negative and clearly significant. Clear signs of beta-convergence

The most striking (and promising) is perhaps the EAST countries, where beta convergence is high even if at lower level than CEC and SDE. However, we also see that some EST regions are really lagging. We have also calculated Sigma-convergence for the same variable. It gives us the following results:

GDP at current market prices, expressed by PPS

Figure 11: Sigma convergence GDP market prices

Based on this calculation, there are no clear signs of sigma convergence in Europe, but to some degree in EAST. However, the opposite in LME. In fact, the LME is an extreme case where divergence has significantly increased. This fact influences the overall sigma convergence. In contrast to the LME countries, we see much more converging tendencies in continental Europe. What we should also observe is that even if LME countries are on a very low divergence level, we might see some increased divergence the last years. Below we have plotted all regions excluding inner London (City of London) in the same type of plot we used in step 2.

Figure 12: Plotting PPS

The plot above illustrates the two tendencies; overall increase in PPS and increase spreading of regions.

6.4 GDP per capita at constant prices expressed in EUR2015

Below we look at Beta-convergence for all for GDP at constant prices. By using constant prices, we remove the effect created by inflation. Inflation might give illusion of change: The calculation is like this:

Beta convergence: GDP at fixed prices, EUR2015

Figure 13: Beta-convergence for all for GDP at constant prices

The calculated curves are negative and clearly significant. Therefore, also under assumption of constant prices there seems to be beta-convergence. Again, we can see the clustering of the different VOC. We then look at beta-convergence – within each VOC group. That gives us the following results:

Beta convergence within group: GDP fixed, EUR2015

Figure 14: Beta-convergence within each VOC group for GDP in constant prices

This calculation gives us the following result which is not very different from the one without fixed prices. The tendencies are the same, however, the results are less distinct that we saw with normal prices, indicating that the underlying difference to some extent is obscured by inflation. The tendencies are:

- CEC: Negative and significant, with good R2, beta-convergence
- LEM: Positive and non-significant, no signs of convergence. Bad R2
- SDE: Negative, but not significant
- MED: Negative and significant, beta-convergence
- EAST: Same as above, however, both with low R2

We have calculated sigma-convergence for the same variable. It gives us the following result:

GDP - constant prices, unit = EUR2015

Figure 15: Sigma convergence GDP in constat prices

Here we see signs of the opposite to the picture above: regions are not converging. Driven by LME, results change if Inner London west is dropped, as shown below.

Figure 16: Sigma convergence GDP in constat prices excluding inner London

We see above how tendency towards divergence is strong in LME but also to some extent in SDE, while all the other VOC's shows tendency to convergence. Again we have plotted all regions excluding City of London, in the same plot as in Step 2. The gives us the following picture.

Figure 17: Plotting GDP pr capita

The picture shows overall improvement with two main “hubs”, but also some increased spreading of regions.

6.5 Employment per capita

Below we have calculated beta-convergence on employment per capita for all regions.

Beta convergence: Employment per capita

Figure 18: Beta-convergence of employment per capita for all regions

The result shows negative and significant, signs of beta convergence. R2 seemingly ok with 0.2. Following this, we have calculated Beta-convergence – within each VOC group.

Beta convergence within group: Employment per capita

Figure 19: Beta-convergence of employment per capita for each VoC

The results are:

- CSC: Negative and significant at 95 % level. Beta-convergence
- LEM: Not significant and no negative slop. That changes when removing Inner London West, but still not significant.
- SDE: Significant and negative, so beta convergence. High R2 = 0.43
- MED: Same as above, R2 = 0.26
- EAST: Same as above but only 95%, R2=0.24

Furthermore, we have calculated sigma-convergence for the same variable:

Figure 20: Sigma-convergence of employment per capita

Again, results differ when excluding Inner London West.

Figure 21: Sigma-convergence of employment per capita excluding inner London

Excluding Inner London (City) the development is much smoother for all VoC. Excluding LME, we find convergence when it comes to employment. Below we have plotted all regions (again, excluding City).

Figure 22: Plotting Employment pr capita

The visual finding is that employment rate has increased and seems to have become more cohesive over the 25 years period. We discuss the more general conclusions from this analysis in chapter 8 below.

7. European governance and policy impacting regions

7.1 Policies towards regions

The European Union (EU) can only act in areas explicitly authorized by member states through the EU treaties, which specify the legislative authority of the EU, national governments, or both. The EU's authority is confined to what is expressly outlined in the treaties, emphasizing the principle of conferral. Furthermore, the EU adheres to the principles of proportionality, limiting its actions to what is necessary for treaty objectives, and subsidiarity, intervening only when it can demonstrate greater effectiveness than national governments. This ensures decision-making occurs at the most suitable level, aligning with the principle of subsidiarity.

The EU-internal market is a policy area where the EU has high level of competence. However, over the years the EU has managed to build up competence in many other areas (Cram, 1997). In some, such as migration, the EU and member states share competence, while with education the EU only support the member states. Thus, there are:

- Areas with *shared competence*: employment and social affairs, economic, social, and territorial cohesion, migration and home affairs.
- Areas with EU *supporting competence*: education and training.
- *Special competence*, enabling the EU to go beyond what is normally allowed under the treaties: coordination of economic and employment policies.

The open method of coordination (OMC) is a form of intergovernmental policy-making employed in areas where member states are hesitant to relinquish their competence, such as employment, social protection, education, youth, and vocational training (European Parliament, 2014). Unlike binding EU legislative measures, the OMC does not mandate member states to introduce or amend laws. Its foundation lies in collaborative goal-setting adopted by the Council, the establishment of joint measuring instruments, and benchmarking for comparing country performance and sharing best practices. The European Commission (Commission) oversees the monitoring of benchmarking, making the OMC a cooperative framework focused on shared objectives, standardized metrics, and cross-national comparisons.

The member states rely on different national governmental systems providing different degrees of regional autonomy – for example, a unitary vs. a federal system. In addition, several European regions have their own offices in Brussels. They may be differently organized and varies in terms of resources. Further, regions are also represented in the EU through the Committee of the Regions (CoR). CoR is an advisory body to the Union comprised of 329 locally and regionally elected representatives from the member states. The CoR share their opinion and give advice on EU legislation that have an impact on regions and cities. The political priorities for 2020- 2025 are divided into 3: Bringing Europe closer to its people (Future of Europe); Building resilient communities (Green Deal); and Cohesion- fundamental value (Cohesion alliance). Below we shortly comment on some of these policies (European Committee of the Regions, 2020).

7.2 Policies addressing economic transformation

Current Commission President, Ursula von der Leyen (UVDL), put forth her political priorities in July 2019, when she was still a candidate for the job. Under the heading: A Union that strives for more: My agenda for Europe: political guidelines for the next European Commission 2019-2024 (Von der Leyen, 2019), these include:

- A European Green Deal
- An economy that works for people
- A Europe fit for the digital age
- Protecting our European way of life
- A stronger Europe in the world
- A new push for European democracy

She wrote: “We will adapt and update as challenges and opportunities inevitably emerge, but we will always stick to the principles and the aspiration outlined in these guidelines. I see the next five years as an opportunity for Europe- to strive for more at home in order to lead in the world”. (Von der Leyen, 2019, p. 4). Thus, the overall political goals guiding the 2019-2024 Commission is the twin transition, working towards a green and digital Europe. The twin transition is supposed to guide all Commission initiatives and policies. Important for the green transition is the Commission’s growth strategy ‘the European Green Deal’ (EGD) from December 2019 (European Commission, 2019). The overall goal is to reach climate neutrality by 2050. In March 2020 the Commission put forth a new Circular Economy Action Plan and a new Industrial strategy (European Commission, 2020b, 2020c).

Furthermore, in response to the war in Ukraine the Commission proposed May 2022 REPowerEU, a plan to limit EU’s dependence on Russian oil and gas as well as support and fast forward the green transition (European Commission, 2022a). Initiatives includes diversifying the member states energy supplies, securing affordable energy supplies, saving energy, and investing in renewable energy.

March 2021 the Commission proposed the Net-Zero Industry Act (NZIA) to support the enhancement of Europe’s manufacturing capacity for net-zero technologies and address obstacles to scale up production within the region (European Commission, 2023b). It was developed to be able to deliver on the fit-for 55 and REPowerEU objectives. Nevertheless, enhancing manufacturing capacity in Europe necessitates the re- and up-skilling of the European workforce. Additionally, there is a demand for labour across both low and highly skilled occupations, underscoring the importance of facilitating legal labour migration within the Union.

7.3 Policies addressing social transformation

The goal of the NextGenerationEU is to emerge stronger from the pandemic, transform the economies, create opportunities and jobs for Europe. Rebuilding a post-covid-19 Europe to become greener, more digital and a more resilient Europe (Buti & Messori, 2020). The funds are actively addressing critical challenges in Europe and providing support to those in need. Following Russia’s aggression on Ukraine, the EU budget was mobilized to offer emergency assistance and support both in Ukraine and EU countries, focusing on alleviating the humanitarian consequences of the conflict.

At the core of NextGenerationEU is the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), a key instrument allocating grants and loans to aid reforms and investments in EU Member States. To access RRF funds, Member States must develop Recovery and Resilience Plans detailing their investment strategies. Additionally, they must meet specified milestones and targets, with disbursements contingent on the Commission’s assessment of their satisfactory fulfilment.

The remaining funds from NextGenerationEU are distributed to EU Member States through various EU programs, including the Recovery Assistance for Cohesion and the Territories of Europe (REACT-EU), Horizon Europe, InvestEU, European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, and the Just Transition Fund (JTF). These programs contribute to the comprehensive effort to address challenges and foster recovery and resilience across the European Union.

The funding from NextGenerationEU is based on EU borrowing on the markets. The Commission is also looking at introducing their own new resources to cover the repayments of NextGenerationEU such as the Emission Trading System (ETS) and carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM).

7.4 Policies addressing labour and skills

In 2019, the EU established the European Labour Authority (ELA), an EU agency, to assist member states and the Commission in enforcing EU rules on labour mobility and social security coordination are fair, straightforward, and efficient. The ELA is also tasked with facilitating and ensuring effective labour mobility in Europe, notably through the initiatives of European Employment Services (EURES). Thus, it supports the free

movement of workers by providing information, guidance, and assistance in resolving cross-border challenges. ELA commenced its operations in 2019 and is expected to be fully operational by 2024. Its headquarters are located in Bratislava, Slovakia. Moreover, building on the Juncker Commission's European Pillar of Social Rights (European Commission, 2021), the UVDL Commission put forth a European Pillar of Social Rights Action plan in March 2021.

The effective implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights is no more important than ever and greatly depends on the resolve and action of member states, who primarily hold responsibility for employment, skills and social policies. EU-level actions can complement national actions and this action plan is the Commission's contribution to the implementation of the social pillar principles, in line with the calls from European leaders and the European Parliament.

The action plan sets out three targets for 2030 in the areas of employment, skills and social protection, as well as being consistent with the UN's SDG:

- At least 78% of the population aged 20-64 should be in employment by 2030.
- At least 60% of all adults should participate in training every year.
- The number of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion should be reduced by at least 15 million by 2030.

A concrete action presented March 2021, under the European Pillar of Social Rights is the 'Recommendation of Effective Active Support to Employment' (EASE) (European Commission, 2021). EASE outlines a strategic plan for a gradual shift from the emergency measures implemented to protect jobs during the pandemic to new initiatives aimed at fostering a job-rich recovery. Through the EASE initiative, the Commission encourages job creation and job-to-job transitions, with a focus on the digital and green sectors.

The European Year of Skills (European Union, 2023) in 2023 aimed to tackle skills gaps in the European Union and enhance the EU skills strategy, with a specific focus on reskilling individuals in digital and green technology skills. This initiative involved facilitating the acquisition of appropriate skills for high-quality employment and assisting small and medium enterprises, emphasizing national efforts and existing/new EU initiatives and funding opportunities. The Year supported skills-related activities and events throughout Europe. Various stakeholders, including the Commission, the European Parliament, Member States, social partners, employment services, chambers of commerce, education providers, and workers and businesses, to collaborate to promote skills development.

Another initiative on skills is the European Skills Agenda (European Commission, 2023c), a five-year plan to help individuals and businesses develop more and better skills and to put them to use, by:

- strengthening sustainable competitiveness, as set out in the European Green Deal
- ensuring social fairness, putting into practice the first principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights: access to education, training and lifelong learning for everybody, everywhere in the EU
- building resilience to react to crises, based on the lessons learnt during the COVID-19 pandemic

The European Skills Agenda includes 12 actions organised around four building blocks: A call to join forces in a collective action, actions to ensure that people have the right skills for jobs, tools and initiatives to support people in their lifelong learning pathways, and a framework to unlock investments in skills.

7.5 Policies addressing labour migration

The EU has over the years developed more and more cooperation in the area on for example border control, such as Schengen Agreement and Frontex. However, legal migration is a shared competence between the EU and its member states. Only member states have the competence to decide on the number of nationals from non-EU countries being admitted to their territories for work. In the following, the focus is on how the EU recently has started to link migration to skills and employment, and thus view migration as part of the solution to demographic challenges within the union.

In November 2020, the Commission put forth a new EU Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion for 2021-2027 (European Commission, 2020a). The action plan promotes inclusive education and training, employment opportunities and skills recognition of people with a migrant background, access to health services and access to adequate and affordable housing. The action plan is also linked to the aims described in the European pillar of social rights action plan.

A couple of months earlier, in September 2020, the Commission put forth a 'New pact on Asylum and Migration' (European Commission, 2020d). In connection to this a revision of the Blue Card Directive took place. It will, among other things, allow highly qualified migrants to benefit from improved rights, and in particular the right to move and work in other EU countries, as well as quicker and streamlined procedures.

In April 2022 the Commission published a policy package on skills and talent: 'Attracting skills and talent to the EU' (European Commission, 2022b). This included proposing a revised Single Permit Directive and a revised Long Term Residents Directive. Regarding Talent Partnerships (with selected third countries – currently Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt, Bangladesh and Pakistan), a need to match real labour markets needs and skills in a tailor-made and flexible way on both sides is highlighted. Here the risk of brain drain should be transformed to brain gain. Both the European Skills Agenda and the New Pact on Migration and Asylum acknowledge the necessity for a strategic shift in legal migration. This involves a focus on effectively attracting and retaining talent to stimulate growth and innovation potential. Additionally, there is an emphasis on directing legal migration towards regions and occupations facing skills shortages. Over the past two decades, the EU has established a legal framework that significantly aligns the entry and residence conditions for specific categories of non-EU nationals across Member States. This framework encompasses labour-related purposes, including admission and residence for highly qualified workers (commonly known as "blue card" holders), seasonal workers, and intra-corporate transferees. Three key pillars of a sustainable EU policy on legal migration:

- a legislative pillar, recasting the Long-Term Residents Directive and the Single Permit Directive, to simplify the procedures for the admission of workers of various skill levels to the EU, and the mobility within the EU of workers from non-EU countries that are already in the EU, and improving their rights and their protection from labour exploitation;
- an operational pillar, addressing the challenge of international matching by setting out concrete steps to develop Talent Partnerships with key partner countries and the key features of an EU Talent Pool; and
- a forward-looking pillar, based on three specific priorities for action that should further guide the EU's policy on legal migration: care, youth and innovation.

In October 2023 the Commission presented a toolbox for addressing demographic change in Europe: 'Demographic change in Europe: a toolbox for action' (European Commission, 2023a). The EU encourages member states to apply the tools in national and regional contexts in a whole-of-government approach by addressing and managing demographic change focusing on 4 pillars:

- 1) support parents by better reconciling family aspirations and paid work, notably by ensuring access to quality childcare and good work-life balance;
- 2) supporting and empowering younger generations to thrive, develop their skills, facilitate their access to the labour market and to affordable housing;
- 3) empowering older generations and sustaining their welfare, through reforms combined with appropriate labour market and workplace policies;
- 4) where necessary, addressing labour shortages through managed legal migration, in full complementarity to harnessing talents from within the EU.

Furthermore, as part of the new pact on asylum and migration, the Commission published their 'Skills and Talent Mobility' package on November 15th, 2023 (European Commission, 2023d). The package aims to bridge the gap between employers and non-EU nationals, hoping to ease legal migration to the EU for non-EU nationals and match them with employers where there is a need for both low and high skilled labour. It also includes initiatives on making it easier for member states to recognize and approve non-EU citizens education

and qualifications. Regarding the proposal for a Talent Pool, it will be voluntary for the member states to join. It is dependent on the member states for its implementation. In addition, the member states will still be able to decide the volume of people they decide to take in as the initiative does not guarantee a resident permit. Initiatives includes:

- The Commission proposes a *regulation for establishing an EU talent pool*. The aim is to make the recruitment from outside the EU easier. However, it is voluntary for the member states to participate. In addition, the member states will need to support the management of the platform. The new EU talent pool will support the implementation of talent partnerships. It will build on EU's job mobility portal EURES.
- Recommendation on recognition of third country nationals' qualifications.
- A proposal for a *Council Recommendation 'Europe on the Move'*- learning mobility for everyone.

The Commission's proposal for an EU Talent Pool will now be negotiated by the European Parliament and the Council. The Commission will support Member States' implementation of the Recommendation on recognition of qualifications of third country nationals, and invite them to report on national initiatives, reforms, good practices and statistics. The Recommendation 'Europe on the Move' will be submitted to the Council for its consideration and adoption.

7.6 Policies addressing regional development and cohesion

EU policies on regional development has a long history.⁸ EU's cohesion policy aims to balance out countries and regions in the Union through strengthening the economic, social, and territorial cohesion. The cohesion policy is decided upon every seven years (same as the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF)). Initiatives includes the Interreg program.⁹ Below is a brief overview of EUs cohesion policy and current funds available for regional development.

Currently, the EU cohesion policy is set to deliver on political priorities, such as the green and digital transition. The focus is on delivering a 'just' transition, leaving no region behind. For the 2021-2027 period all parts and corners of Europe are to take part in the green and digital transition. It is designed to be more flexible and able to react to unforeseen challenges.

Five main objectives to drive investments:

- Smarter Europe: achieved through innovation, digitalization, economic transformation and SME support.
- Greener, carbon free Europe: implementing the Paris Agreement and investing in clean energy to fight climate change.
- Better connected Europe: with strategic transport and digital networks
- More social Europe: supporting social inclusion and delivering equal access to healthcare.
- Europe closer to citizens: based on locally-led strategies and sustainable urban development.

Furthermore, the regional funding is becoming more tailored. Even if it is still largely based on GDP per capita new criteria are added, such as youth unemployment, climate change and migrant integration. Furthermore, the rules for receiving funding have been simplified. In addition, regions have been divided into three categories. The list of regions eligible for funding from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) as allocated through the three categories of regions (European Union, 2021b) are:

⁸ For more information about the history of EU regional policy see: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/what/history_en

⁹ For more information about Interreg see: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/cooperation/european-territorial_en

- Less developed regions category, ex. ITF4 Puglia, ES61 Andalucia, HU31 Észak-Magyarország, and LT02 Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas.
- The transition regions category, ex. FRH0 Bretagne, FI19 Länsi-Suomi
- The more developed regions category, ex. FRK2 Rhône-Alpes, DE11 Stuttgart, NL32 Noord-Holland, IE05 Southern, ES21 País Vasco and CZ01 Praha.

Cohesion policy is delivered through 4 funds (European Union, 2021a). Recovery assistance for cohesion and the territories of Europe (REACT-EU)¹⁰ can also be mentioned here.

Fund	Notes
European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)	Created to enhance economic, social, and territorial cohesion across the European Union, the ERDF seeks to address regional disparities by promoting investments in a smarter, greener, more connected, and socially inclusive Europe that is closer to its citizens. The fund supports programmes managed jointly by the European Commission and national or regional authorities within member states. The member states administrations are responsible for selecting projects and overseeing their daily management.
Cohesion Fund (CF)	The Cohesion Fund supports member states with a gross national income (GNI) per capita below 90% of the EU 27 average, aiming to bolster the EU’s economic, social, and territorial cohesion. It funds’ investments in environmental initiatives and transport infrastructure (TEN-T). For the 2021-2027 period, the Cohesion Fund applies to Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia.
European Social Fund Plus (ESF+)	The European Union’s primary tool for investing in people and advancing the European Pillar of Social Rights is the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+). With a budget of nearly EUR 99.3 billion for the 2021-2027 period, the ESF+ continues to play a key role in supporting the EU’s employment, social, education and skills policies, including related structural reforms. As part of the EU’s cohesion policy, it aims to promote economic, territorial and social cohesion by reducing disparities between member states and regions. The ESF+ consolidates four previously separate funding instruments from the 2014-2020 period: the European Social Fund (ESF), the Fund for European Aid to the most Deprived (FEAD) the Youth Employment Initiative and the European Programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI).
Just Transition Fund (JTF)	The Just Transition Fund (JTF) is a new instrument under the 2021-2027 cohesion policy and serves as the first pillar of the Just Transition Mechanism within the European Green Deal, which seeks to achieve EU climate-neutrality by 2050. Its goal is support the people, economies, and environment of regions facing significant socio-economic challenges due to the transition towards a climate-neutral European Union.

Table 10: List of EU funds relevant for regions

Two years ago, the European Commissioner for Cohesion and Reforms, Elisa Ferreira, initiated a reflection on the future of cohesion policy. A high-level group of specialists, comprising experts from European, national, regional, and local policy actors, socio-economic partners, academia, and civil society, was convened for this purpose. The group was tasked with conducting an independent analysis of the current state of affairs and the implications for cohesion policy. Professor Rodríguez-Pose chaired the group, and a report was published in February 2024 (European Commission, 2024). The report underscores that a one-size-fits-all approach is

¹⁰ For more information about REACT-EU see: https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/react-eu_en

inadequate and emphasizes the necessity to better address and tailor policies to the diverse needs of different regions. This includes strengthening infrastructure and institution building. Moreover, the report suggests that cohesion policy should play a more significant role in other EU and national policies.¹¹

7.7 Policies addressing institutional transformation at regional level

The concept of Smart Specialisation has since its launch as a concept for stimulating the European economy in the wake of the financial crisis of 2008 (Foray et al 2009) been considered a main tool to engage European regions in a bottom-up – top-down arrangement. The bottom-up grip is defined by the need for regional actors to perform lessons of strategic planning through entrepreneurial discoveries, while the top-down take is represented by the Commission rewarding the effort politically and economically. Being piloted in 2011, the concept was made mandatory for regions wanted to access the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) from the budgetary period starting in 2014. As such, the concept was understood both as a remedy to fix the shortcomings of the Lisbon agenda, and as “a pillar in the fulfilment of the EU cohesion policy” (Wigger, 2023:31). Thus, the concept is understood as a means to serve the goals of economic, social and territorial cohesion alike, through “balanced economic growth and upward economic convergence” (Wigger, 2023:21).

To which extent Smart Specialisation is capable of delivering on these three dimensions of cohesion, is a highly disputed question, and one that requires the introduction of other factors. For instance, the role of institutional capacity to profit from the policy scheme, both at the national and the regional level, seems to be important (Medve-Bálint & Šćepanović, 2019; Morgan, 2017). In literature grouping nations or regions across nations such as club typologies (von Lynker & Thoennesen, 2017) or typologies for varieties of capitalism (Duranton et al, 2009; Hall & Soskice, 2001, Pinto et al, 2019), the institutional capacity is broadly understood as differing more from category to category than within categories. Whether this apply or not is both a theoretical and an empirical question. Purely empirical studies derive their conclusions from the testing of data models, while theoretically based model combine the presentation of data with qualitative analysis of underlying mechanisms. Basically therefore, the view on whether Smart Specialisation will serve to alleviate problems of inequality or unequal economic growth or not, depends on two important factors. The first is our valuation of the inherent mechanisms operating the global and the EU economy, and the second is the extent to which the concept integrates with other policy fields relevant to bring about cohesion.

As for the first question, the scholarly opinions differ in well-known ways between those holding a reformist perspective and those who do not (McCann & Ortega-Argilés, 2016, Morgan, 2017; Wigger, 2023). We don't intend to pursue this debate, beyond raising the question about the salience of comparative and competitive advantages, and the ability of these notions to function as openers to combat inequality. Concerning the second question, the observation is more interesting. Whereas Smart Specialisation is, more or less additionally, conceived as a tool to pursue cohesion and equality, it is not being institutionally coupled to policy areas that can serve to make an additional impact to bring about cohesion as aimed at through the scope of the GI-NI project. When issues from the EU social pillar is being brought into regional cases, it happens accidentally and not according to a systemically induced intention.

From the perspective of regional governance, this is unfortunate as our preliminary findings from work package 8.2. (Johnsen et al, 2024) suggest that policy fields with which we have to deal, such as education, skills and migration, presupposes strong interaction between national and regional authorities. It may follow from this that if Smart Specialisation is deemed a good integrator along the geographical steering chain, from the Commission via the states to the regions, for accomplishing bottom-up business development and economic renewal, it might be a good idea to bring the methodology onto the field of social integration to accomplish a broader take on bringing about prosperity and equality. But in order to perform in such a broader context, we further suggest considering the notion of collaborative advantage (Johnsen & Ennals, 2014) to supplement the

¹¹ A copy of the report and information about the meetings of the group can be found here: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/how/future-cohesion-policy_en

words comparative and competitive, not the least to highlight the need for concerted action across sectors, pillars and geographical levels to prevail in the rugged terrains of cohesion.

8. Concluding reflections

In this report, we aim to explore the patterns of regional divergence and convergence, as well as the distribution of institutional capacity across the European Union. Building on the relationship between regional resilience and the varieties of capitalism (VoC) typology, the foundation of this paper lies in understanding how key megatrends—specifically in the areas of technology, globalization, and migration—are shaping Europe. The interaction between these trends and regions is inherently reciprocal: while these global forces influence regions in different ways, the regions' responses to these challenges vary significantly. Consequently, by examining regional convergence and divergence across Europe, we may gain insights into the EU's capacity to manage major disruptions.

Over the period under discussion, Europe has faced significant challenges, including the financial crisis, the migration crisis, and various international disruptions. Despite these upheavals, regional development patterns generally follow positive trajectories, although notable exceptions exist. Against this backdrop, this paper builds on the VoC framework to address three key questions: (a) How are European regions (at the NUTS-2 level) performing in terms of socioeconomic variables? (b) What are the development patterns when comparing NUTS-2 regions within different VoC categories across key socioeconomic indicators? (c) What are the trends in development when measuring sigma and beta convergence of NUTS-2 regions across these indicators?

These questions are explored through a structured, three-step approach. First, we considered a broad range of indicators and conducted case studies of select regions to provide a comprehensive view of their socioeconomic performance. In the second step, we focused on a narrower set of indicators, analysing the development patterns across all regions and within the various VoC categories. Finally, we conducted a sigma and beta convergence analysis across three key indicators to measure regional convergence over time.

In conclusion, we discuss the EU's policy toolbox for addressing regional disparities, highlighting policies that target economic, social, and institutional development. By examining these areas, the report offers a nuanced understanding of how regions across Europe are coping with large-scale challenges and where further policy interventions may be needed.

Some key findings of this report highlight, firstly, that we find the Varieties of Capitalism (VoC) framework to be a highly insightful lens for understanding regional development patterns across Europe. Throughout all three stages of our analysis, a clear VoC pattern consistently emerges, offering valuable perspectives on the divergence and convergence among regions. Perhaps the most striking finding is the significant progress made by Eastern European countries, which have markedly caught up with the rest of Europe over the past 25 years. This convergence is particularly noteworthy compared to the more gradual and less pronounced development observed within other VoC configurations.

In contrast, the development patterns within other VoC groups, such as the Mediterranean (MED) countries, are less dynamic. The MED regions, in particular, seem constrained by their social models, which appear to maintain them within a specific trajectory, limiting their ability to break out of established patterns and improve their socioeconomic position. This rigidity presents challenges for regions attempting to elevate their performance beyond their current developmental stage. Moreover, while some individual regions have exceeded expectations, showing impressive improvement, others continue to lag behind. These outliers underscore the complexity of regional disparities and highlight the need for nuanced policy responses.

Addressing these differences presents a significant challenge, especially when viewed through the lens of general policy principles. On the one hand, the European Union seeks to promote cohesion across all regions, striving to reduce disparities and ensure more equitable development. On the other hand, the EU also aims to foster innovation and drive improvement, which often requires tailored, flexible policies that may not align with the uniformity required for cohesion. Striking a balance between these two goals—cohesion and innovation—will likely prove to be one of the major challenges for regional policy moving forward.

Crafting policies that are both flexible enough to accommodate regional specificities while also supporting overarching EU objectives of integration and innovation will be crucial. This tension between fostering regional competitiveness and maintaining social and economic cohesion will require innovative policy approaches to

ensure that no regions are left behind, while simultaneously enabling others to continue their upward trajectory.

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Growing Inequality: a novel integration of transformations research — GI-NI

Coordinator

Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO, Netherlands

Consortium

CNAM – CEET, Centre d'études de l'emploi et du travail (France)
University of Groningen (Netherlands)
Centre for European Policy Studies (Belgium)
University of Adger (Norway)
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